

Assessment of tree-based ecosystem services for urban resilience – *Case study in Turrialba, Costa Rica*

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Master's thesis

Assessment of tree-based ecosystem services for urban resilience

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Abstract

The urban challenges we are facing together with climate change call for enhancement, monitoring and management of the urban natural capital to improve the resilience of urban ecosystems. Trees are remarkable components of the urban landscape that can adapt to rough biotic and abiotic changes while influencing other processes to transition smoothly towards a new equilibrium, namely metastatic resiliency. While there is a need to refocus on local resources instead of importing from outside city boundaries and to influence the transition to a sustainable city, urban trees appear to be a great tool. Urban forests are proved to offer a multiple range of benefits among others improving air quality, improving hydrology, saving energy, sequester carbon, removing anthropogenic air pollutants, increasing property values and economic development, improving human health and well-being, protecting biodiversity and provision of wildlife habitat. While scientific knowledge exists, there is a need to turn it into readily available information that can promote efficient urban planning decisions integrating urban forestry. This implies understanding the structure, function and value of the urban forest we want to enhance. In this respect, the urban forest assessment software *i-Tree Eco* developed by the US Forest Service has been tested on a study area located in a tropical region: Turrialba, Costa Rica. Local data availability is poor and the study reveals the need to improve input data to use the software on such a location. However, the model revealed a lot of various uncertainty sources resulting in misleading outputs particularly on hydrology clearly unsuitable to strong rain events. Yet, the model's strengths lie in urban forest structural estimations through partitioning of the study area, in raising awareness of the multiple benefits of urban trees and in providing a framework to include urban forests in decision-making. Eventually, it should be investigated beforehand if *i-Tree Eco* is adapted to the purpose of the study. The quantitative assessment of hydrology benefits was found to be more reliable on i-Tree Hydro model, based on more advanced water balance and also providing storm analysis. Except for storm analysis, i-Tree models do not account for the benefits of trees under climate change conditions, neither for urban trees modified processes due to urban stressors. To reflect the availability of climate-ready trees in decision-making processes, a multi-criteria framework is suggested in this paper. Anyhow, integrating urban forestry in decision-making goes through shifting from classic optimisation methods to multi-variable methods seeking a consensus of several scenarios dealing with different information natures including non-market ecosystem services. Recommendations also include the need to capture heterogeneity of the urban forest within the urban landscape, which is not reflected by i-Tree softwares. Mapping methods or satellite image analysis are essential decision-making supports and allow to identify canopy cover distribution useful for

green network design, or to understand local effects of trees in relationship with the local environment. Qualifying tree-based ecosystem services also goes along with participatory methods to capture intangible benefits and to improve decision-making to more holistic and inclusive processes.

Preface

This Master's thesis was realized as a final project of a Master's degree in Environmental Engineering at the Technical University of Denmark combined with the Climate-KIC Master Label Programme from the European Institute of Innovation and Technology, corresponding to 32.5 ECTS. It was carried out abroad at the Watershed Department of the Tropical Agricultural Research and Higher Education Center (CATIE) located in Turrialba, Costa Rica. The project was undertaken from November, 18th, 2019 to May, 4th, 2020, under the supervision of Andreas Ibrom, Associate Professor at DTU Department of Environmental Engineering, and Laura Benegas, Head of CATIE's Watershed Department.

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*“Si tu peux voir détruit l’ouvrage de ta vie
Et sans dire un seul mot te mettre à rebâtir,
Ou perdre en un seul coup le gain de cent parties
Sans un geste et sans un soupir
Si tu peux être amant sans être fou d’amour,
Si tu peux être fort sans cesser d’être tendre,*

*Et, te sentant haï, sans haïr à ton tour,
Pourtant lutter et te défendre; [...]
Et, ce qui vaut mieux que les Rois et la Gloire
Tu seras un homme, mon fils.”*

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1. Background overview

In the past 100 years, human society has gone through two very dramatic changes. Firstly, the population has quadrupled to currently reach 7.7 billion inhabitants, and secondly, we have become an urban species [1]. In 1900, 86% of humanity lived in the countryside and in 2018 more than 55% of us now live in cities of more than 100,000 people. A number which is expected to rise to 70% by 2050. This urbanization will particularly impact the development of megacities. Nowadays, there are 36 mega-cities with 10 million or more people, compared to just eight 20 years ago.

At the same time, climate change is expected to increase the frequency and severity of natural disasters and extreme weather conditions, such as floods, droughts and heat waves. These affect urban areas increasing temperature levels and threatening human health and biodiversity. In this climate urgency, it is paramount to enhance capacities in carbon capture, water retention and warming mitigation which are insufficient and especially in urban areas [2].

Based on research, the Stockholm Resilience Centre has proposed a concept of Planetary Boundaries [3], where they identify a “safe operating space for humanity”. The Earth systems considered to be affected most heavily by human activity are the *biological diversity* and *biochemical flows*, followed by *land-system change*. As a consequence, the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment [4] has documented that over 60% of ecosystem services were deteriorated or are already overused.

“How can we take better advantage of the benefits and minimize the negative impacts of urbanization? How do we create cities that are more ecologically sustainable and resilient to fluctuations in internal and external environmental forces, and that provide healthier conditions so that people can not only exist but also thrive?” are the question raised by Carreiro et al. (2007) [5].

There is an obvious need to create cities that are more resource efficient and more resistant to economic and environmental fluctuations, offering healthier conditions for the populations. To do this, we must find ways to work “with” instead of “against” nature [6]. We need to find ways to partner with the natural world to solve environmental problems notably through *nature-based* solutions contrasting with costly engineered solutions. Nature should no longer be seen as a consumer good or a commodity but should become part of our solutions to adapt to changing global conditions.

Urban dwellers suffocate in extreme heat, breathe poor quality air and live under mental stress partly due to the urban environment. Such living conditions lead to a growing interest in biophilic cities; cities closer to nature, hosting biodiversity and containing natural places localized so as to be crossed regularly by the inhabitants. The eco-city movement, embraced by many environmentalists and urban designers around the world, is re-examining the benefits and services derived from natural and semi-natural habitats in and around cities [7]. Now, about 30 years old, it has provided a venue for supporting projects, creating networks, and accelerating transdisciplinary exchange of information on urban sustainability, and has hosted many international conferences since 1990.

More and more, the urban nature and green infrastructure of cities will be used to adapt to climate change and, to some extent, to mitigate it. Studies highlight the contributions of nature, also called ecosystem services, to improve the quality of life and contribute to human well-being. *The Value of Urban Life* poster Appendix L. illustrates how nature contributes to improving the lives of the cities' inhabitants and their surrounding regions [8]. Broadly speaking, the ecological advantages of urban nature relate to the improvement of water and air quality, stormwater management, mitigation of temperature variations, protection of biodiversity and wildlife habitat, carbon storage and other social benefits. At the societal and cultural level, urban green infrastructures promote tourism and recreational activities, offer educational opportunities and contribute to safer cities.

Trees, in particular, are a vital component of urban green infrastructure, providing many valuable ecosystem services. Urban forest ecosystems contribute greatly to urban resilience. About 50 years ago, the US government created a new division within the US Forest Service called Urban Forestry. Giving urban forestry its own political identity has stimulated the growth of the scientific developments in this area at many universities around the world [5]. There is now a large body of knowledge on the ecological, economic and social role of trees, in and near cities.

2. Project aim

The first purpose of this project is to investigate why trees are particularly relevant to increase urban resiliency. Then, how to assess the benefits provided by trees within the *ecosystem services* perspective to reflect the added value they can provide to cities' planning projects. Indeed, integrating ecosystem services in decision-making processes is a real challenge.

A case study located in Turrialba, Costa Rica basically aimed to assess the ecosystem services brought by the local urban forest with the US-based software *i-Tree Eco*. However, the aim of study had to be adapted due to scarce local meteorological data availability and to limitations of the software, poorly adaptable to other regions than to the United States. As such, the problematic has shifted to: What can a city with scarce data availability like Turrialba do to qualify tree-based ecosystem services with a tool such as *i-Tree Eco* with the purpose of inte-

grating them to sustainable urban planning decisions? Is there an inevitable need to improve the data or can we perform a relevant qualitative analysis with what is available?

Indeed, engineers also have to cope with less developed areas with scarce data availability which makes it impossible to use complex data-demanding tools and/or to analyse the local situation with relevant trustable numbers including reasonable uncertainty. In fact, even in this type of situation, it is important to be able to come up with results, if not quantifiable then qualifiable that can be used in decision-making and informing purposes. In such settings, common sense and expert opinion are particularly valuable. Moreover, communicating in a way that non-experts can understand is incredibly important for the scientific community. This type of communication can be performed thanks to results from qualitative analysis. Besides, benefits of trees are proved by scientific papers but a lack of methodology to use those results in direct decision-making is also proved which broadens the scope to: “which valuation and decision-making methods are the most suitable for tree-based ecosystem services?”.

After defining and giving valuable insight on both *urban resilience* and *urban forests*, the ecosystem services derived by urban trees will be explored from literature review. Then the case study of Turrialba City in the Cartago province of Costa Rica will be introduced and detailed from presentation to methodology and results. In a next chapter, *i-Tree Eco* model will be discussed and recommendations will be given on different aspects.

The focus of this study is made on the benefits of trees to human well-being and to the environment through physical processes of trees, and not through the more abstract recreational, aesthetic or meditative services delivered by trees. The analysis of the latter more intangible ecosystem services is based on participative and survey analysis and will be complementary to the analysis of physical ecosystem services provided by trees.

Chapter 2: Urban resilience and urban forest

1. Urban resilience

1.1 Defining the city

Within the ecology and environmental science literature, limited attention is given to the definition of cities as an entity and it tends to be assumed [9]. When cities have been defined, they have most often been conceptualized as entities separate and distinct from “natural” or rural areas. Scientific researchers rely on the definition of city as either by population, built-up area or specific land-use type (e.g., residential, commercial) in comparison to natural areas [9]. Another alternative is to use impervious surfaces reflecting human settlement and impact [10]. Moreover, some environmental researchers have integrated the term “urban ecosystem” [4] to promote the city’s ecological structure and functions such as natural ecosystems. Through the use of the urban ecosystem concept, research frameworks emerged integrating socioeconomic dynamics and relating these to multiscale environmental outputs (within and outside the city) [11].

An urban system is highly dependent on importing resources extracted beyond its landscape. All urban systems rely on food, fuels, and materials from elsewhere, and all cities work as marketplaces. Cities usually cannot manage all waste they generate and export it to their hinterland, mostly polluting the environment. Figure 2.1 represents material flows through an urban system with inputs, additions to stock and outputs. This representation reflects the definition of an urban ecosystem: “open system, in which energy, materials, and organisms move into, through,

Figure 2.1: Material flow over an urban system [12]

and out of the system” [5].

Ferrao and Fernandez (2013) [12] present these processes in an *urban metabolism* assessment framework which connects resources, urban biogeochemical and socioeconomic processes (providing housing, goods and services, transportation of people and goods), and exports.

This representation of the city describes the current configuration of city metabolisms, mostly linear. This way, cities are vulnerable due to their resource dependency imposing stresses on the local supply and damaging the natural environment during both resource extraction and waste disposal. In addition, urbanization significantly alters stream flows and water quality due to increased impervious surfaces, increased pollutants emitted from various sources and decrease in vegetation cover. These changes bring to increased stormwater runoff, potential floods and alters well-being and human health [12].

In the future, resource and material flows might be altered and may require systemic changes such as reducing urban dependence on external resources. This requires a focus on the inner stocks of cities representing a buffer to the risk of an altered linear flow. Increasingly relevant, this focus on local resources would enhance the resilience of urban systems. In fact, cities may be considered as “resources reservoirs”. The concept of “urban harvesting” is introduced by Agudelo-Vera et al. (2012) [13] as a management tool to change inefficient linear system into sustainable urban metabolism: “closing cycles by harvesting urban resources”. Revaluing the nature in cities that has a potential to be a resource for many services to the city dwellers and the environment, could be part of what can be harvested directly within the city rather than looking for these services outside of the city.

Another way to define cities is to compare their metabolism to natural neighbour areas. Comparatively, nature is illustrating how extreme cities have become: cities and natural ecosystems differ greatly in their main energy sources, origin of matter, surfaces and vertical structures, direction of energy and material flows and waste disposal methods. Almost all material is recycled in natural ecosystem, whereas in cities almost no material cycling exists; origin of matter is local in natural terrestrial ecosystem, whereas it is outsourced in cities [5]. The idea of *urban ecology* is to minimize those differences showed Table 2.1.

Feature	Cities	Natural ecosystems
Main energy source(s)	Fossil fuels (coal, petroleum, natural gas), nuclear power	Solar
Origin of nutrients and other materials	Mostly external	Mostly internal
Surface and structure	Surface sealed; vertical structure dominated by artificial hard surfaces	Permeable soil surfaces; structure dominated by vegetation in most cases
Flow of energy and material	High input-output systems for materials; almost no internal cycling of matter	High percentage of matter recycled within the system
Waste disposal	Large number of dumping sites often far from the city	Nutrient export low

Table 2.1: Important ecological differences between cities and natural terrestrial ecosystems [5]

Urbanization, defined as the alteration of natural habitat into a landscape consisting mainly of grey infrastructure, results in a lot of abiotic changes not taken into account in this definition. Urban animals and plants are evolving consequently. For example, seeds growing out of pavement cracks can foster reproduction by generating heavy and compact seeds designed to fall close to the plant [14]. Schilthuizen (2019) [15] proves that these organisms are on their way to becoming very *urban species*.

Although urbanization brought measurable benefits to human societies such as labor forces concentration and extensive transportation facilitating large-scale production and trade as well as higher overall living standards, the outcome is negative on the environment, on human health and on well-being [5].

Indeed, cities are becoming increasingly stressed by environmental and social factors such as unequal resources and services allocation, hotter mesoclimates, flooding, poor air and water quality, water scarcity. But the economist John Kenneth Galbraith stated: “The test of the quality of life in an advanced economic society is now largely in the quality of urban life”. Indeed, the urban landscape became the reference biotope for humankind which also has become an *urban specie*. Hence, increasing urban life quality is an urgent and vital issue.

1.2 Urban conditions

Urban environments form microclimates that differs on many variables to the surrounding rural area. Those differences are exposed Figure 2.2.

Climatic parameters	Characteristics	Compared to the surrounding area
Air pollution	Gaseous pollution	5–25 times more
Solar radiation	Global solar radiation	15–20% less
	Ultraviolet radiation	15–20% less
	Duration of bright sunshine	5–15% less
Air temperature	Annual mean average	0.5–1.5°C higher
On clear days	2–6°C higher	
Wind speed	Annual mean average	15–20% less
Calm days	5–20% more	
Relative humidity	Winter	2% less
	Summer	8–10% less
Clouds	Overcast	5–10% more
Precipitation	Total rainfall	5–10% more

Table 2.2: Average difference in climatic parameters of built-up areas compared with surrounding rural areas [16]

The city’s topography, surroundings, density, street network, shade due to different heights buildings and the type and amount of urban vegetation, influence those factors which contribute in a synergetically forming urban microclimates. For example, there is less solar radiation due to high air pollution but the latter also traps heat. Studies also show that higher atmospheric particulate concentrations (providing condensation nuclei for water [17]) in cities increases clouds and rainfall.

Pollution

Vehicle traffic mainly contributes to air pollution in urban areas, generating gaseous pollutants, such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur dioxide (SO_2), carbon monoxide (CO), methane (CH_4), non-methane volatile organic compounds ($NMVOC_s$), ammonia (NH_3), and particulate matter [18]. Ozone (O_3) is formed through chemical reactions involving NO_x and volatile organic compounds [19]. Moreover, adding excessive lawn nitrogen fertilizing and nitrogen contained in human waste, N has significantly increased in urban ecosystems [20].

PM10 and PM2.5 particulate matter are associated mainly with road-transport emissions but other human activities can also produce PM10, such as combustion of fossil fuels in power stations, industrial processes, construction, and chemical reactions involving gaseous pollutants [19]. Particulate matter contains organic compounds, hydrocarbons, acid aerosols, and metals attached or adsorbed to a carbonaceous core [18]. Key pollutants are the traffic related elements called TREs i.e. Cd, Mn, Cu, Mo, As, Sb, Zn, together with Pd, Pt, and Rh [21]. TREs, N and S can precipitate directly on ground surfaces, or first accumulate in the atmosphere and then fall on ground surfaces through rain. For this reason, the presence of TREs is not only in the atmosphere but also in road dust, soils, vegetation and represent a major risk factor for

human health as well as for the environment.

Heat-island effect

Heat-island effect is an urban microclimate phenomenon characterized by local temperature elevation in urban areas in comparison to neighbour boundary areas (up to 3°C higher in tropical urban areas and 1.5°C in temperate ones [5]). The elevated air temperature comes often with a reduced relative humidity.

Figure 2.2: Heat-island effect; comparison of surface and air temperatures during day and night from city centre to boundaries [22]

The heat-island effect phenomenon is more pronounced during the night than during the day and has different origins: thermal (1), radiative (2), hydric (3), aerodynamic (4) and anthropogenic (5).

(1) Urban surfaces have a great thermal capacity. Heat stored through conduction in the ground and in materials during the day is high and it is restored during the night limiting urban atmosphere nocturnal cooling.

(2) During the day, the heat-island effect favours increase of temperatures of urban surfaces due to their low albedo. Comprised between 0 (no reflection at all) and 1 (perfect mirror), most of urban surfaces have an albedo value close to 0 since their color is dark except if light painting is used then it is between 0.3 and 0.9; grass has an albedo between 0.25 and 0.30

and trees between 0.15 and 0.18 which is also low [23]. During the night, heat loss is limited through infrared radiation.

(3) When natural soils area is limited, latent heat flux corresponding to evaporation is limited.

(4) Irregularity of urban elements (buildings, streets, etc.) limit ground wind speeds, air renewal and heat extraction.

(5) Anthropogenic activities (industry, air conditioning, transportation, etc.) release heat.

Figure 2.3: Influence of tree greenways on the microclimate of a canyon street [24]

On Figure 2.3, physical processes are represented by 1: evapotranspiration, 2: net radiation, 3: leaf radiation interception, 4: conduction/convection, 5 : comfort. It shows how trees modify their environment by intercepting radiation through leaf area, by evapotranspiration avoiding overheating of the leaves and consuming part of the received energy through radiation.

In some small open spaces in cities this difference can be as much as 5°C [25]. During the day, wide streets, squares, and non-vegetated areas are the hottest parts, while at night, narrow streets have higher temperatures than the rest of the city [26]. Consequently, a big investment is allocated in reaching the comfort zone inside buildings [5] altered by temperature increase.

Hydrology

Urban landuse significantly modifies the hydrological cycle by transforming pathways and behaviours. Vegetation cover removal reduces water interception, soil compaction and impervious cover expansion reduce infiltration and lowers soil moisture and groundwater recharge [27]. It brings to the increase of peak runoff from precipitation events and to collection of pollutants leading to the loss in water quality [28]. Consequently, heavy investments are allocated to stormwater drainage systems to avoid floodings.

1.3 Defining urban resilience

Different definitions of the term *resilience* were found in literature:

“Resilience is a measure of robustness and buffering capacity of the system to changing conditions” [29].

“Resilience is the tendency of a system to stay in its current vegetation state (high resilience) or to switch to another state (low resilience)” [30].

“The capacity of individuals, communities, and systems to adapt, survive, and grow in the face of stress and shocks, and even transform when conditions require it” [31].

By considering the city as the “system” mentioned in above definitions, and climate change as the “changing conditions”, this concept can be applied to urban areas.

The “landscape self-organizing complexity” principle suggests that urban landscapes are spatially extended complex systems able to self-organize [32]. “Self-organization is the capacity of complex systems to develop and change internal structures spontaneously and adaptively in order to cope with or manipulate their environment” [33]. From this perspective emerged several relevant ideas to understand urban resilience: “(1) local interactions play a critical role in the formation of regional and global patterns, while large scale factors set constraints; (2) the exact behaviour of complex systems is inherently unpredictable; (3) the traditional system stability based on homeostatic equilibrium is unachievable and (4) system metastability (or nonequilibrium resilience) is determined primarily by the system’s internal diversity, flexibility, and adaptability in response to unpredictable environmental changes” [5].

Applied to cities, since they have a large number of diverse elements interacting nonlinearly, it is extremely difficult or impossible to precisely predict the ecological future of such systems, no matter the amount of information that is available on them [34]. However, urban ecosystem dynamics can be understood and influenced, with the purpose of facilitating the system to cope with environmental uncertainties and extreme events. What is more, it is shown that degradation thresholds have been crossed in many urban natural habitats, thus irreversibility has been reached and ecological succession alone cannot restore ecosystems without human intervention [35]. Within this perspective, human-beings are not only considered as source of disturbances but as an affected component of the complex system that has an important role to play in shaping dynamics as the most active actors in cities. Hence, in order to build resilient

cities able to cope with unpredicted responses, it is important to frame our thinking beyond *homeostatic stability* thinking [5] (equilibrium state conservation as a response of resisting to perturbations).

In this study there are two forms of resilience to differentiate:

- The urban resilience to climate change where trees can play a significant role;
- The resilience of urban trees to the various stressors partly intensified by climate change.

In other words, how do urban trees impact urban environment and how does urban environment impact urban trees? In that respect, urban resilience designates a dual consideration.

Finally, previous parts of the report justified the need for change in the direction of an increased sustainable urban resilience to face future extreme changes.

2. Urban forest characteristics

Urban forests are recognized to deliver various benefits to urban dwellers and to urban environment. However, to measure the contribution of urban forests in building more resilient cities, the impact of urban environments on urban trees must be understood.

Figure 2.4, with the approach and style of planetary boundaries, gives an overview of the different stresses affecting natural forests and how they are expected to change in the future compared with preindustrial background levels [30]. Urban forests, in comparison are facing the same categories of stresses which are intensifying with climate change, including human, climate, abiotic and biotic stressors. Stressors listed in the Figure 2.4 are also applicable to urban forests excluding demand for wood and fires which could be replaced by human related stresses such as urban infrastructures, vandalism and deferred maintenance.

Figure 2.4: Stresses and disturbances affecting forests and their expectation to change in the future compared with preindustrial levels [30]

Within abiotic stressors, there is a complex system of factors [36]: soil compaction, altered temperature and moisture patterns (high soil temperatures, poorly drained soil, increased vapor pressure deficits due to urban heat-island effect), soil alkalisation/neutralisation [37] (more

common due to concrete chemistry) or acidification both impediments to tree health (alkalinisation more than acidification since disturbed urban soil is rarely too acid) [38], insufficient rooting volume, high concentration of salts, excessive nutrient input such as nitrogen and sulfur from different anthropogenic sources [20] or inversely nutrient deficiency due to interrupted nutrient cycles [38].

Adding these abiotic stresses to the fact that during transplanting (for non-seeded trees) trees lose much of their root system, it results in a high rate of urban tree planting failure.

Stresses are placed into categories but there are many connections among them. For example, a tree stressed by drought may have fewer reserves and be more vulnerable to insect or disease outbreak [30]. Moreover, although some disturbances can promote forests resilience (e.g. elevated CO₂, increased deposition of nutrients from pollution), stressors usually impact forests negatively and have increased in intensity and frequency over the past decades. On Figure 2.4, question marks represent big uncertainty, either on how current levels exceed preindustrial background conditions or how levels are expected to evolve in the future [30].

Green area in the Figure reflects the level of stress that falls within the range of “background” variability to which forests are adapted, are healthy and maintain healthy environmental processes. Very high levels of disturbance (red area in Figure 2.4) are conducive to risks such as loss of soil nutrients, of seed banks and ways to disperse them. Consequently, at these levels, forest’s intrinsic processes are degraded and their ability to recover is reduced. In such extreme cases, a shift to a new vegetation state is likely. The challenge is to define at which point the trajectory changes, which levels of stresses are the limit and if the transition is abrupt or linear (orange area in Figure 2.4) [30].

These multiple stressors inhibit free of charge ecosystem services to society and they must then be replaced by expensive engineered solutions [39].

Under the *urban ecosystem* perspective, altering the urban forest will alter the flows passing through the city. If we look at biodiversity, the flow of species through the city should also be part of elements going through the city, such as other nature flows (water, air, etc.). Thus, since most of urban areas represent a discontinuity in biotic corridors by disconnecting nature areas with build-up concrete and impervious areas, one of the criteria of urban greenspace design is to design connectivity known as the “landscape connectivity” principle. For this purpose, basic landscape elements to be considered are patches (green areas), corridors (linear belts), and matrix (surrounding built-up areas). Although much of the vegetation in cities is planted and managed, biotope islands or remnant forest patches exist in many dense cities [5]. A case study in Frankfurt-am-Main demonstrates the possibility of successfully maintaining natural reserves, even though surrounded by dense built-up areas [40].

Altering the forest through urbanization will also alter the microbial flows. In a forest, trees “talk” via mycorrhizal fungi that colonize the plant’s root system and develop a symbiosis called “mycorrhiza” [41]. An almost microscopic network is formed in which nutrients, water, CO₂, and even information such as signals about pests and disease are exchanged enabling biological communication. These microbes are essential for healthy soil and consequently for

healthy urban ecosystems. However, these fungal networks through which forests and plant systems self-regulate are highly fragmented in cities. It was found that urban environments have lower microbial activity and diversity compared to rural or natural ecosystems [42] and urban forestry literature frequently reports high mortality rates and low average lifespans for street trees [43].

Another approach to increase our understanding on how an urban area might affect species composition and biochemical processes is the *urban-rural gradient* approach [5] comparing urban forests with similar reference areas outside the city. For example, two studies used this approach to determine whether relationships exist between urban land use and atmospheric inputs to soil nitrogen cycling in urban forests. Typically, large forests far from urban areas receive from 60% to 80% of their annual nitrogen needs from locally recycled, microbially mineralized nitrogen [44] and the rest comes from atmospheric deposition. Within cities, the amount of nitrogen available for urban forest may increase due to both high nitrate gaseous emission rates as well as heat-island effect increasing microbial production of inorganic nitrogen. Knowing natural forest processes outside cities, this approach may enable by comparing responses to hypothesize on the forest conditions within cities and if processes are impacted in urban forest remnants. The above mentioned studies found that urban forest remnants behave as nitrogen sources rather than as nitrogen sinks as it would be the case in natural ecosystems [5].

Although researchers have predicted how natural forests respond to climate change [45], responses of urban forests to climate disturbances are unknown. Indeed, their species composition is very diverse and non-native compared to natural forests. However, as an emerging field, specific studies about tree roots have been carried out although the need for more research in this field is highlighted by Brunner et al. (2015) [46]. Following findings testifying the potential adaptability of trees especially through roots, are mentioned later in this paper. At higher soil pH, micro-nutrients (B, Cu, Fe, Mn, and Zn) lack to exist in soluble forms that can be uptaken by trees, and phosphorus is also less available. Alkaline soil may also alter mycorrhiza composition and abundance which can degrade root colonization process and therefore nutrient uptake capacity. However, root adaptations enhancing Fe uptake have been observed, such as through production of a specialized enzyme to reduce Fe [38]. Another example is that roots may be able to selectively exclude salt ion uptake to tolerate saltwater [46].

In order to overcome growing urban stressors and succeed to grow an urban forest ensuring urban sustainability, recommendations on how to manage urban forest in terms of species choice through so-called “climate-ready” species, will be presented in chapter 5). This strategy, part of a greater urban forestry plan, could influence the urban ecosystem to a new state and avoid the catastrophic scenario predicting complete irreversible disturbance of current urban ecosystem and large mortality of urban forests.

Chapter 3: Ecosystem services provided by urban forest

By influencing urban ecosystem dynamics to a new stable state (non homeostatic stability) more resistant to extreme climate conditions and climate uncertainty, what is commonly called “climate adaptation”, system metastability can be achieved to ensure urban (nonequilibrium) resilience (see Part 1.3).

Trees have always adapted to their changing environment, sometimes in unpredictable ways, at a time scale contrasting to the Darwinian notion that evolution could never be seen in a single lifetime [47]. With this remarkable ability to adapt, urban forests represent a great tool to influence flow dynamics in urban environments and have a great potential to adapt processes through which they survive to climate change, and consequently support the other elements and processes of the urban ecosystem to resist (through adapting soil processes, hosting biodiversity thus protecting species survival processes contributing to the whole ecosystem, mitigating anthropogenic pollutant emission processes, mitigating heat-island effect processes, adapting by protecting human-beings from health problems intensified with climate change).

1. Ecosystem services common language

The concept of ecosystem services is used to identify linkages between the natural processes, and the economic and social gains, which we humans obtain from the ecosystems and its functions [48]. Interest in ecosystem assessments has been growing from both scientific and policy perspectives. The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment [4] has adopted ecosystem services as a method for identification and assessment of services provided by nature (Figure 3.1), and defines it as a function of biodiversity levels [49]. The set of services secured by the levels of biodiversity, consists of supporting (e.g. soil formation, pollination), provisioning (e.g. food), regulating (e.g. flood regulation) and finally, cultural services (e.g. aesthetic, educational). In other words, reductions in biodiversity have a significant impact on the overall resilience of urban ecosystems [50], affecting human health and the overall well-being in the city. Specifically, biodiversity creates conditions to generate ecosystem services that city planners value - including energy efficiency, storm water runoff, air pollution removal, carbon storage and sequestration, water quality provision, and heat-island effect mitigation.

Figure 3.1: Ecosystem services framework (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment [4]). The services provided by nature are shown in the green boxes. Blue boxes are describing social benefits derived from the ecosystem services. Relations between individual units are represented by the arrows, where arrow's width (low to high) stands for the intensity of linkages between the ecosystem services and human well-being, and colour (light to dark) shows the potential for mediation by socioeconomic factors.

Ecosystem services origin among other disciplines in economics, ecology, sociopsychology and several methods have been developed to measure their value. The challenge is to make this assessment readily available to be integrated in decision-making processes helping to balance efficient production (economic growth) and distribution of ecosystem services on all beneficial aspects (tangible and intangible). This way, identification of ecosystem services could build a bridge to link urban ecology with economics and conserve natural capital of cities. A constraint to this integration is that, in our society, monetary valuation only provides a convincing argument that urban trees can contribute to societal wealth and urban life quality. Indeed, there is usually a low priority put on urban forests in policy-making processes and this is partly related to the failure of expressing them in monetary terms [51].

Thus, the challenge is also to monetarise services provided by natural ecosystems or to value them in another convincing way to show that associated benefits can outweigh planning, maintenance or recovery costs. Since ecosystem services language puts human-being as main beneficiaries, it is interesting to value benefits from one unit of nature to urban dwellers. This way, some cities have determined a minimum target value of accessible urban green space value per capita in relation to human health (varying between 6 to 10 m^2 [52]). Furthermore, the trade-off between local short-term economic benefits and long-term sustainability of urban ecosystems has to be done by distinguishing long-term and short-term decision-making. Besides, all stakeholders have to be taken into account since valuation can vary a lot according to the considered one (e.g., land owners vs. citizens).

Typically, these environmental economics techniques are split into four categories: conventional market approaches, household production functions, hedonic pricing, and experimental meth-

ods such as surveys [5].

Household production functions are based on the principle that consumers often do not gain utility directly from the purchased goods, but by transforming the goods with a household production function into a valuable good or service. Applied to ecosystem services, for example, the protection of watershed forests could mitigate droughts which is not directly valued but the value can be derived from savings in household water collection costs [53].

Hedonic pricing handles market-priced goods entailing a particularly consumer valued component (for example the value of a garden in a property) assigned to a price index reflecting its contribution to the total value of the goods [5].

Experimental methods are mainly used to capture non-market values of ecosystem services provided by nature through “contingent choice models” such as surveys answering questions about hypothetical scenarios and extrapolated to the entire population. Questions are based either on the willingness-to-pay approach (“how much they would be willing to pay to ensure a welfare gain from the change in the provision of ecosystem services”) or on the willingness-to-accept approach (“how much they would be willing to accept to endure a welfare loss from a reduced provision of the services”).

Besides, other methods such as conventional life cycle assessment aim to monetarize ecosystem services. Else, ecologists have developed non-monetary valuation methods such as thermodynamics approaches (e.g. *eco-exergy* and *emergy*) or footprint analysis [54], which will be discussed later.

In order to assess the value of ecosystem services provided by forests, the most common way is to compare the value of projected benefits from urban trees measured as avoided costs to the value of projected costs due to their maintenance and design. This method used in the *i-Tree Eco* software, does not include non-marketed value of ecosystem services.

2. Urban trees ecosystem services

Although street trees have simultaneously achieved various purposes, different functions have been considered particularly important at different times. In the late 19th century, when urban areas and diseases were growing out of control, street trees were used to make cities look more beautiful and less dense, as well as for air cleaning and cooling helping heat and air pollution health problems. Then, air filtration thanks to trees became particularly pertinent after World War II for cities laying in ruins. While they were identified as noise buffers, street trees suffered from de-icing salt and from vehicle exhaust increasing with postwar economic boom. Road network development also led to trees removal with the resurgence of a 19th century assertion: “trees do not belong in the city” [47]. Moreover, New York business owners were calling trees into question since they could hide advertisements and storefronts. In early 20th century, social reformers and philanthropists in New York identified the importance of street trees in overpopulated districts. Besides, street tree planting campaigns were initiated to rehabilitate birds diversity within the city. Later, trees planting was used as a tool for woman’s empowerment symbolizing private and public sphere transgression. Trees also represented a community-building tool against ghettoization during African-American civil rights movement [47]. Furthermore, trees are a tool to support the “rights-of-nature” movement by promoting their characteristics of intelligent living beings [55].

Finally, trees are multitaskers and can provide a wide variety of ecosystem services, differently prioritized throughout history. Although, the urban population relies mainly on services derived from external ecosystems such as food and energy (see urban metabolism representation Part 1.1) and benefits generated by urban forests are limited comparing with the amount of imported ecosystem services, urban forest could be used as a tool to solve local environmental problems [56].

Air pollution removal

In an increasingly urbanized world, air pollution mitigation is considered one of the most important issues in urban planning. As mentioned before air pollution harms human health, damages ecosystem processes and reduces visibility. Urban trees help to improve air quality by facilitating widespread deposition of various gases and particles through the transport to large surface areas provisioned by trees and able to absorb them.

Together with carbon dioxide in the process of photosynthesis and with oxygen in respiration, gaseous pollutants can be absorbed into plant tissues through the stomata of the leaves, where transfer and assimilation can fix the pollutants in the tissues. NO_2 and SO_2 , in particular, can inside the plant react with water on inner-leaf cell walls to form sulfurous and sulfuric acids as well as nitrous and nitric acids, which may further react with other compounds and be transported to different parts of the tree [19].

Particles are trapped by all tree surfaces i.e. stems, leaves, branches, and then washed off by precipitation. This deposited particles can be resuspended to the atmosphere or removed

during rain events and dissolved or transferred to the soil. This combination of events can lead to positive or negative pollution removal depending on various atmospheric factors. There are some cases when resuspended particles lead to increased pollution concentrations. During particularly dry months, trees resuspend more particles than they remove [57]. Moreover, transpiration of trees increases air water content that aids the settlement of airborne particles and greater surface roughness of trees (which increases turbulent deposition and impaction processes by local higher wind speed) make them more effective in the capture of particles than other types of plants [5]. What is more, variations in the structure and micro-roughness of a leaf surface affect patterns of particle deposition [58].

The effectiveness of this ecosystem service varies by plant species, canopy area but also on the type and characteristics of air pollutants, on the local meteorological environment and on other processes through which trees affect their environment. Indeed, urban vegetation can directly and indirectly affect local and regional air quality. The main ways through which urban trees affect air quality are [59]: temperature reduction (lowering the activity of chemical reactions producing secondary air pollutants) and other microclimate effects such as air turbulence, direct removal of air pollutants (by absorbing gaseous compounds through leaf stomata), emission of volatile organic compounds (VOC) (see Part 3.), tree maintenance emissions and energy effects on buildings (reduces energy consumption in buildings consequently reducing air pollutant emissions from fossil-fuel power sources [60]). These cumulative and interactive effects of trees on climate, direct pollution removal, VOC and power plant emissions determine the net impact of trees on air pollution.

On the financial aspect, cost savings through the reduction of medical services to harmed citizens, and of engineered decontamination processes, could be used into the assessment of this ecosystem service.

Carbon storage and carbon dioxide sequestration

Trees reduce the amount of atmospheric carbon (from carbon dioxide) by sequestering carbon in new growth tissue every year, through photosynthesis. The amount of carbon annually sequestered is increased with the size and health of the trees and depends on the species composition.

Furthermore, as a tree grows, it stores more carbon by holding it in its accumulated tissue. As a tree dies and decomposes, it releases stored carbon back into the atmosphere. Maintaining healthy trees will keep the carbon stored in trees. Moreover, when a tree dies, using the wood to heat buildings will help reduce carbon emissions from wood decomposition or from fossil-fuel or wood-based power plants [61]. However, the latter assertion is not valid when heating the building with wood replaces a renewable energy source. In this case it would be equivalent in terms of CO_2 emissions to let the tree decompose. Thus it depends on the regional fuel composition to generate electricity and on regional climate. Another way to make carbon storage of the urban forest valuable on the short term, i.e. that the city's carbon emissions are reduced by urban forest, is to ensure that the amount of young healthy trees, though

old enough to be efficient, is always higher than aging, unhealthy and dying trees. As such, the carbon uptake by present trees would be higher than the carbon release by decomposition. Nevertheless the latter idea is limited to the short run since those relatively young efficient trees would get to the dying phase and subsequently emit carbon in turn. To positively compensate this carbon, we would need another greater amount of young trees, but the urban forest has spatial limits. Moreover, juvenile trees are not efficient enough in carbon uptake, thus they need to grow enough until representing a significant carbon sink.

Oxygen production

Oxygen production is one of the most commonly cited benefits of urban trees. A tree's net annual oxygen production is directly related to the amount of carbon sequestered by the tree linked to the accumulation of tree biomass. Thus, it depends on photosynthetic capacity of plants which depends on species composition, age structure and health of urban tree. However, this tree benefit is relatively insignificant since our atmosphere has an enormous and stable oxygen reserve thanks to extensive production by aquatic systems. "If all fossil fuel reserves, all trees, and all organic matter in soils were burned, atmospheric oxygen would only drop a few percent" [62].

Soil pollution removal

In urban environments, leaves, bark and the root system of trees are exposed to atmospheric pollutants through processes such as wet and dry deposition. They can trap or uptake contaminants bound both to airborne particulate matter and/or to the soil [63]. In that respect, the phytoremediation potential of trees in urban environments is mentioned as an ecosystem service to rehabilitate contaminated lands by removing pollutants from the soil or rendering them harmless [64] (in particular with regard to heavy metals). Moreover, Markert et al. (2008) [65] mentions how the bioaccumulation capacity of trees has been used to trace elements in urban and industrial areas. Hence, as an organism that contains information on the quality of the environment, trees can be used as bioindicators. The latter associated ecosystem service is to inform about the health of the urban environment and to prevent alarming levels.

Soil quality and biogeochemistry improvement

The following ecosystem services are operated by tree roots playing an important role in soil composition and structure. Soil compaction in urban areas breaks down soil structure through filling pore space with soil particles which eliminates space for air and water. But air in soil allows for gas exchange and for water transport carrying nutrients which roots will not be able to grow and nourish the tree [66].

Yet, tree roots can positively influence soil quality, hydrology, and biogeochemistry in urban environments. More precisely, tree roots improve soil physical properties, maintain or enhance soil organic matter, fix N_2 and deeply uptake nutrients, increase water infiltration and storage, decrease loss of nutrients to erosion and leaching (through water channels), decrease soil acidity and improve soil biological activity [38].

Organic matter is an important component of soils to trees mainly for its contribution to soil structure. As the basis of soil food web life, soil organic matter can also be a reservoir of nutrients and can contribute to hold water for trees. Although organic matter is expected to be lower in cities than in forests where trees and organisms decay locally, single trees are able to renew soil organic matter themselves. Indeed, organic matter from fine roots and mycorrhizal fungal biomass released through their rapid turnover are important contributors to the success of trees growing in heavily urbanized areas [66].

Although the effect of nutrient high concentration spots on urban tree root systems is poorly documented, it is known that tree roots can help regulate nutrient cycles by influencing provision and availability of nutrients in the soil via root turnover, nutrient uptake and root exudates [38].

In physical terms, tree roots form part of a complex system able to stabilize soil and reduce erosion [67]. Soil with roots dries more quickly due to transpiration which increases soil's shear and tensile strength and the root/soil tangential resistance to slipping [38].

In addition, tree roots mechanically increase soil stability. In particular, vulnerability to landslides due to constructions altering natural ground and resulting in steep slopes, can be reduced by tree roots as a mean of slope reinforcement. Particularly exposed to erosion, stream banks can be consolidated thanks to tree roots [38].

Furthermore, tree roots are main contributors to soil structure and to soil formation. Indeed, tree roots form soil macropores and channels by penetrating roots. The latter facilitates soil air circulation, water storage and filtering and creates cracks leading to soil fragmentation, aggregate formation and resistance decrease for further root growth. Tree roots can also directly enhance aggregation by releasing various compounds cementing soil particles [38].

Finally, it is a virtuous circle: growing trees improve their local soil that improves their growing processes and enhances ecosystem services they provide. Moreover, increased infiltration thanks to roots rehabilitating the soil, combined with increased vegetation interception over ground, will increase evapotranspiration.

Rainwater retention

Surface runoff is a serious issue in urban areas since it contributes to pollute streams, rivers and consequently natural water reservoirs. Moreover, high area of impervious surfaces increases the amount of surface runoff.

Urban vegetation and soil play crucial roles in rainwater retention and runoff decrease. During precipitation events, some fraction of precipitation is intercepted by vegetation while the remainder reaches the ground and does not infiltrate on impervious surface. While trees intercept precipitation, their roots facilitate infiltration through evapotranspiration and increased soil storage. [68]

Through water interception, discharge of retained water by vegetation into stormwater drains and rivers is gradual which lightens water load and avoids peak flows. This way, likelihood of floods is reduced [5].

Soil structure improvement thanks to trees also explains the rainwater retention improvement in soils, since it leads to a greater storage and to improved soil water uptake processes.

Associated with soil pollution removal, these benefits improve the quality of water, directly with groundwater recharge and indirectly by avoiding runoff transporting urban material and pollution all along until the rivers.

On the financial aspect, cost savings deriving from avoided flood damages, less heavy stormwater drainage and detention infrastructures, avoided water quality and groundwater availability loss, could be used in the monetary assessment of this ecosystem service.

Cooling effect

Due to urban infrastructure, dark surfaces, materials with high thermal capacities and the lack of nature in urban areas, heat-island effect occurs in street canyons.

By shading buildings, providing evaporative cooling through evapotranspiration and lowering wind speeds subsequently reducing air penetration from outside into indoor space, urban trees affect energy consumption to adapt indoor climate to comfort zone. In addition, another beneficial function of trees is in terms of infrared radiation since only about 20% of incident solar energy is re-radiated by the leaves unlike dark artificial surfaces. The rest is conserved by the plant which significantly reduces long-wave radiation in cities [5].

Trees tend to reduce building energy consumption in the summer months, however they can either increase or decrease building energy use in the winter months, depending on the location of trees around the building. For example, in the northern hemisphere, an evergreen tree located on the southern side of a residential building may produce a shading effect causing an increasing heating need.

Finally, these effects of urban trees next to buildings are only beneficial during the winter if they are not located south and are evergreen to block wind. In order to have the best beneficial effect throughout the year, it would be relevant to plant evergreen trees on the north (decreasing cold wind speeds during the winter) of the building and deciduous trees on the south (admitting solar radiation during the winter and blocking it during the summer). Besides, according to Parker (1983) [69], trees on the west side of buildings are the most valuable. In addition, the

study of Yokohari et al. (2001) [70] showed that cooling effect of urban vegetation could extend approximately 150 meters into surrounding residential areas.

However, high temperatures and drought induced by climate change affect physiology of trees and may significantly reduce their evaporative cooling capacity [71].

Resulting heating or cooling energy savings from this ecosystem service are very valuable in terms of emissions reduction and especially to lower energy peak consumption, which requires additional power plants thus increases tremendously emissions and costs (throughout plant's lifecycle).

In addition, tree shade can protect street paving from weathering [72]. Indeed, asphalt entails an oil binder that heats up and evaporates without tree shade, leaving unbound aggregate. Street rehabilitation costs can be significantly reduced with street trees cover.

Noise reduction

Urban trees can attenuate high frequencies noise over 70 decibels (perceived as bothering for human-being) by absorption, deflection, refraction from leaves, stems and branches. Noise reduction also operates through noise masking by generating simultaneous pleasant sounds as wind moves tree leaves or as birds sing in the canopy. For instance, a 3-meters wide trees belt with dense foliage can generate a reduction of 3 to 5 dBA. Furthermore, such as particles trapping, it is more efficient at the noise source [5].

Habitat and biodiversity conservation

Numerous types of wildlife (such as birds, mammals, insects, reptiles, and amphibians [5]) inhabit urban areas. Trees provide a habitat and facilitate movement of organisms among remnant patches hosting native wildlife. This way, urban forests can create biodiversity corridors linking rural boundaries. This can benefit biodiversity conservation for both fauna and flora species, since urban forests are also habitat for pollinators with their buds, blossom and fruit. The latter is particularly important to sustain urban bird life. As such around 160 species have been identified in Porto Alegre in Brazil [73].

Cultural ecosystem services

Trees in urban areas also provide intangible ecosystem services. Called “cultural services” they represent various physical and psychological benefits from nature [74].

Most readily available benefits of urban forests are recreational and aesthetic services. “Vegetation softens the urban hardscape to create a more aesthetically pleasing landscape. Vegetation creates different colors, shapes, dimensions, textures, sounds, and feels, and these attributes vary infinitely with season, time of day, and weather conditions” [5]. Acting as a “screen and buffer”, vegetation can block unpleasant views and turn them into pleasant natural views contrasting with harsh and closed building atmosphere. Parks, in particular, enable to look further away than the next concrete wall as well as providing a calm and healthier environment than the noisy and polluted grey parts of cities. The latter functions of trees and green areas provide health and psychological services since it reduces mental fatigue and aggression [75] by providing durable physical and mental spaces. “People’s positive feeling toward parklands is believed to be connected with our human evolutionary link with nature and hence biophilia, because natural places are associated with ancient survival values of supplying food and water” [5] (from [76]). This also leads to therapeutic benefits complementary to medical cures, since vicinity to green spaces has been showed to increase patients recovery rates [77]. More recent research showed relationships between maternal exposure to green space and infant birth weight [78].

On a social aspect, green surroundings in residential neighbourhoods tend to reduce crimes and can alleviate poverty by getting same access to managed green places than more favoured neighbourhoods [79].

Furthermore, urban forests can also be the place for outdoor classroom education, since greenery has been proved to improve concentration and self-discipline [80]. In addition, urban nature is a tool to educate people about environmental protection and reconnect them with nature, especially through the understanding that nature has been there in a wild state before cities have been built. Some natural areas such as forest remnants also provide laboratories for scientific research to understand species and ecosystem responses to the altered environment and especially to predict urban forest patches regeneration [5].

Increased property values and economic development

“One of the most frequently cited reasons that people plant trees is for beautification. Trees add color, texture, line, and form to the landscape” [25]. Studies comparing the selling prices of residential properties show that people are willing to pay more for properties with large trees compared to properties with few or no trees. However, this correlation between the presence of trees and the value of properties also depends on location, tree species, size of properties, etc., and is difficult to translate into economic terms. Beautification, shade privacy, wildlife habitat, noise abatement, wind reduction, and soil protection are products that are difficult to price. Urban green infrastructures influence economic development of the cities. They provide jobs, promote tourism and are attractive for investors which adds to municipal income.

3. Urban trees ecosystem disservices

Emissions by trees

Trees may produce wind-dispersed pollen, known allergen [81] impacting human health and emit a range of gaseous matter participating in photochemical reactions. Through these processes depending on species-specific tree properties, they can negatively impact air quality. Particularly, emission of biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOC's such as isoprene and monoterpene) can induce high ozone levels which is harmful to humankind and the environment at ground level. Tropospheric ozone is not emitted directly into the air but is created by chemical reactions between nitrogen oxides (NO_x) emitted by anthropogenic sources and BVOC's in the presence of sunlight.

These reactions can also lead to particulate matter formation, which can contribute to ozone reactions as a supplementary VOC if it evaporates in high temperature and concentration conditions [82]. Thus, these chemical reactions are interrelated and can influence

Figure 3.2: Interrelated chemical reactions leading to ozone formation through VOC's [82]

each other depending on urban and climate conditions (Figure 3.2). Although they can also be reached in colder conditions, unhealthy levels of ozone are particularly reached on warm high insolated days [83]. In these conditions, VOC emissions by urban trees increase. The latter can also be triggered during flowering periods [84], in response to drought conditions, to high concentrations of ground level ozone [85] or to insect outbreaks [82].

In particular, the effect of a heat wave on biogenic VOCs emission has been investigated in a study case [82] located in Berlin that experienced a heat wave in 2006 with the highest observed temperature $36.6^{\circ}C$ and the highest ozone concentration level around $200 \mu g/m^3$. The result as expected demonstrated that during heat wave, VOC emissions can considerably enhance air pollution. Hence, the study recommends to accompany urban tree planting campaigns with a vehicle fleet reduction especially during heat waves.

Furthermore, Bonn et al. (2018)[86] showed that trees emitting mainly isoprene increase ozone and total PM10 concentrations, while tree species emitting mainly monoterpenes induce less of both.

However, a balance can be met between VOC emissions increasing with temperature and the cooling capacity of canopy cover. This way, increased tree cover compensates ozone formation by lowering overall VOC emissions. A computer simulation of June 4th 1984 ozone conditions in Atlanta showed that a 20% loss in the study area's urban forest could lead to a 14% increase in ozone concentrations.[87]

Pollutant trapping

Urban trees in street canyons also contribute to altering the local flow and trap pollutants through their aerodynamic effects. In Buccolieri et al. (2011) [88], the combined influence of street building morphology and vegetation on flow and dispersion in an idealized street canyon is simulated using laboratory experiments and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). The “aspect ratio” W/H is used with W and H the width and the height of buildings, respectively. It is noticed first that the “aspect ratio effect” (in a street canyon without trees street-level pollutant concentrations decrease when “aspect ratio” increases) lowers its effect in the presence of trees. Furthermore, simulations for two typical winter and spring days showed that trees increase concentrations by trapping pollutants.

The structural modification on local climate brought by the presence of trees in a street canyon has been simulated by Bruse et al. (1999) [89] on a quite simple case study of a North-South orientated street canyon (width 16m) with homogenous buildings (height 16m) on both sides and 20 meters high deciduous trees with a dense crown layer (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Flow field and air temperature for the canyon without trees (left) and with trees (right) in 1.8m height at 14:00 CET on the 23rd of June after 32 hours simulation [89]

On the lower urban boundary layer, interactions between trees and buildings produce small scale patterns of varying local climate conditions, very sensitive to structural changes. Inside the right canyon with trees, the air temperature is around 1.0 to 1.3°C lower than in the case without trees. Below the trees, wind speed is a little lower and vortex eddies (arrows) at the extremities of the canyon extend a bit further into the street: the vertical wind flow between buildings is suppressed by the tree canopy. In addition, a new hot spot can be identified at the

southern end of the street due to wind speed reduction inhibiting air exchange [89].

Hence, this study shows how trees affect aerodynamics by creating small-scale air circulations and blocking bigger scale air circulation. Although trees tend to lower general temperature level of the street, they also create hot spots with reduced wind speed inducing higher pollutant concentrations and higher chemical activity [90, 91].

However, studies [92] showed that trapping effects of trees are stronger than positive effects of deposition and removal, although these effects are very local and depend on many variables (vegetation type and density, meteorological conditions, street geometry and building morphology, pollutant characteristics and emission rates).

Costs of planting, maintaining trees and conflicts with urban infrastructure

To assess the relevance of creating urban forests and planting trees in the city, it is necessary to consider both the benefits (mentioned above) and the costs. Indeed, the benefits/costs ratio is a good decision-making indicator since it increases both when profits increase or costs decrease. Therefore, it is important to inventory the costs generated by the trees.

The greatest expenses are generally related to planting especially for trees on residential site (yard trees), and pruning, especially for street trees (public trees). Significant costs are also generated by managing conflicts with infrastructure. Indeed, Tree roots can damage sidewalks, curbs and gutters, paving, sewer lines and home foundations. Large trees can damage power lines and require frequent pruning. Street trees lay leaves, flowers, fruits and branches all year round, forcing municipalities to pick them up. When the rains are abundant, this debris can clog sewers and cause flooding. As a result, street and park trees are removed and sidewalk conflicts are the second most common reason for this, according to a study in San Joaquin Valley Communities [72] that surveyed 18% of responding cities removing more trees than they plant.

Other costs are also due to tree caring and mortality rates which can be significant especially when tree diseases spread. Irrigation, tree removal and administrative activities are also costly.

Chapter 4: Case study: Turrialba, Costa Rica

1. Contextual information

1.1 *i-Tree Eco*

By employing field-surveyed urban forest information from randomly located plots or complete inventory, location specific data, hourly meteorological and air pollution data, *i-Tree Eco* estimates various measured structural forest attributes, its numerous effects and economical value within a sampling error [93]. *i-Tree Eco* was developed based on the Urban Forest Effects (UFORE) model [68] that later became *i-Tree Hydro* focusing on hydrology effects of trees. Part of the i-Tree Suite, *i-Tree Eco* aims to provide statistical estimations of the urban forest structure and of its main physical functions facilitating the translation into monetary values to include in decision-making processes. The hydrology module of *i-Tree Eco* is a simplified UFORE model and represents one of several used models: precipitation-interception model [68], dry-deposition model [94], surface and upper air weather pre-processor [95], biogenic emission model (based on UFORE-B) [96], dry weight biomass model (for carbon calculations) and the sampling-based statistical estimation model.

After implementation of the input data (field-surveyed and local meteorological data), *i-Tree Eco* allows to get access to a large list of output data:

- Composition and structure (by tree specie or by stratum): population, distribution, importance value (addition of population and leaf area percentage), condition, crown health, leaf area and biomass, ground cover composition, land-use, relative performance index of trees, maintenance (depending on tree size and health);
- Benefits and costs (by species or by stratum): carbon storage of trees, annual carbon sequestration, annual net carbon sequestration, hydrology effects (potential evapotranspiration, evaporation, transpiration, water intercepted, avoided runoff), oxygen production by trees, pollution removed by trees hourly and its associated percent air quality improvement throughout a year, VOC's (Volatile Organic Compounds) emissions by trees, UV effects of trees, effects of trees on building energy use and consequent effects on CO_2

emissions from power sources, structural economic values, as well as the economic values for air pollution removal and carbon storage and sequestration;

- Pollution and weather: hourly values over one year of reduction in UV index, air quality improvement, air pollutant flux (dry deposition), isoprene and monoterpene emission, avoided runoff, precipitation and temperature;
- Georeferenced data, for individual field-surveyed trees results, when ticking “coordinates” in the settings for “individual level results”;
- Availability of a general *Written Report* automatically generated and summing up some of the results (non-exhaustive).

It is important to notice that individual level results give results for each individual field-surveyed tree whereas all other reports give the results for all trees together, considering statistical tree population estimation.

The software also intends to give recommendation on maintenance and invasive species. However, analysis of invasive species is not available for studies outside of the US, since invasive species are identified using an list of US invasive species per state.

Processing and theory behind the model are described Part 3. after following presentation of the study site.

1.2 Characterization of the case study area

1.2.a General description

The present case study, aiming to qualify the benefits of trees in the urban area of the city of Turrialba using *i-Tree Eco* has been initiated by the Watershed Department of the Tropical Agricultural Research and Higher Education Center (CATIE), regional center dedicated to research and graduate education in agriculture, and management, conservation and sustainable use of natural resources. Until now the CATIE has been focusing on rural research (among others on agroforestry which studies the benefits of trees in agroecological systems) but there is a recent interest from the Watershed Department to expand their research to urban areas. This case study is a pilot project, that aims to sensitize the municipality of the city to urban forest management and will eventually launch a project proposal to San José, the capital city of Costa Rica. The city of Turrialba has been chosen since it is the closest urban settlement to the research centre, which facilitates the field measurements.

The study area is located in the Costa Rica Central Valley, province of Cartago, canton of Turrialba. Turrialba is the largest of the eight cantons that comprise this province. It has an estimated population of 70,000 that is distributed over an area of 1644 km^2 . The canton of Turrialba is divided into ten municipalities also called district or cities: Turrialba, La Suiza, Peralta, Santa Cruz, Santa Teresita, Pavones, Tuis, Tayutic, Santa Rosa and Tres Equis. Tur-

rialba is the largest of the ten municipalities containing approximately 40% of the canton's total population[97] with an area of 419 hectares (area based on shapefiles delimiting the city of Turrialba used in the Watershed Department of the CATIE). The study site is a parcel of 12 hectares located within the city of Turrialba (see Part 2.1). In a geographical and watershed management point of view, the canton of Turrialba is located in the sub-basin of the Turrialba river (Río Turrialba). The extreme coordinates of the sub-basin in Transverse Mercator for Costa Rica (CRTM05) projection and datum WGS84 are: North: 1107494.928297 m, East: 538203.859664 m, South: 1092485.424995 m and West: 518843.050841m (Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: Location of the Turrialba river sub-catchment [98]

The altitudinal gradient of the sub-catchment ranges from 3300 masl (meters above sea level) on the volcano Turrialba to 580 masl in its estuary and its total extension is of 11,358 hectares. In general, according to the indexes calculated for the basin, it is concluded that it is not prone to suffer flooding and has a low tendency to concentrate high volumes of drainage water. The Turrialba river basin, in hydrographic terms, is located in one of the most water-important areas of the country and is subordinated to the Reventazón river basin, responsible for the generation of 25% of the country's electricity. In fact, a hydro-power diversion dam is located on the Turrialba river immediately downstream of the city just below the confluence of the

Colorado River. The dam diverts water from the Turrialba river through a tunnel to the Angostura Hydroelectric Project on the Reventazón river.

Among its productive activities, coffee and sugar cane crops stand out in the primary sector; in the processing industry, the sugar mill in Juan Viñas or the artisanal dairy production in Santa Cruz and in the service sector, hotel industry and nature tourism in the Volcán Turrialba National Park.

Along the length and width of this altitudinal gradient, various ecosystems are distributed such as montane rainforests, highly humid montane and pre-montane forests or transition tropical rainforest. In many areas, the original vegetation is secondary (area which has regrown after a timber harvest) or has been transformed into forest or coffee plantations, pastures or annual crops.

From an environmental management perspective, the territory is subscribed to the Conservation Area of the Central Volcanic Mountain Range of the Ministry of Environment and Energy (National System of Conservation Areas) and includes part of the Turrialba Volcano National Park. In terms of actions taken to protect the environment, despite the fact that the municipalities involved have solid waste management programmes, environmental education of the population is still incipient and the final disposal of solid waste has been controversial in Turrialba [98].

Historically, the evidence of human occupation in the region goes back to pre-hispanic times as evidenced by the antiquity of the archaeological sites of Guayabo and Guadiria. However, the most complete records of activity in the region refer to colonial times, associated with the agricultural colonization policies of the 19th century and the culmination at the beginning of the 20th century with the establishment of the present cantons of Jiménez, Turrialba and Alvarado. At this time, the development of the region was closely related to agricultural export production and the presence of the Atlantic railway, which facilitated the transfer of products such as coffee, banana and sugar cane to the port of Limón on the Caribbean coast [99]. Nowadays, the latter production dropped to 15% of the region's productive activity. Moreover, the conditions of productivity and competitiveness have changed due to the economic recession of the last decade, the excessive specialisation of primary activities, weak intersectoral linkages with the rest of the regional economy and low contribution in the value chains of major agricultural products [100].

In terms of air quality in the city of Turrialba, there is a lack of information. Nevertheless, it is known that respiratory disease are part the main mortality causes. Moreover, since one of the main roads linking the pacific to the Caribbean crosses the city, the traffic is high, entailing a significant number of trucks, and concentrated in the city centre. Thus it can be assumed that the air pollution levels reach excessive amounts at some specific high-traffic and high temperature hours.

The Turrialba river basin is an area of transition between the urban and the rural, the anthropic and the natural, the centre and periphery of the country. For this reason, the powers of various ministries overlap, each of them using different territorial and scale approaches.

1.2.b Biophysical Characterization

Climate

Although very complex, the climate within the study basin can be classified as tropical-humid. Costa Rica has a rainy season that starts at the end of April and extends for approximately 245 days. The average annual precipitation and temperature are respectively 2635mm and 22.5°C (26.4°C during the day). Although Costa Rica weather patterns are influenced on an annual basis by alternating rainy and dry seasons, heavy rainfall events can occur in any month of the year. However, records in the study area show that December is the wettest month of the year with an average precipitation of 306mm, while March is the driest month with an average precipitation of 81.2mm. Annual rainfall ranges from about 2500mm (litres per square metre) in the lower part (valley), from 2500 to 4000mm in the middle and from 2000 to 2500mm in the upper part of the basin. Due to the volcano elevation, rains are convective and orographic, very intense.

The temperature is stable throughout the year; a small decrease occurs between the months of December to February, this due to the increase of the northeast trade winds (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2: Average monthly precipitation and average monthly temperature of the meteorological station CATIE, sub-basin of the Turrialba River. Source: CATIE Meteorological Station, 2016

Topography

The dominant physical feature in the study area is the Turrialba volcano, with a peak elevation of 3340m. The city of Turrialba is located on the lower southeastern slopes of the volcano at 646m above sea level. The elevation in the drainage basin drops 2000m over a distance of only 22km, from the summit of the volcano to the city of Turrialba. Overland slopes are steeper in the upper part of the basin while slopes in the lower portion are more gradual. Steep gradients in the upper slopes produce high-energy flows that erode the streambanks and transport materials to the lower part of the river. Figure 4.3 shows the wide range of slopes found along the Turrialba river channel profile [97].

Figure 4.3: Longitudinal profile of Turrialba River obtained from 10x10m Digital Elevation Model [97]

Hydrology

Evapotranspiration and water balance were estimated using the Thornthwaite method with data over 30 years from the CATIE meteorological station. The annual evapotranspiration value is 1036mm/year. No water deficit was presented in any month and this can be explained by the large amount of monthly precipitation, which is always greater than the potential evapotranspiration of each month. In addition, the average water runoff is of 1792mm/year.

Figure 4.4 shows the estimated outflows from the Turrialba river sub-basin, showing a small drop in flow in October, followed by a further drop in flow in March and April, which is consistent with the decreases in precipitation for those months.

Figure 4.4: Monthly average flow of the Turrialba River sub-basin. Source: CATIE Meteorological Station, 2016

The Turrialba river drainage basin is tributary to the larger Reventazón river that empties into the Caribbean. The average slope of the basin is 20%, but 54% of the area has slopes greater than 25% [101].

The Turrialba river has a movable bed that undergoes changes on its path, both vertically and horizontally, as it has to calibrate its course to the hydrological conditions of the basin. The most intense changes take place in the Turrialba Valley, since the geomorphology of the place has been transformed, rejuvenating the drainage area with lacustrine fillings [101].

Previous hydrologic models have divided the Turrialba river basin into six different hydrologic units: Coliblanco, Playas, Jesús María, Esmeralda, Roncha, and Colorado. Five rainfall gauges (location used to monitor terrestrial bodies of water) are evenly distributed throughout the area surrounding the watershed: Irazú, San Antonio, Pacayas, Rosemont and CATIE. The Turrialba streamflow gauge is located immediately downstream of the confluence with the Colorado river. Basin features are depicted in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: Features of the Turrialba River Watershed [97]

The city of Turrialba spreads from where Turrialba and Colorado river start converging at the lowest elevation levels to the confluence of both rivers. Aquiares river is also flowing through the city, as well as the “Quebrada Las Gamboas” from a micro-basin.

Water quality

Studies on surface water quality in the Turrialba river basin carried out by [102] show that, according to the water quality indices suggested by the Regional Coordinating Committee of Drinking Water and Sanitation Institutions of Central America, Panama and the Dominican Republic (CAPRE), the current state of surface water quality is classified as poor. The above is evidenced in Table 4.1, which shows the average standard values recommended as well as the values for the following variables representative of the water quality of each river flowing through the city of Turrialba: biochemical demand of oxygen (BOD), dissolved oxygen (OD) total dissolved solids (STD), hydrogen potential (pH), temperature (T), nitrates (NO_3), phosphates (PO_4), turbidity in NTU (Nephelometric Turbidity Units) and faecal coliforms in MPN/100ml (MPN stands for *Most Probable Number* method).

Sampling station	BOD [mg/l]	OD [mg/l]	STD [mg/l]	pH	T [°C]	NO3 [mg/l]	PO4 [mg/l]	NTU	Faecal coliforms (MPN/100ml)
Aquiares river	7.7*	9.5	159.7	8.2	18.1	1.3	9.4	0.6	15362.0*
Colorado river	8.8*	8.7	174.7	8.0	24.1	6.6	11.3	7.0	226666.7*
Turrialba river	7.8*	8.8	207.3	8.3	23.2	3.1	29.2	10.1	3669533.3*
CAPRE norm	ORV	2	300	6.5 – 8.5	18 – 30	5	0.01	1	0
	MRV	4**	1000	> 8.5	> 30	10	5**	3**	0**

Table 4.1: Studies of drinking water quality in the sub-basin of the river Turrialba [102]. Legend: ORV: optimal recommended value; MRV: maximal recommended value; *: Average value exceeding acceptable maximum; **: Maximum permissible value in water

Uncontrolled activities in the upper part of the Turrialba river sub-basin, such as agriculture, the improper disposal of dairy processing derivatives, the construction of septic tanks and the channelling of sewage into the Turrialba River channel, contribute to reducing the quality of the river's water.

Ecosystems

With respect to the geology of the Turrialba river sub-basin, most of the area of the sub-catchment Turrialba is covered by materials from the Turrialba volcano activity, representing 86% of the basin (lava flows, agglomerates, ash and shallow intrusive volcanic rocks). 9.18% is formed by volcanoclastic sedimentary rocks (sandstone, limestone, lutite and turbidite). The rocks located in the lower part of the sub-basin are dragged by the action of erosion and deposited downstream of the channel. Finally, 4.81% are alluvial and colluvial deposits forming up to 1000m wide flat areas adjacent to the rivers [103].

The soil depth in the sub-basin of the river Turrialba is variable. 42.04% has a depth between 40 to 90cm, while 41.55% is greater than 90cm. Most of it is characterized by deep soils that guarantee good quality for agricultural activities and allows the rain to be filtered out when it reaches the ground and to feed the underground streams with water. Finally 16.41% has a soil depth of less than 40cm: this happens when the deposited material has little adhesion, thus when external agents can carry and deposit it in low elevation areas.

The sub-basin mainly has soils with strong limitations that restrict their use to perennial and semi-perennial vegetation; the limitations are associated with slopes, erosion, soil depth, textures, etc. [98] In general, Costa Rica has fertile soils as a product of past volcanic activity of the region. The city of Turrialba rests on pyroclastic or volcanic deposits composed of andesitic lava, fluvial debris, and pyroclastic flows. The soils in the study area could be classified in two main groups: silts and clayey silts [97].

The sub-basins area is part of the biological corridor linking the different wildlife protected areas (National park volcano Turrialba, National park Tapanti, National park Barbilla). According to the life zones classification proposed by Holdridge [104], for the sub-basin of the river Turrialba five different zones were found as shown in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6: Holdridge life zones of the Turrialba river sub-catchment [98]

Among those, one is defined as transitory (Tropical moist forest transition to premontane); this area is the smallest in the sub-basin (160.97 hectares) and is located at the mouth of the river. The premontane wet forest is the most represented with 6441 hectares and is located from the town of Turrialba to La Pastora. The lower montane wet forest extends towards the slopes

of, the volcanoes Turrialba and Irazú (20 km distance between both) has an extension of 3105 hectares and holds the springs of some of the main tributaries to the river Turrialba. In the highest areas on the slopes of the volcano Turrialba are the lower montane rain forest (364.53 ha) and the montane rain forest (1285.7 ha) life zones.

With respect to this classification, the city of Turrialba includes tropical moist forest transition to premontane as well as premontane wet forest life zones.

The premontane wet forest covers an area of 38,652.95 hectares (53.62%). The forest is of medium height, semi-perennial with 2 to 3 layers. In the canopy, there are a few deciduous species during the dry season. The trees are generally 30 to 40 meters tall, with wide round crowns and relatively short, smooth trunks. The understory trees are 10 to 20 meters tall, with dense crowns and often have smooth and dark barks. The shrub layer is 2 to 3 meters high, often dense and the ground is completely bare with the exception of ferns. There are some epiphytes but they are not very conspicuous. The climbing plants are abundant and the trees are covered by a dense layer of moss. [105]

Moreover, the corresponding biomass of this forest biome is of 364 $ton.ha^{-1}$ which is lower than the tropical moist forest with a biomass of 449 $ton.ha^{-1}$ [106]. Since the second present forest biome in the study area is transitory from tropical moist forest to premontane, the biomass there is somewhere between the latter numbers. It represents 3.35% of the biological corridor with 2413.66 hectares.

Studies for specific flora and fauna for the Turrialba river sub-basin are scarce or non-existent. However, detailed studies have been carried out for the biological corridor of the Central Volcanical Cordillera, Talamanca, of which 91.4% is part of the basin. Therefore they share a great part of the biodiversity present there.

The sub-basin of the river Turrialba is located in the atlantic biogeographical region, being the region with the greatest richness in birds and mammals of Costa Rica. Due to the altitudinal gradient and stable climatic conditions, it is expected that a large number of species estimated to the number of 889 have been established. In the higher zone of the basin (Turrialba Volcano National park) in particular 84 species of birds have been identified including the quetzal (*Pharomachrus mocinno*) and diverse species of colibri, but the number of mammals and reptiles is low. In terms of vegetation there are low-lying species common in cold and humid areas. The dominating species are the genus *Chusquea* and shrubs of the families *Ericaceae*, *Hypericaceae*, *Rosaceae* and *Asteraceae* [107].

Calvo [108] points out that human influence has caused the almost total disappearance of the habitats necessary for the native fauna in the city of Turrialba, thus favouring the presence of species native to altered areas that due to the removal of their specific habitat had to migrate to another more favorable site.

The species encountered in the city of Turrialba have been identified on the field and listed per common and scientific name accompanied by pictures of their leaves (both sides of the leaf if needed and eventually the trunk type), flowers, fruits and eventually a bigger picture of the tree. This information forms an identification guide used during the field survey in the city

detailed in the next part. Figure 4.7 present one of the local species with its identification features. The other identified species can be seen in the Appendix B. .

Common name	Sotacaballo	Common name	Güitite
Scientific name	<i>Zygia longifolia</i>	Scientific name	<i>Acnistus arborescens</i>
Leaf			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference:	http://unibio.unam.mx/irekani/handle/123456789/54904?proyecto=Irekani	Reference:	http://ecobiosis.museocostarica.go.cr/especies/ficha/1/12200

Figure 4.7: Identification features of two local species: *Zygia longifolia* and *Acnistus arborescens*

Besides, the species information used in the *i-Tree Eco* software to simulate the urban forest is available in the *i-Tree* database online [109]. When inputting a specie in the input field-surveyed data, a list of species is suggested and the chosen one will be linked with this information: genus name, species name, family, order, class, common name, growth form, percent leaf type (informing on leaf density), leaf type, growth rate, longevity and height at maturity. The local species used in the *i-Tree Eco* simulation and their information from the database are listed in the Appendix A. .

Natural hazards, risk and vulnerability

The sub-basin of the river Turrialba presents multiple threats mostly from a natural origin. However, some of these threats are related to human activities namely socio-natural threats, such as floods, which sometimes occur due to stagnation of sewers with solid waste, poor construction of the rainwater network, infrastructure near flood plains of rivers, etc.

Turrialba is affected by other natural hazards such as volcanic, due to the nearby location of the Turrialba volcano. It is also threatened by seismicity and by landslides that can be activated due to geological faults and rainfall.

Areas with moderate susceptibility (ranges are from very low to very high susceptibility) to landslides, which in this case are located in and all around the city of Turrialba, may be due

to the alluvial origin, which is a product of materials washed away by the Turrialba river in the past, whose channel ran through the centre of the city of Turrialba. Expansion of human occupation of the fertile mountain slopes in the region over the last 100 years and the associated clearing of the mountain forests for agricultural purposes have accelerated runoff rates, resulting in significant increases in the volume of the bedload materials carried by area streams. In fact, the river Turrialba develops high-energy flows during extreme rainfall events (high rainfall amounts that typically exceed a total of 2000mm on an annual basis and the steep gradient of the drainage basin combine to produce flashy flow events of extreme energy, hydrologic model results indicate the peak discharge in the hydrograph can occur downstream at the city of Turrialba within a 2-hour period.) that cause the streambanks to erode rapidly. Those conditions pose a threat to the safety of the citizens residing along the immediate riverbanks and the public infrastructure located within the area. Under these circumstances, natural geomorphologic alterations in the channel, like erosion and sedimentation, become a problem which is more important than the floods in themselves (see pictures on Figure 4.8) [97].

Figure 4.8: Left: aerial view of the city of Turrialba looking upstream; right: Eroded left bank showing historic alluvial sediment deposition [97]

However, one of the most serious hazards in the city concerns the rivers Colorado and Turrialba, which have been heavily modified and altered by the population. The Colorado River has been modified by engineering works of dubious technical thoroughness and passes through the city through a covered tunnel, in which a kind of canal has been built with cladding walls. The beams and structures of these channels have become an obstacle since rocks, trunks, garbage or even whole trees obstruct them, causing the overflowing of water and floods in streets and homes. Indeed, according to the hypsometric curve of the channel, the sub-basin is in a state of equilibrium and old age and drags material and stones of great size along the channel, which affects the lower part of the sub-basin during the rainy season.

Moreover, most of the downtown areas of the Colorado river are undergoing subsidence and the materials of the structures have deteriorated with the floods, which makes the city even more vulnerable. The greatest danger is that during the floods the flow leaves its original bed and forms a new channel. This risk is especially serious in the river Turrialba, that could drag

much of the central district's infrastructure and human lives on its way [101].

A vulnerability analysis to flooding per river flowing through the city of Turrialba has been conducted in 2000 in the context of an international capacity building for natural disaster reduction within the framework of a regional action programme for Central America [110]. According to CATIE, 11 high flow events have occurred over the last 100 years, with the frequency of such events increasing in recent years in response to the land use changes in the upper basin [97]:

- The hydraulic capacity of the Turrialba river is sufficient, since there is an area of 405 m^2 under the Alegría bridge. If the estimated flow is 500 m^3/s with an average speed of 3 m/s , it can be inferred that the point of intersection of avenue 6 and street 3 has a risk potential (zone 1 on map 4.10): at this point the river bank height is low and during big rainfall events there is a risk that water enters this sector of the city, damaging houses in the lower part of the river;
- Historically, the Colorado river has caused the most floods to the city. If we look at the drainage capacity of the canal with respect to discharges, we can deduce that in this sector of the city every 5 to 10 years drastic floods can occur, causing floods in its surrounding areas. Such as explained above, it is a socio-natural threat since this area has been modified by urban planning. Avenida 2 (zone 2 on map 4.10) where the river has been constrained to a tunnel is the specific vulnerable point for these risks. See pictures below 4.9;
- On the “Quebrada Las Gamboas” coming from a micro basin, a system has been constructed on its course when it enters the city in the “Americas” neighbourhood (zone 3 on map 4.10). The constrained area of the channel leads to a yearly risk of flooding in this sector due to possible clogging of its course when the water carries waste materials from the city or from rural areas.
- The expansion of the city until the rivers Aquiares and Azul, which is an alluvial area, increases potential flooding zones (zone 4 on map 4.10).

Figure 4.9: Left: dwelling flooded by the Colorado river in the center of Turrialba; right: point at which the waters of the Colorado River exceed the level canal and inundate the city. Pictures from Manual Mora in 1996 [110]

In addition, Figure 4.10 maps the different vulnerability zones based on the above mentioned study. The delimited area in red represents the area of study simulated with i-Tree in the follow-up of the report. In the framework of this study, only risk zones 1 and 2 are relevant.

Figure 4.10: Mapping of risk zones to floodings based on the vulnerability analysis [110] on OpenStreet Map of Turrialba. Zone 1: river Turrialba; zone 2: river Colorado; zone 3: quebrada Las Gamboas; zone 4: river Aquiares. Red delimited zone: study area.

Historical documentation indicates that Turrialba volcano has erupted seven times since 1723. The last reported eruption occurred in 1866, following a period of intense activity during the early 1860s. The volcano has been explosively eruptive in recent years from 2014 to 2017 resulting in large clouds of volcanic ash. The summit of the volcano has three craters, with its flanks showing several historic lava flows, one of which passes close to the city of Turrialba. The volcano is considered active and seismicity has appeared high under the volcano since 1996. However, the majority of these earthquakes are of moderate magnitude (< 6.5) and superficial, thus barely perceived by the population.

From the establishment of the city to the present, the spatial planning has met economic and

social criteria, which have not taken into account the degrading effect of certain practices and activities on the environment and natural resources. The absence of a territorial planning plan that guides and orders the use of the physical space combined with the physical characteristics of the basin, mentioned above, is the main cause of the physical vulnerability of the city of Turrialba [101]. In the absence of adequate legislation and its application, the existence of construction in the river drainage areas has reduced their ability to evacuate high flows during heavy rainfall, resulting in their strangulation; with the consequent effects of overflows, causing damage to property, infrastructure and people themselves.

The lower part of the basin requires the implementation of a rigorous territorial plan, compliance with the existing legal framework, political will and the construction and/or adaptation of infrastructure to protect the population and reduce vulnerability to disasters.

Characterization of Variability and Climate Change

Figure 4.11: A2 scenario of climate change in temperature and annual mean precipitation for the Turrialba river sub-basin [98]

Climate variability is the degree of climate variations or fluctuations over a given period of time. When these fluctuations move away from the expected limits, then we may be talking about climate change. To project the effect of a change in climatic conditions, climate change

scenarios have been developed that take into account projections of future population, emissions and technology change, etc. [111]

To get an idea of the effect of a possible climate change on the sub-basin of the Turrialba river, temperature and precipitation variation values were taken according to an A2 climate change scenario (developed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)), where an average annual temperature increase of 3.36°C would be expected by the year 2080 (see Figure 4.11). In the case of precipitation, on average over the whole country a decrease of about 1 mm/day would be expected for the period from 2017 to 2100. Care must be taken with these values, since for the South Caribbean region an increase of the same would be expected which contradicts the country average [111].

1.2.c Relevant socioeconomic information

The number of inhabitants of the city of Turrialba estimated in 2019 is of 27,207 [112]. In terms of demographic distribution per age and per gender, it is quite balanced. 20% of the population is more than 60 years old and it is equally distributed between man and woman. The main causes of mortality (from the 2015 data) are systemic diseases (circulatory, respiratory and digestive) [98].

Education

In terms of education, the Turrialba river basin had in 2011 a percentage of 96.6% of literate population, which is slightly above the national average. However, 2011 data shows that the canton of Turrialba is still below the national average for full secondary education or more with a percentage of 29% of the population and a 39% on the national level.

Access to water

The Turrialba river basin is an area of great water importance and the availability and access to water for human use in the region are high. However, the canton of Turrialba still does not have 100% coverage. The water supply by aqueduct represents 89.6% of the supply in the canton of Turrialba [113]. 8.7% of the water accessed by the population comes from the river. In terms of water management in 2011, even though 97% of dwellings have water supply facilities only 6.7% are supplied by water storage tank. It can then be assumed that the population of the region is highly dependent on the continuity of public supply since the storage capacity is very low. In terms of comfort of the dwellings, hot water system throughout the household installation hardly reach 10% even in the more urbanized areas such as the city of Turrialba. Moreover, of the 28,178 dwellings located in the catchment area, only 56.38% are connected to a drainage system so the remaining 43.62% represent a risk of potential contamination due to inadequate management of domestic wastewater.

Actual land use

Much of the natural high jungle that historically covered the river basin above Turrialba has been converted to coffee, sugar cane and cattle pasture [97].

Figure 4.12: Land use types in the sub-basin of the Turrialba River [98]

The sub-basin of the river Turrialba presents the following uses of land (Figure 4.12): 37.52% pastures, 23.17% perennial crops, 21.91% forest, 9.79% annual crops, 4.84% human settlements, 1.69% water bodies, 0.98% grassland or shrubs and 0.11% bare soil. The annual crops are located mainly in the southeastern part of the basin close to the human settlements for easy access and little steep slopes. Perennial crops (sugar cane, coffee and to a lesser extent cocoa, some using agroforestry systems i.e. trees growing within plantations) are located from the middle to the bottom of the basin, surrounding the city of Turrialba.

Although agricultural predominate livestock activities, the greatest productive activity deriving from cattle is the production of cheese, which is a highly recognized product at the national level, the Turrialba cheese. In the lower part of the basin, close to the city of Turrialba, the agricultural areas are interspersed with pasture plantations, because the farms are small, the

livestock activity is more reduced and is only given for family consumption.

Agricultural management practices are defined by practical and non-environmental criteria. In this sense, the use of agrochemicals is widespread, mainly to combat pests (insects, diseases, weeds) and to add nutrients to the soil (chemical fertilization). Many of the practices leave the soil bare, unprotected from the impact of rain and surface runoff, which increases the vulnerability of the environment and increases the likelihood of flooding in the lower part of the basin. Moreover, intensive horticulture activities do mostly not practice soil and water conservation [101]. Added to other socio-natural reasons, these are threats to the agricultural sector in the region that knew a crisis in .

Besides, the dynamics of urban use do not seem to be regulated by physical restrictions of the environment, nor by normative factors; that is, any area can be occupied by urban settlements, regardless of the characteristics of the area [114].

Employment income sources

The commercial sector in the Turrialba river basin is located mainly in the city of Turrialba which has undergone an economic transition characterized by an increasing importance of services and tourism within the local economy. In the primary sector, in 2015, the labour force was of 8.9% (compared to 21.8% over Turrialba canton), with productive activities such as agriculture and cattle rearing. The secondary sector employed 15.6% of Turrialba city's labor force with activities that include manufacturing, electricity, drinking water supply and construction. Finally, the tertiary sector counted 75.8% of the labor force and is the highly most active sector in the city of Turrialba [115]. Besides, almost half of the population of the city was employed and around 3% unemployed which is low. However, around 50% of the canton's households were considered in poverty in 2009 [116]. This can partly be explained by a decline in the profitability of coffee and sugar cane crops from the early 2000's and by national agrarian policies disfavoring small producers [100], that has weakened agricultural activities. This quick development of the tertiary sector implies more people working in the urban area and the importance of increasing livability of Turrialba city.

Institutions and programmes involved in the urban planning

In Costa Rica, as in other nations, the political constitution is the supreme institutional instrument that acts as a reference for all public policies implemented for the fulfilment of fundamental human rights, such as the right to a healthy and ecologically balanced environment (Article 50) or the division and administration of territory on a municipal basis [98]. The Turrialba river basin is included in the Central Region and considered in the National Development Plan (NDP) from the Ministry of National Planning and Economic Policy (MIDEPLAN) which in its management areas entails a Regional Planning Area aiming to improve the conditions and quality of life of the population through, among others, the proposal of actions and inclusive sustainable human development (promoting citizen participation) [117]. This programme involves territorial planning instruments such as the Rural Development Plan of the Rural Development Institute (INDER) focused on the cantons of Turrialba and Jiménez.

2. Data gathering

2.1 On-field measurements

2.1.a Study area definition

In *i-Tree Eco* at the project creation phase, it is possible to use the “Project Configuration > Define Plots > Via Google Maps” function to define the area, manually or by importing a shapefile from another software. On the next step it is then possible to generate random sample plots. However, we only used the latter function to estimate the number of plots needed to have at least 20% representation of the study area. To do so we drew an area on *ArcGIS* (Geographical Information Software) on a georeferenced map, trying to include the most interesting parts of the city centre of Turrialba.

[Project Configuration > Define Plots > via Google Maps](#)

Map coordinates needs to be checked in the Data Collection Options to see and work with them later.

Figure 4.13: *i-Tree Eco* random plot generation function to estimate number of plots and study area size for the desired representation

We imported the corresponding shapefile in *i-Tree Eco* and performed the random plot generation with the objective of a 20% plot representation and not more than 60 plots with a radius of 11.3 meters (37.24 feet), since our working force resources to help on field-surveying were

limited, thus surveyed plot number had to stay reasonable. After reshaping several times the study area on *ArcGIS*, we finally reached the goal with 60 plots, a study area of 12 hectares and 20.31% of representation. However, 7 plots could not be accessed nor estimated during the field measurements, thus were not included in the study and the final representation percentage dropped to 17.94% of the study area (see Figure 4.13) with 53 plots.

Then, the random plots generation was done with *ArcGIS*, as the *i-Tree Eco* random plot definition did give a very heterogeneous distribution of plots. Finally, function “create random points” was used. Points are dispersed randomly all over the study area, as we do not have any interest to favour more public or private areas, and as the methodology needs to be the most transparent and following a precise methodology (no manual added action such as moving one plot which would overlap another one, which would change the formula of random plot creation).

The defined study area of 12 hectares represents 2.86% of the 419 hectares city of Turrialba. Thus it does not represent the city of Turrialba but just a small part of the city in the city centre, which is within the most urbanized part of the city. Indeed, the city expands quite far and the main activity centre is very small compared to residential areas. Finally this study area aims to represent the benefits of trees in the more compacted urban area, as well as on Rio Colorado and Rio Turrialba natural and artificial streambanks.

Figure 4.14: Position of the study area within Turrialba City with its districts

Figure 4.15: Study area divided in four zones (later called strata) and the field-surveyed plots

As it is seen on picture 4.15, the study area was also divided into four equal parts of 3 hectares each, called Rio “Turrialba”, “Rio Colorado”, “Puente Negro” and “Estacion de tren”, relatively to their main attributes on the site. These parcels were basically created in order to divide the field work in four measurement groups but were then of great relevance in the *i-Tree Eco* simulation, notably in the process of urban forest structure statistical estimation.

2.1.b Field protocol

Obviously the most precise way to assess urban forest structure is to measure and record information on every tree. A complete survey may work well for relatively small populations (e.g. street trees, small parks) but is cost-prohibitive for larger tree populations. Thus, random sampling can provide a cost-effective means to assess urban forest structure and functions [118] and this “Plot Sample” method is chosen at creation of an *i-Tree Eco* project rather than “Complete Inventory”.

Whereas an “Eco collector” is available with the *i-Tree Suite* to collect data during the field work in order to avoid losing data or limit data uncertainties especially due to hand-writing. However, this involved being able to provide a tablet for every helper on the field which implies a lot of resources. Thus the field inventory was performed simply through printing tables with all measured attributes, to fill in by hand on the field. Plots and pictures of respectively North-East-South-West from the centre of the plot as well as the trees present on the plot,

were also inputted in a smartphone application called “AlpineQuest” creating KML files with georeferenced information.

Typically, all field data are collected during the leaf-on season to properly assess tree canopies. In this case, it is not an issue since most of tree species present on the site are evergreen.

In the following table 4.2, field collected data is listed and associated with its specific use in the model: A is associated to air pollution removal; C to carbon storage and/or sequestration; E to energy conservation; H to hydrologic effects; S to structural information and V to VOC emissions. If plot center falls on a building or other surface (such as a highway) where plot center cannot be accessed, the plot is not moved; all distances and directions to trees are measured and recorded from a recorded fixed point (e.g. building corner) referred to as the TMP. The exact coordinates of the trees are also taken.

Variable	Description
Tree ID	Unique tree number
Distance (m) and direction (degrees) from plot center or TMP	Used to identify and locate trees for future measurements; TMP is tree measurement point
Species code (A, C, E, S, V)	Species code from standard i-Tree database list currently containing over 10,000 tree and shrub species
Number of dbhs recorded	For multi-stemmed trees
Dbh (C, S)	Diameter at breast height (cm) for all recorded stems
Dbh measurement height	Recorded if dbh is not measured at 1.37 m
Total height (A, C, E, S, V)	Height to top of tree (m)
Height to crown base (A, S, V)	Height to base of live crown (m)
Crown width (A, S, V)	Recorded by two measurements: N-S (north-south) and E-W (east-west) widths (m)
Percent canopy missing (A, S, V)	The percent of the crown volume that is not occupied by leaves; two perpendicular measures of missing leaf mass are made and the average result is recorded; recorded to nearest 5%
Dieback (C, E, S)	Percent crown dieback to nearest 5%
Percent impervious beneath canopy (H)	Percent of land area beneath entire tree canopy’s drip line that is impervious
Percent shrub cover beneath canopy (H)	Percent of land area beneath canopy drip line that is occupied by shrubs
Crown light exposure (C, S)	Number of sides of the tree receiving sunlight from above; used to estimate competition and growth rates
Distance (m) and direction (degrees) to space-conditioned residential buildings (E)	Measured for trees at least 6.1 m tall and within 18.3 m of structures three floors or less in height
Street tree	Y/N; used to estimate proportion of population that is street trees
Tree status	Indicates if tree is new or removed from last measurement period

Table 4.2: Tree variables collected for *i-Tree Eco* simulation with associated reason for data collection

In order to perform the field inventory, in a limited time with limited resources, we partnered with an environmental focused high school in Pejibaje, *Colegio Ambientalista de Pejibaye* supporting the 6-people team from CATIE (2 coordinators and 4 technical contributors). Approximately 11 students were divided into the four measurement groups, after two training sessions to understand the study context, learn the inventory protocol and especially how to use the different tools available for each group (see Figure 4.17). Moreover, the municipality of Turrialba partnered to get access and accompany on areas classified as risk areas.

Figure 4.16: Field work and training pictures with the technical team (CATIE) and students from *Colegio Ambientalista de Pejibaye*

Figure 4.17: Measurement tools used on the field. Top-left: hypsometer; top-right: meter tape; down-left: compass; down-right: diameter tape.

In order to avoid confusions on the field and work on the same basis for measuring the DBH (Diameter at Breast Height), the crown height and estimating the crown condition such as missing percentage and health, a set of field work information sheets were used such as the one presented Figure 4.18. The remaining sheets can be seen in Appendix C.

CROWN CONDITION – % Solar light exposure

Figure 4.18: One of the field work information sheets to use as references for tree measurements: Crown condition - % Solar light exposure; based on i-Tree Field work manual in Spanish[119]

Once field work is done and once a project has been created in *i-Tree Eco* using “Plot Sample” and entering location, year, meteorological station, measured attributes of field plots to include and study area zones in hectares, all measured inventory data is entered manually in the tab data > plots and trees. First plot information, then ground cover, land-uses and trees related to the plot. Each tree specie entered is related with its characteristics in i-Tree database that can be seen Appendix A. for the set of trees used in this case study.

2.2 Existing data input and assumptions

2.2.a Meteorological data

At project creation level, it is required to choose one weather station among the available ones depending on i-Tree database [109] and on the official data from the NCDC (National Climatic Data Centre) which is the meteorological data provider of the software. This data is typically hourly or 6-hourly (ISH (Integrated Surface Hourly) format for the surface weather data and FDL (not necessarily hourly format) format for upper air data). For hourly data, the timestamps are adjusted to the nearest next top-of-hour. 6-hourly data is disaggregated to hourly values assuming a uniform distribution (e.g. 1 cm over 6 hours is equal to 1/6cm each hour for the 6 hour time period [120]). NCDC values include wind speed, cloud ceiling height, sky cover, temperature, dew point temperature, station altimeter setting, station pressure, 1-hour liquid precipitation for surface weather variables and height, pressure, temperature for upper air variables. In the weather pre-processor, additional surface and upper air parameters are created from these parameters (see Part 4.21). See Hirabayashi et al. (2016) [95] for further explanations on how the output variables such as solar zenith angle and solar radiation are calculated. Those calculations are based on physical formulas and hypothesis.

The NCDC data is the default data used in the software and linked with each available weather station but does usually not include air pollution data. The latter data can be submitted by the user if hourly data is available on the study site (it is asked for hourly concentrations of CO , NO_2 , O_3 , $PM_{2.5}$, SO_2 as well as the pollution monitor source, latitude and longitude). Moreover precipitation data can also be submitted if the user disposes of more accurate hourly data, or, such as in our case, if there is no weather station available in the area of study (this is the case for most locations outside of the US). User-submitted data is then reviewed through i-Tree team and integrated in the database at next update, linked to the location for air pollution data and replacing default NCDC values of a specific weather station for the precipitation data.

This way, we have done several requests and applications to the potential references holding this type of data for the city of Turrialba. We finally managed to get hourly precipitation data of Turrialba years 2017 and 2018 from the National Meteorological Institute of Costa Rica (IMN). This data was incorporated in the system by the end of March when the second 2020 update has been done. It is linked with the meteorological station of Tobias Bolanos International Airport, since looking at the temperature profile, it is the closest to Turrialba among the three available weather stations in Costa Rica (the two others are Limon on the Caribbean coast and Juan Santamaria International Airport). Concerning air pollution data, we did not succeed to find any (UCR University of Cota Rica was a potential target). Nevertheless, weather data is the key input to run the model whereas air pollution data is optional.

When creating a new project, although the field data is from the current year, it is possible to choose another year and a weather station that is not on the same location, assuming that the

outdate year of data has a similar climate tendency than the case study year.

How to choose the best weather station year and location when weather data from NCDC is not available for the study site area, is the challenge for such a case study with scarce data availability, with the US based *i-Tree Eco* software. By selecting different years, and selecting a weather station, a map (see Figure 4.19) appears where it is possible to see all available weather stations with a summary including the weather station location (elevation, latitude, longitude), the status of collection completeness (poor, fair or good), the annual precipitation data collected hourly and every 6 hours. If the latter values are very low or equal to 0, it can be assumed that the collected data is scarce and results using this data cannot be validated as it will not be representative of the study area.

Since from one year to another it can vary a lot, it is important to look up different years while choosing the most recent possible year. In fact, since the field measurements are current data, it is more accurate to use recent weather data.

Figure 4.19: *i-Tree Eco* weather station selector map and related information

Furthermore, it is important to choose a weather station that is the closest to the climate zone of the study area. For this purpose, it is also possible for one chosen weather station and year, to download and visualizing the hourly data sets of precipitation, temperature and photosynthetically active radiation in the reports tab when a project is created until the running stage. This way, for each variable, the tendency can be seen and compared to the variable tendency of the study area. If the tendency similarity is not verified, it is still possible to edit the project configuration (first steps) and choose another weather station without modifying

the other parameters or input data. Then the project has to be run again.

In our case, the hourly precipitation data used from NCDC is scarce for each available years and for all three available weather stations, thus not representative of Turrialba city precipitation. Hence, it was very important to research local hourly precipitation data to be submitted in the software although the delay was expected to be long. In fact, IMN precipitation data has been processed on a very late stage of the project and it had to be pursued in the meantime.

Thus, a sensitivity analysis has been performed (see Part 5.) to understand more precisely how the model reacts to different meteorological and field data sets.

2.2.b Location data

Beside field-surveyed urban forest data, *i-Tree eco* uses location specific data. A location, if not basically available in the software, has to be added to i-Tree database in the same way than precipitation and air pollution data. It includes name and type (Turrialba city, Turrialba Canton, Cartago Province), latitude and longitude, elevation (646 m), population (27,207), area in square meters (4,190,000 m^2), climate zone (US region whose climate is most similar to climate of new location), general albedo data (such as occurrence of warm temperatures, abundant rain, abundant vegetation, snow and ozone state (US state whose ozone depth is most similar to ozone depth of new location, here *Florida* based on World wide daily ozone map [121]). Optional data includes electricity emissions (Costa Rican value found is of $58gCO_2eq/kWh$ [122]), leaf on and leaf off day of year, mean minimum temperature (63.1°F).

Climate zone data is exclusively used to estimate energy effects of trees on buildings. The chosen climate zone for Turrialba is 2A (hot-humid) according to the US energy department method ANSI/ASHRAE 90.1-2007 [123]. With available choices in the submission form, *Southeast* was chosen as equivalent climate zone region in the US.

Albedo value derived from general albedo data is used to calculate solar radiation reached to leaves that determines photosynthesis through which some pollutants are absorbed by the stomata (represented by the stomatal resistance calculation in the dry deposition model 3.1.b).

2.2.c Benefit prices

Under the tab “Data > Inventory value”, benefit prices used to calculate the benefits of trees in monetary terms by multiplying these unit values in the local currency (CRC in Costa Rica) by the physical quantity calculated in the model (avoided electricity (in kWh), stored carbon (in ton), avoided runoff (in cubic meters) removed quantity of pollutant (in ton)). By entering the currency exchange rate, the results are then given in US Dollars.

According to the reached values for Costa Rica, not all fields were filled but the following ones: benefit of electricity 82.97 CRC/kWh (based on the cost of electricity), benefit of carbon

compensation 4242.55 CRC/ton (7.5 US \$/ton based on the National Fund of Forest Financing (Fonafifo) webpage [124]) and benefit of avoided runoff 1351.5 CRC/ m^3 equivalent to the US average (0.008936\$/gallon). The latter US average monetary value was calculated and applied based on 16 studies of costs of stormwater control, called “Community Tree Guides” published by the US Forest Service. In the Tropical Community Tree Guide [25], to estimate the value of rainfall intercepted by urban trees, stormwater management control costs are based on construction and operation costs for a typical detention/retention basin in Honolulu (Hawaii). The total annual costs of the basin (20-years costs annualized since it is the typical life cycle of this infrastructure) is calculated by summing annualized installment costs (187.567\$/year), construction costs (6577\$/year) and operation and maintenance costs (719\$/year). Divided by the amount of runoff captured in the basin over the course of a typical year, it give the average annual control cost per unit runoff water of 0.01\$/gallon. In the Northern Mountain and Prairie community tree guide [125], same assumptions were used by using detention/retention basin in Fort Collins, CO. Assuming that the basin filled once annually for 20 years, they got the annual control cost of 0.0108\$/gallon which is very close to the previous study. However, by considering the costs associated with collection, transport, and treatment sewer service fees per water volume and per dwelling unit (0.004\$/gallon/dwelling unit), the Northern California coast community tree guide [126] inferred the value of 0.004\$/gallon very far from the other studies. In addition, in the Northeast community tree guide [127], the value of 0.04\$/gallon was used, based on the projected costs and water savings from the Water and Sewer Authority’s 2002 Long-Term Control Plan in Washington, D.C. Thus, these estimations of money saved by avoiding one gallon of water runoff depends on the local specific costs and on the chosen reasoning which should also be chosen according to the local context. The lack of information in Turrialba did not allow to do so.

For case studies in the US, default air pollution removal values are calculated based on local incidence of adverse health effects and national median externality costs (using data from the US Environmental Protection Agency’s Environmental Benefits Mapping and Analysis Program (BenMAP)) [91]. Carbon storage and carbon sequestration economic values are calculated with following default economic value [128]: 4243 CRC/ton.

Furthermore, annual costs linked to the maintenance and management of the urban forest (planting, pruning, tree removal, pest control, irrigation, repair, clean-up, legal, administrative, inspection, etc.) can also be inputted in the software, although it was not done in this case study.

3. *i-Tree Eco* model and implementation

3.1 Model description

Before entering more in depth into the model descriptions, diagrams figure 4.21 and 4.20 synthesize visually which variables are calculated in each model and how they are interconnected. Each arrow (except first arrows showing which variables are linked with each model) means “calculated with”. For the sake of clarity, the direct linkages of variables $Dt, Iv, Rv, Rg, Ig, Ev, Evi, Ep, Egi, Egp$ with maximum storage capacities $Si_{max}, Sp_{max}, Sv_{max}$ are not represented. Furthermore, all above variables calculated by the weather pre-processor are calculated with the raw input meteorological data, mostly from NCDC (see Part 2.2).

Figure 4.20: Diagram of i-Tree precipitation-interception model and weather pre-processor calculated variables, their interlinkages and other parameters they depend on

Figure 4-21: Diagram of i-Tree dry deposition model calculated variables, their interlinkages and other parameters they depend on

3.1.a Precipitation-Interception model description

This model description is based on the report of Satoshi Hirabayashi, 2013 [68]. From version 5 of *i-Tree Eco* the model is capable to estimate precipitation intercepted by vegetation that can contribute to the reduction of stormwater.

The precipitation-interception model implemented in *i-Tree Eco* version 5 was developed based on *i-Tree Hydro* [28]. In typical sampling *i-Tree Eco* projects (plot-based sampling), the area of interest is partially covered by vegetation (trees or shrubs) and the other is impermeable or permeable ground cover. The model assumes that precipitation is uniformly distributed over the area, some portion of which falls on the area covered by vegetation and the others fall on the ground area. The precipitation fell on the vegetation is partially intercepted by leaves, and the remainder reaches the ground under the canopy. The precipitation reached on the ground (directly and/or through canopy) is partially intercepted by depressions on the ground and the remainder infiltrates to the ground of permeable cover or run offs over impermeable cover. This surface runoff over impermeable cover contributes to the flush stormwater.

In case of a full inventory project (not a plot-based sampling project), the area of interested is assumed to be 100% covered by vegetation and only the ground cover precipitation interception model is considered [68].

In addition to the actual scenario described above, the hypothetical scenario, in which the same area of interest is not covered by vegetation at all, is considered in the model. Figures 4.22, 4.23 illustrates these two scenarios. In both scenarios, hourly precipitation interception processes are first calculated (all variables expressed in terms of depth in meters) and total annual surface runoff volume (expressed in cubic meters) is then calculated. Usually, the actual scenario produces less surface runoff than the hypothetical scenario due to the effect of vegetation that intercepts, stores, and evaporates rain water. By taking difference in surface runoff between the two scenarios, the effect of vegetation in reducing the surface runoff can be determined as **net avoided runoff by vegetation**.

Figure 4.22: *i-Tree Eco* precipitation-interception model actual scenario [68]

Figure 4.23: *i-Tree Eco* precipitation-interception model hypothetical scenario [68]

In the case of a plot-based sampling project, two process types are identified: hourly precipitation interception process for vegetated cover and hourly precipitation interception process for ground cover. The vegetated cover interception process is divided into three isolated sub-processes: interception by vegetation, by impermeable cover under canopy and by permeable cover under canopy. The ground cover interception process is divided into two isolated processes: interception by impermeable cover and by permeable cover. In addition, each isolated sub-process involves variables representing storage, evaporation, runoff, dripping or infiltration which are calculated according to three temporal successive stages happening under a time period starting with a precipitation event (stage 1 and 2) and ending with a dry event (stage 3).

Figure 4.24: Precipitation-interception model processes isolation

Hence, each sub-process described in Figure 4.24 is divided for calculations into 3 stages: stage 1 from the start of a precipitation event until full storage capacity is reached (storage capacity of canopy for the vegetated cover interception and storage capacity of the ground for ground cover interception); stage 2 from the fully achieved storage capacity (when subsequent precipitation reaches the ground in the vegetated interception case or runs off in the ground cover interception case) until the end of the rain event; stage 3 from the end of the rain event when intercepted precipitation starts to dry.

In the following hourly precipitation interception model descriptions, all variables are hourly, although they may be expressed in meters instead of meters per hour.

Hourly precipitation interception model for vegetated cover

Figure 4.25 represents how variables from each vegetated cover precipitation interception sub-process according to the three stages, are linked to each other. According to a tree-structure, precipitation variable P is split into in-canopy precipitation variable P_c and through-canopy precipitation variable P_t . Then, respectively to the three isolated sub-processes (interception through: vegetation (P_c), impervious ground cover under canopy (P_t), pervious ground cover under canopy (P_t)) and the three stages, P_c and P_t are transformed into storage (depression storage in case of ground cover), evaporation, dripping from canopy, overland runoff or infiltration.

The three sub-processes or happening simultaneously on the same area covered by vegetation and the only variable linking them is the dripping from canopy process which adds to through-canopy precipitation P_t from stage 2 of vegetation interception for the impervious and pervious ground cover under canopy interception. Diagram figure 4.25 schematizes the model considered processes and stages. However it should not be read as a timeline from phase 1 to phase 3 since each phase does not have the same duration for vegetation, impervious ground or pervious ground processes. In fact, the end of stage 1 is determined by the reaching of full storage capacity of either vegetation storage or impervious or pervious ground depression storage, which are not equal ($S_{v_{max}} \neq S_{i_{max}} \neq S_{p_{max}}$). Since successive stages 1 and 2 last the time of the rain event, stage 3 starts at the same time for the three sub-process types. Hence, water dripping off the leaves can start either when depression storage on the ground is still filling up or if the water on the ground has started to infiltrate or to runoff. For the sake of schematic drawing clarity, the latter information has not been represented on the diagram.

Figure 4.25: Vegetated cover interception model over successively precipitation and non-precipitation event and according to processes type isolation

For a more physical representation, following figures illustrate all variables involved in the vegetated cover precipitation interception model for in-canopy precipitation P_c (Figure 4.26) and for through-canopy precipitation P_t (Figure 4.27).

Figure 4.26: Vegetated cover precipitation interception model variables for in-canopy precipitation (P_c) [68]

Figure 4.27: Vegetated cover precipitation interception model variables for through-canopy precipitation (P_t); left: impervious cover under canopy, right: pervious cover under canopy [68]

In-canopy precipitation at time t (P_{c_t}) is calculated as the difference between precipitation at time t and through-canopy precipitation at time t :

$$P_{c_t} = P_t - P_{t_t} \quad (4.1)$$

Through-canopy precipitation reaching the ground at time t (P_{t_t}) is calculated as ([129]):

$$P_{t_t} = P_t(1 - c) \quad (4.2)$$

where c is the canopy cover fraction related to the canopy LAI (Leaf Area Index) such as:

$$c = 1 - e^{-kLAI} \quad (4.3)$$

where k is an extinction coefficient (worth 0.7 for trees and 0.3 for shrubs) ([28]).

Interception by vegetation

At stage 1, vegetation storage at time t (Sv_t) is calculated as:

$$Sv_t = Sv_{t-1} + Pc_t - Ev_{t-1} \quad (4.4)$$

The end of stage 1 in the vegetation interception process happens when $Sv_t = Sv_{max}$. If $Sv_t < 0$, 0 is set to Sv_t , whereas if $Sv_t \geq Sv_{max}$, Sv_{max} is set to Sv_t and the first stage ends. Sv_{max} is calculated as:

$$Sv_{max} = S_L * LAI \quad (4.5)$$

where S_L is the specific leaf storage of water and is equal to $2 * 10^{-4}$ meters.

Evaporation from vegetation at time t (Ev_t) is calculated as:

$$Ev_t = \left(\frac{Sv_t}{Sv_{max}} \right)^{2/3} * PE_t \quad (4.6)$$

where PE_t is the potential evaporation at time t calculated by the i-Tree weather pre-processor (see the end of Part 3.1.a and Appendix D. for more detailed information about the calculation).

In stage 2, full storage capacity is reached and thus Pc is not stored anymore and drips from canopy (D) while evaporation occurs from the storage throughout the stage.

At the start of stage 2, $Sv_t = Sv_{max}$, and at the very beginning $Sv_{t-1} < Sv_{max}$. At this time t_0 , canopy drip is calculated as:

$$D_{t_0} = Pc_t - (Sv_{max} - Sv_{t-1}) - Ev_t \quad (4.7)$$

Then, it is calculated as:

$$D_t = Pc_t - Ev_t \quad (4.8)$$

Evaporation from vegetation at time t (Ev_t) is still calculated with equation 4.6 in stage 2 and 3 during the latter only evaporation from vegetation occurs. Since $Sv_t = Sv_{max}$ during stages 2 and 3, evaporation at time t is equal to the potential evaporation from vegetation at time t (PE_t).

Interception by impervious cover under canopy

When considering the sub-process of interception by impervious cover under canopy, the amount of precipitation reaching the ground at time t is the sum of D_t and Pt_t which is equivalent to Pt_t during stage 1 and higher than Pt_t during stages 2 and 3.

At stage 1, impervious cover depression storage at time t (Svi_t) is calculated as:

$$Svi_t = Svi_{t-1} + (Pt_t + D_t) - Evi_{t-1} \quad (4.9)$$

The end of stage 1 happens when $Svi_t = Si_{max}$. If $Svi_t < 0$, 0 is set to Svi_t , whereas if $Svi_t \geq Si_{max}$, Si_{max} is set to Svi_t and the first stage ends. Si_{max} is constant and equal to $1.5 * 10^{-3}$ meters.

Evaporation from impervious cover at time t (Evi_t) is calculated as:

$$Evi_t = \left(\frac{Svi_t}{Si_{max}} \right) * PEg_t \quad (4.10)$$

where PEg_t is the potential ground evaporation at time t calculated by the i-Tree weather pre-processor (see the end of part 3.1.a and Appendix D. for more detailed information about the calculation).

Overland runoff at time t (Rv_t) is calculated as:

$$Rv_t = (Pt_t + D_t) - (Si_{max} - Svi_{t-1}) - Evi_t \quad (4.11)$$

In stage 2, full depression storage capacity is reached and thus $Pt+D$ is not stored anymore and runs off overland while evaporation occurs from the storage throughout the stage.

During this stage, $Svi_t = Si_{max}$, and overland runoff at time t is calculated as:

$$Rv_t = (Pt_t + D_t) - Evi_t \quad (4.12)$$

Evaporation from impervious ground cover at time t (Evi_t) is still calculated with equation 4.10 in stage 2 and 3 during the latter only evaporation occurs. Since $Svi_t = Si_{max}$ during stages 2 and 3, evaporation at time t is equal to the potential ground evaporation at time t (PEg_t).

Interception by pervious cover under canopy

When considering the sub-process of interception by pervious cover under canopy, the amount of precipitation reaching the ground at time t is the sum of D_t and Pt_t which is equivalent to Pt_t during stage 1 and higher than Pt_t during stages 2 and 3.

At stage 1, pervious cover depression storage at time t (Svp_t) is calculated as:

$$Svp_t = Svp_{t-1} + (Pt_t + D_t) - Evp_{t-1} \quad (4.13)$$

The end of stage 1 happens when $Svp_t = Sp_{max}$. If $Svp_t < 0$, 0 is set to Svp_t , whereas if $Svp_t \geq Sp_{max}$, Sp_{max} is set to Svp_t and the first stage ends. Sp_{max} is constant and equal to $*10^{-3}$ meters.

Evaporation from pervious cover at time t (Evp_t) is calculated as:

$$Evp_t = \left(\frac{Svp_t}{Sp_{max}} \right) * PEg_t \quad (4.14)$$

where PEg_t is the potential ground evaporation at time t calculated by the i-Tree weather pre-processor (see the end of part 3.1.a and Appendix D. for more detailed information about the calculation).

Infiltration at time t (Iv_t) is calculated as:

$$Iv_t = (Pt_t + D_t) - (Sp_{max} - Svp_{t-1}) - Evp_t \quad (4.15)$$

In stage 2, full depression storage capacity is reached and thus $Pt+D$ is not stored anymore and infiltrates in the pervious ground while evaporation occurs from the storage throughout the stage.

During this stage, $Svp_t = Sp_{max}$, and infiltration at time t is calculated as:

$$Iv_t = (Pt_t + D_t) - Evp_t \quad (4.16)$$

Evaporation from pervious ground cover at time t (Evp_t) is still calculated with equation 4.14 in stage 2 and 3 during the latter only evaporation occurs. Since $Svp_t = Sp_{max}$ during stages 2 and 3, evaporation at time t is equal to the potential ground evaporation at time t (PEg_t).

Hourly precipitation interception model for ground cover

Similarly as Figure 4.25, Figure 4.28 represents how variables from ground cover precipitation interception model divided into impervious and pervious ground cover interception and according to the three stages are linked to each other.

For a non-vegetated cover, all precipitation reaches the ground, thus precipitation P is not divided into sub-variables such as for vegetated cover. Same variables of depression storage, evaporation, dripping from canopy, overland runoff or infiltration are calculated for each isolated sub-process. Since there is no dripping from canopy, no variable is added to precipitation P for the calculations from stage 2.

Figure 4.28: Ground cover interception model over successively precipitation and non-precipitation event and according to processes type isolation

Such as Figure 4.27, for a more physical representation, following Figure 4.29 illustrates all variables involved in the ground cover precipitation interception model for pervious and for impervious cover.

Figure 4.29: Ground cover precipitation interception model variables; left: impervious cover, right: pervious cover [68]

Interception by impervious cover

At stage 1, impervious cover depression storage at time t (Sgi_t) is calculated as:

$$Sgi_t = Sgi_{t-1} + P_t - Egi_{t-1} \quad (4.17)$$

The end of stage 1 happens when $Sgi_t = Si_{max}$. If $Sgi_t < 0$, 0 is set to Sgi_t , whereas if $Sgi_t \geq Si_{max}$, Si_{max} is set to Sgi_t and the first stage ends. Si_{max} is constant and equal to $1.5 * 10^{-3}$ meters.

Evaporation from impervious cover at time t (Egi_t) is calculated as:

$$Egi_t = \left(\frac{Sgi_t}{Si_{max}} \right) * PEg_t \quad (4.18)$$

where PEg_t is the potential ground evaporation at time t calculated by the i-Tree weather pre-processor (see the end of part 3.1.a and Appendix D. for more detailed information about the calculation).

Overland runoff at time t (Rg_t) is calculated as:

$$Rg_t = P_t - (Si_{max} - Sgi_{t-1}) - Egi_t \quad (4.19)$$

In stage 2, full depression storage capacity is reached and thus P is not stored anymore and runs off overland while evaporation occurs from the storage throughout the stage.

During this stage, $Sgi_t = Si_{max}$, and overland runoff at time t is calculated as:

$$Rg_t = P_t - Egi_t \quad (4.20)$$

Evaporation from impervious ground cover at time t (Egi_t) is still calculated with equation 4.18 in stage 2 and 3 during the latter only evaporation occurs. Since $Sgi_t = Si_{max}$ during stages 2 and 3, evaporation at time t is equal to the potential ground evaporation at time t (PEg_t).

Interception by pervious cover

At stage 1, pervious cover depression storage at time t (Sgp_t) is calculated as:

$$Sgp_t = Sgp_{t-1} + P_t - Egp_{t-1} \quad (4.21)$$

The end of stage 1 happens when $Sgp_t = Sp_{max}$. If $Sgp_t < 0$, 0 is set to Sgp_t , whereas if $Sgp_t \geq Sp_{max}$, Sp_{max} is set to Sgp_t and the first stage ends. Sp_{max} is constant and equal to $*10^{-3}$ meters.

Evaporation from pervious cover at time t (Egp_t) is calculated as:

$$Egp_t = \left(\frac{Sgp_t}{Sp_{max}} \right) * PEg_t \quad (4.22)$$

where PEg_t is the potential ground evaporation at time t calculated by the i-Tree weather pre-processor (see the end of part 3.1.a and Appendix D. for more detailed information about the calculation).

Infiltration at time t (Ig_t) is calculated as:

$$Iv_t = P_t - (Sp_{max} - Sgp_{t-1}) - Egp_t \quad (4.23)$$

In stage 2, full depression storage capacity is reached and thus P is not stored anymore and infiltrates in the pervious ground while evaporation occurs from the storage throughout the stage.

During this stage, $Sgp_t = Sp_{max}$, and infiltration at time t is calculated as:

$$Ig_t = P_t - Egp_t \quad (4.24)$$

Evaporation from pervious ground cover at time t (Egp_t) is still calculated with equation 4.22 in stage 2 and 3 during the latter only evaporation occurs. Since $Sgp_t = Sp_{max}$ during stages 2 and 3, evaporation at time t is equal to the potential ground evaporation at time t (PEg_t).

Annual precipitation interception process

Hourly processes are expressed in terms of the depth in meters. For annual processes, they can be converted into cubic meters by taking areas into consideration. All variables related to vegetation i.e. precipitation P, in-canopy precipitation Pc, through-canopy precipitation Pt, vegetation storage Sv, evaporation from vegetation Ev, canopy drip D, are annually summed up and multiplied by the area covered by vegetation (VA in square meters). All variables related to pervious and impervious ground cover i.e. overland runoff Rv, Rg; evaporation from the ground Evi, Evp, Egi, Egp; infiltration Iv, Ig; depression storage Svi, Svp, Sgi, Sgp, are annually summed up and multiplied by either area covered by vegetation if it concerns ground under canopy (VA in square meters) or area not covered by canopy (GA in square meters) and finally multiplied by the percentage of the study area covered by either pervious or impervious ground relatively to the considered sub-process (pervious or impervious ground interception). Since overland runoff only occurs in case of impervious cover, to obtain the annual total runoff of the actual scenario mixing area covered by vegetation and ground cover, the annual sum of runoff from impervious cover under canopy and the annual sum of runoff from impervious cover without canopy are respectively multiplied by VA and GA and by the percentage u of impervious ground cover of the study area:

$$R_{total} = ((\sum Rv_t * VA) + (\sum Rg_t * GA)) * u \quad (4.25)$$

R_{total} is expressed in m^3 . In order to get the total annual net avoided runoff due to precipitation intercepted by vegetation AR_{total} [m^3], the total runoff of the hypothetical scenario Rh_{total} [m^3] (calculated with total study area A, percentage of impervious cover u and runoff by impervious cover without vegetation Rg) is subtracted to the total runoff of the actual scenario:

$$Rh_{total} = \sum Rg_t * A * u \quad AR_{total} = R_{total} - Rh_{total} \quad (4.26)$$

In addition, in order to get the net annual avoided runoff by species in the study area AR_s [m^3], the following calculation, in case of sample projects (no inventory projects):

$$AR_s = AR_{total} * \frac{LA_s}{\sum LA} \quad (4.27)$$

with LA_s the leaf area for species s across the study area and $\sum LA$ the sum of leaf area for all trees across the study area.

Potential evaporation and evapotranspiration

In order to get a brief overview of the calculation method of potential evaporation for ground and vegetation as well as potential evapotranspiration, the equations below can be compared by identifying which elements are considered in each calculation: Potential evaporation PE and potential evapotranspiration from trees PET in $m.hr^{-1}$ are calculated by the modified Penman-Monteith equation [130]:

$$PE = \frac{1}{\lambda\rho_w} \left[\frac{\Delta R_n + \frac{\rho_a c_p D}{r_a}}{\Delta + \gamma} \right] * 10^{-3} \quad (4.28) \quad PET = \frac{1}{\lambda\rho_w} \left[\frac{\Delta R_n + \frac{\rho_a c_p D}{r_a}}{\Delta + \gamma \left(1 + \frac{r_s}{r_a}\right)} \right] * 10^{-3} \quad (4.29)$$

Most of the elements of these equations depend on temperature and pressure (measured surface pressure) and constants of water such as dew point temperature, specific heat of moist air. In equation 4.28, r_a [$s.m^{-1}$], aerodynamic resistance, is calculated differently according to the considered surface: trees or ground.

For potential evaporation from trees the calculation of r_a (4.30) is computed using the wind estimate height for trees ($Z_t=7$ meters), the roughness height for tree ($d_t=0.95$ meters), the wind speed at tree top (U_t see equation 4.32) which is the measured wind speed U corrected with roughness height for water ($d_w=1.37*10^{-3}$ meters), wind measurement height ($Z_u=2$ meters) and wind estimate height for trees (Z_t).

For potential evaporation from ground the calculation of r_a (4.31) is computed using the wind measurement height ($Z_u=2$ meters), the roughness height for water ($d_w=1.37*10^{-3}$ meters), the wind speed on the ground (U_g see equation 4.33) which is the measured wind speed U corrected with roughness height for water, wind measurement height and wind estimate height for the ground ($Z_g=0.1+d_w$).

$$r_a = \frac{4.72 \left(\ln \frac{Z_t}{Z_{ov} d_t} \right)^2}{1 + 0.536 U_t} \quad (4.30)$$

$$r_a = \frac{4.72 \left(\ln \frac{Z_u}{Z_{ov} d_w} \right)^2}{1 + 0.536 U_g} \quad (4.31)$$

where respectively:

$$U_t = U \frac{\ln \left(\frac{Z_t}{d_w} \right)}{\ln \left(\frac{Z_u}{d_w} \right)} \quad (4.32)$$

$$U_g = U \frac{\ln \left(\frac{Z_g}{d_w} \right)}{\ln \left(\frac{Z_u}{d_w} \right)} \quad (4.33)$$

In equation 4.29, r_a [$s.m^{-1}$] aerodynamic resistance related to the evaporation and transpiration processes and r_s [$s.m^{-1}$] stomatal resistance related to transpiration from trees, are calculated as shown below:

$$r_a = \frac{208}{U_t} \quad (4.34)$$

$$r_s = \frac{200}{LAI} \quad (4.35)$$

where U_t is the wind speed at the tree top calculated in equation 4.32 and LAI the leaf area index. Thus, the potential evapotranspiration PET depends on the species type.

3.1.b Dry deposition model description

With its dry deposition component (UFORE-D) integrated into *i-Tree Eco*, dry deposition of air pollution (i.e. pollution removal during non-precipitation periods) to trees and shrubs and associated percent improvement in air quality can be estimated with *i-Tree Eco*. This model description is based on the report of Satoshi Hirabayashi et al., 2015 [94].

In this model, deposition processes are considered linear: flux is proportional to the pollutant concentration. As an estimated without 3-dimensional considerations, air purification is considered to be a fraction of the flux that the tree absorbs.

Air pollutant flux calculation for CO, NO₂, SO₂ and O₃

Air pollutant flux F in $g.m^{-2}.h^{-1}$ at time t is calculated as a product of the deposition velocity $V_d [m.s^{-1}]$ and the air pollutant concentration $C [g.m^{-3}]$.

$$F = V_d.C.3600 \quad (4.36)$$

Minimum and maximum flux at time t are calculated likewise by using values of $V_{d,min}$ and $V_{d,max}$ at time t .

Deposition velocities for CO , NO_2 , SO_2 and O_3 are calculated as the inverse of the sum of the aerodynamic resistance R_a , quasi-laminar boundary layer resistance R_b , and the canopy resistance R_c , all in $s.m^{-1}$ ([131]). The aerodynamic resistance can be calculated with meteorological data as seen part 3.1.a and thus is independent of the air pollutant types, while the quasi-laminar boundary layer and canopy resistances are separately calculated for CO , NO_2 , SO_2 and O_3 . In addition, the canopy resistance is calculated depending on off-leaf and on-leaf periods. In this case study, since the biome is tropical, only on-leaf period will be considered.

$$V_d = \frac{1}{R_a + R_b + R_c} \quad (4.37)$$

The minimum and maximum values of V_d are estimated depending on the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) [132]:

- If $PAR > 0$ (at daytime):

	NO_2	O_3	SO_2
$V_{d,min}$	0.001	0.001	0.002
$V_{d,max}$	0.005	0.008	0.01

Table 4.3: Minimum and maximum estimations of V_d according to PAR level and to considered air pollutant

- If $PAR \leq 0$ (at nighttime): $V_{d,min} = V_d$ and $V_{d,max} = V_d$.

Aerodynamic resistance calculation

The aerodynamic resistance R_a is calculated based on meteorological data as ([133]):

$$R_a = \frac{u(z)}{u_*^2} \quad (4.38)$$

where $u(z)$ [$m.s^{-1}$] is the mean wind speed at height z and u_* [$m.s^{-1}$] the friction velocity. The latter variable depends on the stability of the atmosphere (i.e. neutral, unstable, stable) which can be determined by empirically estimated Monin-Obuhkov stability length L , based on the Pasquill stability class. Table below lists the empirical estimation (with z_o roughness length) of the stability length according to the Pasquill stability class.

Pasquill stability class	Monin-Obuhkov stability length estimation
A	$\frac{1}{L} = -0.0875.z_o^{-0.1029}$
B	$\frac{1}{L} = -0.03849.z_o^{-0.1714}$
C	$\frac{1}{L} = -0.0807.z_o^{-0.3049}$
D	$\frac{1}{L} = 0.z_o^{-0}$
E	$\frac{1}{L} = 0.0807.z_o^{-0.3049}$
F	$\frac{1}{L} = 0.03849.z_o^{-0.1714}$

Table 4.4: Monin-Obuhkov stability length empirical estimation according to Pasquill stability class [94]

Based on table 4.4 atmosphere is considered neutral when $L = 0$, unstable when $L < 0$, stable when $L > 0$. Calculations of friction velocity u_* is different according to the three atmosphere stability states and each method is detailed in Appendix E.

For the neutral atmosphere ($L = 0$), the friction velocity is calculated in the dry deposition model as Equation 4.39 where k is the von Karman constant ($=0.41$), $u(z)$ [$m.s^{-1}$] the mean wind speed at height z , z [m] height of the weather station, d [m] displacement height, z_o [m] roughness length.

$$u_* = \frac{k.u(z-d)}{\ln\left(\frac{z-d}{z_o}\right)} \quad (4.39)$$

The latter equation is recognized as the turbulence and logarithmic wind profile equation described by Monteith and Unsworth, 2013 [134]. A simple interpretation of the relation between the shape of the mean wind profile, turbulence, and stability is illustrated in Figure 4.30. In neutral stability Figure 4.30 a, the eddy structure can be envisaged as a set of circular

eddies with diameters increasing with height and given by the mixing length $l = kz$, rotating with tangential speed equal to the friction velocity u_* , i.e.:

$$w' = u' = u_* = l \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \quad (4.40)$$

where w' and u' represent the vertical and horizontal velocity fluctuations, respectively [135]. The qualitative effect of stability on the shape of the wind profiles is apparent in Figure 4.30 [a–c] and is summarized in semi-logarithmic form in Figure 4.30 d.

In each of the examples in Figure 4.30 the momentum flux transmitted to the surface is assumed the same, and so u_* is constant. Since, by differentiating equation 4.41, this requires the gradient of each profile at the lowest levels to be the same.

$$u_* = k \frac{\partial u}{\partial \ln(z-d)} \quad (4.41)$$

As height increases, velocity gradients become smaller in unstable conditions and larger in stable conditions than those for the neutral case.

Integrating equation 4.41 brings to equation 4.39.

Figure 4.30: Windspeed profiles and simplified eddy structures characteristic of the three basic stability states in air flow near the ground [135]

In addition, the aerodynamic resistances related to the evaporation of rain water from the surface of leaves, from the ground or evapotranspiration from trees, are determined by calculating

the wind speed at tree top U_t or wind speed on the ground U_g which are expressed similarly than friction velocity u_* but with the roughness height for water d_w instead of the roughness length z_o .

Quasi-laminar boundary layer resistance calculation

Quasi-laminar boundary layer resistance R_b is calculated as [136]:

$$R_b = 2(Sc)^{\frac{2}{3}}(Pr)^{-\frac{2}{3}}(ku_*)^{-1} \quad (4.42)$$

where Sc is the Schmidt number equal to 1 for O_3 , 0.76 for CO , 0.98 for NO_2 and 1.15 for SO_2 ; and Pr the Prandtl number equal to 0.72.

Canopy resistance calculation

For air pollutant CO , the removal by vegetation is not directly related to transpiration and its canopy resistance R_c [$s.m^{-1}$] is set to a constant based on data from Bidwell and Fraser, 1972 [137], different according to the leaf period (see table below):

In-leaf period	Out-of-leaf period
50,000	1,000,000

Table 4.5: Canopy resistance for CO according to the leaf period

The canopy resistances for NO_2 , O_3 and SO_2 can be calculated based on a hybrid of big-leaf and multi-layer canopy deposition models [131, 138], starting with this equation:

$$\frac{1}{R_c} = \frac{1}{r_s + r_m} + \frac{1}{r_t} + \frac{1}{r_{soil}} \quad (4.43)$$

where r_s is the stomatal resistance, r_m the mesophyll resistance, r_{soil} the soil resistance (= $2941s.m^{-1}$ in growing season and $2000s.m^{-1}$ otherwise) and r_t the cuticular resistance. Table 4.5 gives values of r_t and r_m for each air pollutant in $s.m^{-1}$:

Parameter	NO_2	O_3	SO_2
r_m	100 [139]	10 [139]	0 [140]
r_t	20,000 [140]	10,000 [132, 141]	8,000 [132, 141]

Table 4.6: Mesophyll and cuticular resistances for NO_2 , O_3 and SO_2 from literature [94]

Canopy resistance is the only calculation that considers soil in the dry-deposition model. The soil resistance is attributed to a constant value different according to growing season status. It

is not considering the different soil types. In equation 4.43 can be seen the model of Wesely [142] based on the following resistance network for different canopy layers Figure 4.31.

Figure 4.31: Resistance schematic for dry deposition model of Wesely [142]

r_a represents the aerodynamic resistance, r_b the boundary layer resistance and r_b the canopy resistance such as in equation 4.37. The term r_{st} represents the surface bulk resistance component for leaf stomata, r_m for leaf mesophyll resistance, r_{lu} for leaf cuticles in healthy vegetation and otherwise the outer surfaces in the upper canopy, r_{dc} for a gas-phase transfer affected by buoyant convection in canopies, r_{cl} for leaves, twig, bark or other exposed surfaces in the lower canopy, r_{ac} for transfer that depends only on canopy height and density and r_{gs} for the soil, leaf litter, etc., at the ground surface [142]. On the right hand side of the schematic is the complex model combining parallel and series resistances for vegetation, lower canopy and ground. On the left hand side is the simplified schematic with the equivalent resistances. The general formula of the canopy resistance that comes out:

$$\frac{1}{r_c} = \frac{1}{r_{st} + r_m} + \frac{1}{r_{lu}} + \frac{1}{r_{dc} + r_{cl}} + \frac{1}{r_{ac} + r_{gs}} \quad (4.44)$$

This formulation assumes that the concentrations representative of the plant mesophyll (C_m), substrates in the upper canopy (C_{lu}), substrates in the lower canopy (C_{cl}) and substrates at the ground surface (C_g) are in equilibrium with a single concentration C_c in air. In this model, all four substrate concentrations will be assumed to be zero (whereas it may be useful to use non-zero values for gases such as NO , NO_2 and NH_3 that are emitted from the surface, the distinctions among the substrate concentrations are not used in Wesely model).

The first and second terms of equation 4.44 are equivalent to first and second terms of equation 4.43. The lower canopy term of Wesely model is not considered in i-Tree dry deposition model

but the last term representing the ground resistance is considered through r_{soil} in equation 4.43.

For a bigger picture, another representation of the resistance model for gases including three surface categories (water, ground, vegetative canopy) is designed by Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006 ([143]) Figure 4.32. On this figure r_{cw} is the water resistance, r_{cg} the ground resistance and r_{cf} the foliar resistance. When a vegetative canopy is present, the surface resistance r_c is often referred to as the *canopy resistance*. The canopy resistance is the most difficult of the three to evaluate because of the complexity of vegetative surfaces. The capture of gases by vegetation depends ultimately on the accessibility of the gas to sites within the plant capable of absorbing the gas [143]. Thus, it depends on the chemical specie, on the canopy type and on meteorological conditions.

Figure 4.32: Extension of resistance model to include vegetative removal paths [143]

A number of pathways are available from the quasi-laminar layer to the vegetation canopy or ground, including uptake by plant tissue inside leaf pores (stomata), the waxy skin of some

leaves (cuticle), and mesophyll of leaves, deposition to the soil, and reactions with wetted surfaces. Each of these pathways can be represented by an appropriate resistance to transport; the total canopy resistance r_c is then determined by summing these resistances in parallel:

$$\frac{1}{r_c} = \frac{1}{r_{cf}} + \frac{1}{r_{cg}} \quad (4.45)$$

$$\frac{1}{r_{cf}} = \left(\frac{1}{r_{cut}} + \frac{1}{r_{st}} \right) LAI \quad (4.46)$$

The Seinfeld and Pandis model does not consider the resistances relative to the lower canopy (r_{dc} and r_{cl} in the Wesely model) and has therefore similar considerations than the i-Tree model: r_{cf}^{-1} is equivalent to $(r_m + r_s)^{-1} + r_t^{-1}$ and r_{cg} is equivalent to r_{soil} . Moreover, out of all possible deposition pathways of the latter model, not all of them are considered in the i-Tree dry deposition model: the vegetative and the ground one. Yet if a water surface is present, resistance r_{cw} is the resistance to uptake by water surfaces and replaces r_{cg} in equation 4.45, however, water surfaces are not taken into account for the canopy resistance calculation.

The stomatal resistance r_s calculation method is based on following observations from literature:

- The visible part of the solar spectrum from 400 to 700 nm, or synthetically active radiation (PAR) is largely absorbed to drive photosynthesis, while the near-infrared spectrum part (700-3000 nm) is largely scattered by vegetations [144];
- Direct beam and sky diffuse radiation are intercepted very differently by canopies [144], diffuse radiation is used much more efficiently than direct radiation by a canopy of photosynthesizing leaves [145];
- The stomatal resistance is linked to leaf photosynthesis [146];
- Calculating canopy photosynthetic rates from leaf photosynthetic rates requires dividing the canopy into N layers for which leaf area index is usually chosen as 0.1 or 0.2 [147];
- It is preferable to compute stomatal resistance on the basis of the irradiance on both sunlit and shaded leaves and weighing these resistances according to the fraction of sunlit and shaded leaf area [131].

Therefore, in order to perform the derivation of stomatal conductance g_s inverse of stomatal conductance r_s for the whole canopy, the following partitioning of the canopy and of the solar radiation above the canopy is effectuated:

Figure 4.33: Modelisation of canopy and solar radiation above canopy through partitioning for stomatal resistance calculation

It is assumed that shaded leaf area only gets diffuse radiation (red dotted line) whereas sunlit leaf area gets both direct and sunlit radiation (red and grey dotted line). After the above partitioning of the canopy and the solar radiation is performed, the following steps are computed:

- Flux density calculation of PAR intercepted by sunlit and shaded leaves in each layer of the canopy;
- Stomatal conductance calculation for sunlit and shaded leaves in each layer of the canopy;
- Stomatal conductance weighing for each layer according to the fraction of sunlit and shaded leaf area;
- Whole canopy stomatal conductance calculation by accumulating stomatal conductance for sunlit and shaded leaves throughout all layers.

The two last steps are computed by the following equation (equation 4.47) to calculate the weighted stomatal conductance for each layer j out of N layers and equation 4.48 to calculate the whole canopy stomatal conductance:

$$g_{s,j} = \Delta F_j^* g_{s,sun,j} + (\Delta F - \Delta F_j^*) g_{s,shade,j} \quad (4.47)$$

$$g_s = \sum_{j=1}^N g_{s,j} \quad (4.48)$$

where ΔF is the leaf area index in each layer chosen as 0.1 or 0.2 and ΔF_j^* is the sunlit leaf area index in the j^{th} layer. The difference $(\Delta F - \Delta F_j^*)$ is the shaded leaf area index in the j^{th}

layer.

The partitioning of the canopy in N layers and of the solar radiation as well as steps one and two of the list above, are detailed in Hirabayashi et al. (2015) [94].

Air pollutant flux calculation for PM2.5

Given that *i-Tree Eco* analyzes particulate matter less than 2.5 microns (PM2.5) which is a subset of PM10, PM10 has not been included in this analysis. Moreover, PM2.5 is generally more relevant in discussions concerning air pollution effects on human health. Deposition velocities of PM2.5 to trees are estimated from literature and vary with wind speed [58, 148, 149]. These papers measured deposition velocities to tree leaves from 17 tree species under wind speeds of 1, 3, 6, 8, 9 and 10 $m.s^{-1}$. For each wind speed, the median deposition velocities from the measured deposition velocities was used to estimate the deposition velocity of PM2.5 for that wind speed per unit leaf area (Table 4.7). Wind speed 8.5 $m.s^{-1}$ is chosen as a combination of deposition velocity values for wind speeds 8 and 9 $m.s^{-1}$.

Wind speed ($m.s^{-1}$)	1	3	6	8.5	10
Median V_d ($cm.s^{-1}$)	0.03	0.152	0.197	0.924	2.110
Standard Error (SE)	0.012	0.133	0.281	1.610	5.257
$V_{d,min}$	0.057	0.442	0.862	5.063	14.542
$V_{d,max}$	0.006	0.018	0.029	0.082	0.570

Table 4.7: Summary of average deposition velocities of PM2.5 by wind speed from the literature per unit leaf area

In table 4.7, the maximum deposition velocity adds $1.96 * SE$ to the median value. The minimum deposition velocity is based on the lowest recorded value within species considered from literature, since using the standard error to estimate the lower range produced negative deposition velocities. Moreover, the standard error of the estimates among the species is used to estimate a potential range of values of deposition velocities: to estimate the V_d for wind speeds between 1 and 10 $m.s^{-1}$ that do not have a measured value, values are interpolated from the closest measured values. For wind speeds above 10 $m.s^{-1}$, the V_d for 10 $m.s^{-1}$ is used; for a wind speed of 0 $m.s^{-1}$, the V_d is assumed to be 0 $m.s^{-1}$. Resuspension of PM2.5 from trees according to wind speed level is estimated from Pullman (2008) [148]. The latter paper measured resuspension percentages of PM2.5 from tree leaves of three tree species under wind speeds of 6.5, 10 and 13 $m.s^{-1}$. Such as for the deposition velocities, averages of percent resuspension are calculated between all three trees species from literature for each wind speed given above. Likewise, to estimate the percent resuspension for wind speeds between 0 and 13 $m.s^{-1}$ that did not have a measured resuspension rate, values were interpolated between the closest measured values. For wind speeds above 13 $m.s^{-1}$, the percent resuspension rate for 13 $m.s^{-1}$ is used; for a wind speed of 0 $m.s^{-1}$, the value is assumed to be 0%.

Wind speed($m.s^{-1}$)	Deposition Velocity ($cm.s^{-1}$)			Resuspension (%)
	Average	Minimum	Maximum	
0	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.0
1	0.03	0.006	0.042	1.5
2	0.09	0.012	0.163	3.0
3	0.15	0.018	0.285	4.5
4	0.17	0.022	0.349	6.0
5	0.19	0.025	0.414	7.5
6	0.20	0.029	0.478	9.0
7	0.56	0.056	1.506	10.0
8	0.92	0.082	2.534	11.0
9	0.92	0.082	2.534	12.0
10	2.11	0.570	7.367	13.0
11	2.11	0.570	7.367	16.0
12	2.11	0.570	7.367	20.0
13	2.11	0.570	7.367	23.0

Table 4.8: Deposition velocities and percent resuspension by wind speed per unit leaf area [94]

The deposition velocity of PM2.5 to the trees per unit leaf area found in table 4.8 according to the wind speed given by the meteorological data is then multiplied by the leaf area index:

$$V_d = V_{d,PM2.5} \cdot LAI \quad (4.49)$$

$$V_{d,min} = V_{d,PM2.5,min} \cdot LAI \quad (4.50) \quad V_{d,max} = V_{d,PM2.5,max} \cdot LAI \quad (4.51)$$

During non-precipitation periods, flux values of PM2.5 are cumulated on leaves hourly with a percent of the accumulated PM2.5 resuspended back to the atmosphere based on local wind speed. At time t , newly deposited PM2.5 flux $F_{PM2.5,t}$ can be calculated as for the other air pollutants with equation 4.36. Minimum and maximum flux at time t are calculated likewise by using values of $V_{d,min}$ and $V_{d,max}$ at time t .

Resuspended amount of PM2.5 to atmosphere at time t R_t can be calculated as:

$$R_t = (A_{t-1} + F_{PM2.5,t}) \cdot \frac{rr_t}{100} \quad (4.52)$$

where A_t [$g.m^{-2}.h^{-1}$] is the amount of PM2.5 accumulated on leaves at time t and rr_t is the PM2.5 resuspension rate at time t . Minimum and maximum resuspended amounts are calculated likewise with extremum values of flux and accumulated amount of PM2.5.

Newly accumulated amount of PM2.5 on leaves at time t can be calculated as (likewise for extrema accumulated amount on leaves at time t):

$$A_t = (A_{t-1} + F_{PM2.5,t}) - R_t \quad (4.53)$$

After PM2.5 is resuspended back to the atmosphere, net PM2.5 flux at time t $F_{PM2.5,net,t}$ [$g.m^{-2}.h^{-1}$] can be calculated as (likewise for extrema net flux at time t):

$$F_{PM2.5,net,t} = F_{PM2.5,t} - R_t \quad (4.54)$$

When net flux is negative due to a large amount of resuspension and the absolute value of the net flux is greater than the total PM2.5 amount in the atmosphere ($M_{total}[g.m^{-2}.h^{-1}] = C[g.m^{-3}.h^{-1}] * mixinglayerheight[m]$), the net flux is adjusted to be equal to $-M_{total}$.

During precipitation events, the accumulated PM2.5 is assumed to be washed off to the ground surface, depending upon the precipitation intercepted and stored on leaves and running off from leaves. During stage 1 of the vegetation precipitation interception model (see part 3.1.a) until full capacity of canopy storage Sv_{max} is reached, precipitation is stored on leaves and no water runs off from leaves. During this period, no PM2.5 is washed off. Once maximum capacity is reached, all the accumulated PM2.5 is assumed to be washed off with dripping water. Hence, resuspension, accumulation and net flux for these time periods (stage 2 of precipitation interception model) are set back to 0.

Transpiration flux calculation

Transpiration is the escape of water vapor from plants and is controlled by leaf resistances. The process is comprised of two stages: evaporation of water from cell walls and diffusion out of the leaf mainly through stomata [150].

Transpiration flux, T_f [$g.m^{-2}.h^{-1}$] is estimated as:

$$T_f = \frac{C_{leaf} - C_{air}}{\frac{1}{g_s} + r_a} \cdot \frac{3600}{LAI} \quad (4.55)$$

where C_{leaf} [$g.m^{-3}$] is the water vapor concentration at the evaporating surfaces within the leaf; C_{air} [$g.m^{-3}$] is the water vapor concentration in the air; g_s is the stomatal conductance (inverse of r_s [$s.m^{-1}$] stomatal resistance); r_a [$s.m^{-1}$] is the aerodynamic resistance and LAI is the leaf area index. The stomatal conductance is at canopy scale (calculated equation 4.48) and the first term is then divided by LAI to get the transpiration per leaf area unit.

C_{leaf} and C_{air} are calculated as [151]:

$$C_{leaf} = \frac{M_w e_s}{RT} = \frac{2165 e_s}{T} \quad (4.56) \quad C_{air} = \frac{M_w e}{RT} = \frac{2165 e}{T} \quad (4.57)$$

where M_w is the molecular weight of water ($=18 g.mol^{-1}$); R is the universal gas constant ($=8.314 J.mol^{-1}.K^{-1}$); e_s [kPa] the saturation vapor pressure; e [kPa] vapor pressure and T temperature in K.

The hourly transpiration flux mass per unit canopy cover T_f calculated equation 4.55 is converted to depth in $m.hr^{-1}$ by considering that 1 ton of water is equivalent to $1 m^3$ of water, thus by multiplying by 10^{-6} . T_f is then adjusted based on hourly potential evapotranspiration PET $m.hr^{-1}$ from inside of trees and from the ground described at the end of part 3.1.a . During leaf-off season as well as when T_f exceeds PET throughout the year, T_f is adjusted to:

$$T_f = \bar{R}.PET \quad (4.58)$$

where \bar{R} is the averaged ratio between T_f and PET, calculated when PET is larger than T_f during leaf-on season:

$$\bar{R} = \frac{\sum_t^n \frac{T_{ft}}{PET_t}}{n} \quad (4.59)$$

Thus, hourly transpiration flux will vary depending on temperature, precipitation (from where e and e_s are derived) and tree specie (defining stomatal conductance and leaf area index).

3.2 Processing

Before running the model, input data can be checked and the software gives a summary and guidelines to solve those errors. In this case study, errors were related to: missing minus signs in some longitudinal coordinates, wrong coordinate numbers (Figure 4.9), sum of the area of each plot higher than the study area. The latter error is due to default area value that had not been modified in the “Project & Strata area” tab.

However, coordinate data of each plot and tree cannot be verified since *i-Tree Eco* does not know about the coordinates of the defined study area and if the plot and tree coordinates entered manually are within the study area or not. Thus, it is important to export in CSV format, the inventory data of plots and trees with its coordinates. It is then possible to import the CSV file in *QGis*, *ArcGIS*, are even in the *Google Maps Engine* by creating an online *Google My Maps* file in *Google Drive*. This way, it is easy to identify problematic points that would be place outside of the study area, due to an error in coordinates due to manual data input uncertainties. In our case, 2 tree coordinates and 1 plot coordinate were very far from the study area. By comparing with the trees from the same plot and with the closest plots, it is possible to clearly identify where it should be placed.

Point	Inpitted longitude	Corrected longitude
Plot 8	-83.5829	-83.6829
Plot 23 Tree ID 2	-83.782	-83.682
Plot 49 Tree ID 1	-87.679	-83.679

Table 4.9: Corrected field-data coordinate values in Turrialba case study

One of the trees we had in plot 23 had a longitude of -87.679 whereas all longitudes of the data set begin with -83. Thus, the tree longitude has been corrected to -83.679 (see table 4.9). Common sense can easily help to solve this type of errors.

Next step is then to “Submit Data for Processing” in the “Reports” tab. An email should then be received to confirm project has been run and that the results can be downloaded in “Track & Retrieve Results”. However, at this step, error messages can also be received per email from the i-Tree team. This way, another error message appeared at first running test of the Turrialba case, meaning that one species contained in the project was no longer available in the i-Tree database, indicating that the project was created in an outdated version of *i-Tree Eco*. The specie in question is the *Tecoma stans* that had to be removed and the i-Tree version updated before resubmitting the project. Anyways, the DBH of this tree is very little and assimilable to a bush which is not the main focus of this study. However, it should be possible to encounter another specie with similar characteristics within the same genus in i-Tree database to replace it, or a new specie with its information can be submitted and integrated in the database by the technical team, with delay.

Finally, the project could be run and results retrieved. In order to interpret the results, it is important to understand how they are obtained. To this end, a brief description of resulting variables is presented below and related to the corresponding modules of the model (described in previous Part 3.1) used for calculation.

Structural attributes

Basic urban forest structural attributes on which all further tree function calculations are based, are tree population, diversity and condition. When field-surveyed plots are attributed to their corresponding *stratum*, data is summarized as a stratified random sample meaning that plot averages of trees per unit area for each stratum must be calculated to get their area weighted average: this statistical method is called “stratified sampling”. Dead trees are included in the estimates of the number of trees and plots that are not marked as 100% measured will also be accounted for. Thus, this method will give estimates of the tree population and tree cover per stratum, then generalised to the whole study area with area weighted values.

Without stratum, tree population is calculated proportionally, according to the percentage of representation of the plot inventory and to the percentage of trees and of each specie in the inventory data. Hence, considering stratum distribution of plots, composition structure changes. Leaf area of trees and subsequently leaf biomass, is assessed using measurements of crown dimensions, percentage of crown canopy missing, and species-specific data informing on leaf density such as “Percent leaf type” and “Leaf Type” which are actually genus-specific information and provide a small range of possible options (Percent leaf type is either picea, hardwood, palm or pinus and Leaf Type either evergreen, semi-evergreen or deciduous).

Air pollution removal

Pollution removal is calculated for CO , NO_2 , SO_2 , O_3 and PM2.5. Particulate matter less than 10 microns (PM10) is another significant air pollutant but given that *i-Tree Eco* analyses particulate matter less than 2.5 microns which is a subset of PM10, and that PM2.5 is generally more relevant in discussions concerning air pollution effects on human health, PM10 removal is not included in available results.

Air pollution removal estimates are derived from calculated hourly tree-canopy resistances for NO_2 , SO_2 , O_3 based on a hybrid of big-leaf and multi-layer canopy deposition models (see model description Part 3.1.b). As the removal of CO and PM2.5 by vegetation is not directly related to transpiration, removal rates (deposition velocities) for these pollutants are based on average measured values from the literature that were adjusted depending on leaf phenology and leaf area (see Part 3.1.b). Particulate removal incorporated a resuspension rate of particles back to the atmosphere according to wind speed level. There are some cases when net PM2.5 removal is negative or resuspended particles lead to increased pollution concentrations thus negative values.

Carbon Storage and Sequestration

To calculate current carbon storage, biomass for each tree (different from leaf biomass) was calculated using equations from the literature and measured tree data (species-specific density is not considered). Open-grown, maintained trees tend to have less biomass than predicted by forest-derived biomass equations [19]. This is adjusted by a 0.8 correction factor for trees located in urban areas. Stored carbon is obtained through multiplying tree dry-weight biomass by 0.5 [19].

To estimate the gross amount of carbon sequestered annually from the air by plants (carbon sequestered as a result of tree growth), average diameter growth from the appropriate tree genus, diameter class and tree condition is added to the existing tree diameter (year x when the tree was measured) to estimate tree diameter and carbon storage in year $x+1$, using same biomass models as above.

Oxygen production by trees

The amount of oxygen produced is estimated from carbon sequestration based on atomic weights: $netO_2release(kg/yr) = netCsequestration(kg/yr) * (32/12)$. To estimate the net carbon sequestration rate in kg/yr , the amount of carbon sequestered as a result of tree growth is reduced by the amount lost resulting from tree mortality. Thus, net carbon sequestration and net annual oxygen production of the urban forest take its decomposition into account [152].

Avoided runoff

Annual avoided surface runoff is calculated based on rainfall interception by vegetation, specifically the difference between annual runoff with and without vegetation. Although tree leaves, branches, and bark may intercept precipitation and thus mitigate surface runoff, only the precipitation intercepted by leaves is accounted for in this analysis (see Part 3.1.a).

Building Energy Use

If appropriate field data were collected, seasonal effects of trees on residential building energy use were calculated based on procedures described in the literature [72] using distance, direction of trees from residential structures, tree height and tree condition data, simulating wind speed and air temperature reductions. The associated value of energy consumption reduction or increase to heat or cool the building are then translated to economic values.

Structural Values

Structural value is the value of a tree based on the physical resource itself (e.g. the cost of having to replace a tree with a similar tree) calculated through valuation procedures of the Council of Tree and Landscape Appraisers [153], which uses tree species, DBH, condition, and location information [154, 155].

VOC emissions

With its biogenic emission component UFORE-B integrated into *i-Tree Eco*, volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emissions from trees can be estimated [96]. The amount of VOC emissions depends on vegetation genus, leaf biomass, air and leaf temperature, transpiration rate, LAI, photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) flux which is corrected with an hourly light correction factor based on modelling of the canopy in N layers (such as in the dry deposition model for stomatal resistance calculation). This way, estimates of the hourly emission of isoprene (C_5H_8) and monoterpene (C_{10} terpenoids) are obtained. Both hourly emission estimates are then translated yearly and for the whole urban forest.

Forecasts processing

Forecasts are possible on a timescale of maximum 100 years. They are available on urban forest composition and structure (leaf area, biomass, tree cover, average DBH growth, basal area (to estimate the space for urban planning), carbon storage and sequestration). However, this module is not available to forecast hydrology or air pollution removal effects of trees. It is used to forecast the mortality rate from weather events such as storms, hurricanes, tropical depression, tropical storms, pest outbreaks or drought and how to compensate with tree planting programmes. In this module, a scenario can be created by choosing duration of forecast, annual days of frost, annual mortality rates, tree planting project (stratum of tree planting location, DBH of planted trees, start year and duration of planting), extreme event such as pest outbreaks and weather events (event type and year). Composition, structure and benefit reports for all estimated trees of the study area are available over the forecasted years.

4. Structural results

Despite the lack of local input data, requiring a sensitivity analysis to understand how uncertain results are, a set of results on composition and structure of the urban forest, and of its carbon sequestration and storage and oxygen production are available, within a standard error, to draw conclusions. In fact, those results are only calculated based on input field-data results and on species-information from i-Tree database. Forest population and composition obtained with the stratified statistical method (see Part 3.2), is the basis of leaf area index, leaf biomass carbon storage and sequestration and oxygen production calculations.

Those results are estimations that entail an uncertainty related to the considerations and chosen level of complexity of the model from the developers which cannot be measured as well as a statistical uncertainty deriving from the used statistical method and that can be measured. The latter uncertainty is given as the standard error in the leaf area and biomass reports. It is important to look at average values combined with their standard error to see the distribution around the average value. Standard error is then taken into account in subsequent calculation using statistics-derived values. Thus, standard error obtained through leaf biomass estimation, is used in VOC emissions calculation for example. But standard errors in the model only appear on composition and structure results. However, since standard error is very important for leaf area and biomass results, it should propagate as important uncertainties on pollution removal, hydrology and VOC emission results. In addition, carbon and oxygen results are calculated using equations and measured tree data from literature, thus more empirical approximations that do not lead to quantifiable uncertainty values.

For the sake of visual clarity of the model and since standard errors do not appear in further results, they are not represented in following graphs. However, it is important to keep in mind that these errors are high meaning that the range of possible values is very wide and the uncertainty very high. For instance, leaf area index of specie *Acnistus* in stratum “Estacion de tren” is of $16.9 \text{ m}^2/\text{ha}$ and its standard error of 15.1 which corresponds to a very broad gaussian distribution. This last assertion can be extended to all values since for each species standard error is close to the average value.

First of all, general information is derived from the simulation of a little part of Turrialba urban forest. With a total of 41 trees measured on the 53 field-surveyed plots, the number of trees statistically estimated over the whole 12 hectares study area is of 340 with a tree cover of 17.1%. Most common species of trees are estimated to be *Zygia longifolia*, *Cecropia palmata* and *Acnistus* and the percentage of trees with a DBH less than 15.2cm (considered small or young) is of 33.6%. Carbon stored in the estimated tree population is of 138 tons economically representing 1034 US\$ over the whole lifecycle of the forest and carbon sequestration of 9.2 tons/year (in 2019 year of field measurements) translated into 69 US\$/year. Proportionally, oxygen production represents 23.2 tons/year. The structural value of the urban forest, is estimated to be 62,298\$ according to the Council of Tree and Landscape Appraisers.

Results are available in the different tabs of the software (“Composition and structure, Benefits and costs, Individual level results, pollution and weather” and “Pest analysis” only available for the US) and on the whole study area, per specie, per stratum or both and as individual results for each field-surveyed tree.

The first graph below presents the tree count, canopy cover, leaf area and dry weight biomass for each specie as percentages of the whole urban forest. Species are sorted from highest to smallest tree count.

Figure 4.34: Estimated composition and structure per specie of studied urban forest

The dominant in tree count species mentioned above are clearly visible on the graph. However, they are not all dominant in terms of canopy cover and of leaf area. Indeed, the percentage of representation of *Acnistus* in terms of canopy cover or in leaf area is very small compared to its tree count. This is due to the fact that most of the trees from this specie are in a small DBH class (< 15.2cm) (see Figure 4.35), representing almost half of small tree population. *Zygia longifolia* specie on the contrary has an even higher representation of the urban forest in terms of canopy cover, making it from far most dominant specie of the forest in the present year. Similarly species *Cojoba arborea* and *Mangifera indica* and *Erythrina* also have a much higher representation in canopy cover than their actual tree count meaning their DBH class

is relatively high (45.7-61 and 76.2-91.4 DBH class on Figure 4.35). In addition, it can be inferred that canopy cover and leaf area behave the same way and follow same species ranking. Dry weight biomass also follows the same tendency, however some species stand out such as *Mangifera indica* and *Erythrina* which have a higher ratio dry weight biomass/canopy cover. This can be explained by the fact that although their count is moderate to low, all trees from this species have a significant DBH.

Figure 4.35: Diameter at Breast Height (DBH) class of each specie

Looking at this set of results already allows to describe the present urban forest on carbon storage and sequestration (dry weight biomass) as well as on hydrology, air pollution removal and on shading effect (leaf area and canopy cover). However, those results only characterize the urban forest at the present time. Indeed, it can be assumed that the urban forests does not reach an equilibrium for population and distribution of each specie (general number of trees, proportion of young trees compared to ancient trees), since their population is determined by human actions planting and removing trees according to the local urban nature situation.

Furthermore, another available result in *i-Tree Eco* is the “Importance value”, which is the sum of tree count and leaf area percentages for each specie. However, this is not a relevant value since both elements in the sum are given the same weight so there is no prioritized element. By looking at this result we cannot infer whether it is important in terms of leaf area or in terms of population or both, thus species are not comparable this way. In addition, if a tree is clearly much more represented such as *Zygia longifolia* in this case, it could reveal invasive species defavouring others rather than a specie to encourage if its functions per unit leaf area are also revealed to be good.

While defining the study area, it is crucial to decide on a stratum or non-stratum data collection method. Indeed, the graphs on Figure 4.36 demonstrate the impact of this preliminary decision on the population results, then impacting the whole set of results. After simulating both cases, not considering stratum information gave an estimated tree coverage of 13.8% contra 17.1% coverage with stratum, which is more accurate according to a satellite raster analysis Part 6.

One graph presents the percent of tree population per specie for case with strata and case without strata as well as directly from the field data without estimate over the study area. The second framed graph shows the repartition of tree population for both cases over the four strata. A clear difference can be observed between both cases thus leading to different repartitions. Moreover, this difference is higher when number of measured trees on one stratum is higher than on others such as in “Rio Turrialba”, this due to the fact that heterogeneity of stratum tree population is represented with the stratified statistical estimation. The same behaviour can be observed with species distribution.

Figure 4.36: Tree population change with stratum allocation of field data

Furthermore, it is easy to observe that distribution of trees among species for estimation without stratum and for field measured trees is exactly the same. Thus number of trees calculated without stratum is directly proportional with the percentage of plot representation, which does not represent at all heterogeneity of the study area. Hence, more precision derives from the allocation of stratum information for each measured plot on the field.

Diversity of the tree population per stratum is calculated with different diversity indicators which allows to rely on different methods if one is less trusted than another, since they do not all give similar results. Richness is the number of species sampled in each stratum or city and SPP/ha is the number of species found per hectare of area sampled. Shannon-Wiener diversity index (the higher the more diverse) represents the proportion of species abundance in the population. Its being at maximum when all species occur in similar number of individuals and the lowest when the sample contains one specie. Shannon-Wiener's evenness index (the closer to 0 the less even the community is) refers to how close in numbers each species in an environment are and is comprised between 0 and 1. Simpson's index is a similarity index (the higher the value the lower in diversity). Those results are presented per stratum on Figure 4.37.

Figure 4.37: Specie's diversity indicators of tree population per stratum and native status of the tree population

For more populated strata such as Rio Colorado and Rio Turrialba, diversity is higher which are expected results in this case since the sampling number is small.

As another characteristic of the tree population diversity, the distribution of species according to their origin is also proposed and placed on the same Figure. It shows that most species are native since Costa Rica hosts species from both North and South America.

Urban forests are composed of a mix of native and exotic tree species and often have a tree diversity that is higher than surrounding native landscapes. Increased tree diversity can minimize the overall impact or destruction by a species-specific insect or disease, but it can also pose a risk to native plants if some of the exotic species are invasive plants that can potentially out-compete and displace native species.

Following graph Figure 4.38 presents carbon sequestration and storage function of trees per specie. Values have been translated per unit tree to be able to compare their performance. For the sake of visually comparing carbon storage and sequestration functions, sequestration values have been multiplied by 5.

Figure 4.38: Carbon storage and sequestration per specie in ton/year/unit dry weight biomass

For both carbon amounts, the tendency is not similar among species. This can be explained by growth rate and DBH distribution differences between species. If *Mangifera indica* and *Erythrina* sequester the most carbon per tree and on a similar rate per year, *Erythrina* stores about one third more carbon than *Mangifera indica*. This is due to the distribution of the species according to DBH class (see Figure 4.35) which is higher and narrower for *Erythrina*. Moreover, its growth rate is characterized as fast. This way, for the highest growth rate-DBH distribution combination, one tree can reach up to 2.6 tons of stored carbon and around 100 kg/year of sequestered carbon in this urban forest. *Bignonia* specie (from genus *Jacaranda* see Appendix A. has a carbon storage assimilated to zero, this can be explained by the fact that all population from this specie is very young in this urban forest. But carbon sequestration is not assimilated to zero and will add to carbon storage the following year, since this specie has a fast growth rate although it has a short longevity. However, very low represented trees in this population or with only young trees such as *Persea urbaniana* or *Roystonea regia* which have fast or moderate growth rates and long or moderate longevities do not have relevant results in this graph but underestimates on species-specific carbon potential.

Anyhow, these results per tree are more relevant to characterize the general performance of one tree specie, if there is equally young and older trees. It can be seen on DBH distribution that some trees such as *Erythrina* are all included in the same high DBH class showing that all trees from this specie are in an advanced age. Thus, once more, this results are proper to this urban forest at its current stage and cannot be generalized to species performance.

Nevertheless, some traits of certain species can be hypothesized such as the fact that higher DBH distribution class species grow old in urban areas, thus are more resistant and their consequent carbon storage and sequestration potential is higher than the average. Moreover, since carbon sequestration each year adds to carbon storage, the faster growers, reaching the highest DBH, have a good carbon storage performance. Thus *Magnifera indica*, *Erythrina*, *Cojoba arborea* have a good carbon storage and sequestration potential. For some of them, it could already be seen on composition graph Figure 4.34 where dry weight biomass stood out. For the others, it is interesting to look at present graph per tree since it highlights other species which have a lower count in this forest and are younger but still have a good carbon sequestration function.

It is also possible to get the quantity of oxygen produced per stratum and per specie. Since it is proportional with the atomic weight factor to the carbon sequestration, it is equivalent to the results on carbon sequestration.

To estimate current health of the urban forest, an indicator named Relative Performance Index (RPI) is calculated by considering the percentage of trees in each weighed state (*excellent*, *good*, *fair*, *poor*, *critical*, *dying* or *dead*). In this case all trees are either in the *excellent* or *good* state, thus their RPI is equal to one or a little lower.

Furthermore, a statistical estimation of the ground cover composition has also been calculated based on the field work observations (on the measured plots, each ground cover type was assigned a percentage by visual estimation). Ground cover composition according to different types corresponding to “grey” or “green” infrastructure elements of the city, is presented per stratum on the chart Figure 4.39. Strata have been sorted from highest to smallest plantable space represented by green dots. Plantable space includes maintained and unmaintained grass, herbs and bare soil. This way, it can be seen that the neighbourhoods including river banks (Rio Colorado and Rio Turrialba) have at the present time, a bigger site availability for planting. “Estacion de tren” neighbourhood is from far the greyest, on which an greenery need is thus identified in order to rebalance and avoid discontinuity between neighbourhoods.

However, this ground composition distribution does not include private or public spaces, that would be relevant to add, since planting actions can focus on both space status but procedures and campaigns are completely different between public and private. To this end, chart Figure 4.40 presents the distribution of trees according to their public or private status, in each neighbourhood and on the whole study area under “total”. The grey dot represents the percentage of street trees that is also available in the programme.

Figure 4.39: Ground cover composition per stratum

Most neighbourhoods are comprised mainly of public trees, where the potential on private planting opportunities could be investigated. Inversely, Rio Turrialba neighbourhood has most of its trees as private status and could analyse potential public planting options, especially on street trees which are at 0 percent.

Then, results on benefits and costs are available, as the aim of *i-Tree Eco* is to provide a cost-benefit analysis of the urban forest. Although it is not available in this case study, energy savings on building heating and cooling are calculated in terms of carbon emissions, knowing the amount of emissions per

Figure 4.40: Public, private and street trees distribution per stratum

MWh and translated in monetary value. A health impact summary related to the pollution removal benefit of trees, is also available and based on EPA Environmental Benefits Mapping and Analysis Program [156]. For each effect such as “Acute bronchitis, acute respiratory symptoms, asthma exacerbation, hospital admissions, mortality, school loss days, work loss days,etc.” the incidence (total number of adverse health effects avoided in a year due to a change in pollution concentration) and economic value associated with the incidence of adverse health effects, are estimated. Then, a table states the net annual benefits by subtracting the costs of planting trees and maintaining them as well as of damages caused by trees such as infrastructure repairs and litter clean-up. In addition, net benefits are also available per stratum.

5. Sensitivity analysis

5.1 Methodology

The lack of local meteorological and air pollution data is a challenge for this type of case studies. Indeed nothing can be concluded from uncertain alternative input data sets (data from NCDC existing in other locations than in Turrialba can be chosen) if it is not understood how the model works and reacts. For this reason, it is attempted to run a sensitivity analysis despite low accessibility to the model's parameters.

There are two types of sensitivity analysis, the linear and non-linear ones. In the linear case, the impact of one parameter on the results is analysed by modifying it linearly with distribution conservation (for example adding 2 degrees to the whole temperature data set). Since the software does not allow to access meteorological data sets, it is a non-linear model: the analysis of how entire data sets with different distributions impact the results will be performed. The aim of this study is to investigate how sensitive the model is to different input data sets and if some parameters require more accurate data (field, meteorological or air pollution data) or if a correction can be applied on the results to overcome the local data scarcity.

However, most of the outcomes of the sensitivity analysis will be qualitative and accompanied with results applicable to Turrialba case study. Also, independently from meteorological data availability, available resources allocated to field-surveying can be different from one study area to another. Thus, it is important to understand what is the minimal resources to mobilise in order to get acceptable estimations on the urban forest composition.

Field data sensitivity

“How sensitive is the model to inventory data ? What is the minimum number of plots we need to measure to get an acceptable representation ? Is it useful to measure a lot more plots and put much more effort in it ?” These are relevant upstream questions to ask before any field measurements, in order to optimise resources.

A sensitivity analysis of number of measured plots on structural results is presented in this part. This analysis is only interesting if stratified information is used, since without stratum consideration, a simple proportionality relation links field-surveyed population and estimated population. Then, the most important is to measure the right proportion of trees from each specie, so that the field data can be representative for the general tree population estimation. Thus, when plots are chosen randomly, if the tree population of the study area is homogeneous in terms of tree species and in terms of spatial distribution around the city, it is not needed to measure a number of plots that defines a high representation of the study area, a moderate representation should be enough (20 to 30% for example). However, it is hardly possible to know if the distribution is homogeneous on all these aspects upstream. Stratify the area according will allow to better estimate the distribution upstream and act accordingly. Indeed, each area stratified can be associated with one type of spatial and species distribution of trees:

homogeneous or heterogeneous. With stratum consideration, the sensitivity is analysed for both distribution types. By creating three different projects with the same field inventory data but varying areas of one spatially heterogeneous or one spatially homogeneous stratum in term of trees, changes in structural results on tree population are identified. In this analysis, tree species distribution in each stratum is not considered. The spatial distribution of trees on each stratum has been done by looking at the satellite image as well as by looking at the number of trees associated to each plot in the field input data of *i-Tree Eco*. If within one stratum, there is a high variability of tree number per plot, it defines a spatially heterogeneous plot. If the latter variability is low, it is identified as homogeneously distributed stratum. Stratum “Estacion de tren” is considered spatially homogeneous and “Puente Negro” as well as “Rio Colorado” spatially heterogeneous. If the latter variability is low, it is identified as homogeneously distributed stratum. However, since the number of plots and associated trees per stratum is low, a variability of number of trees per plots from 0 to 3 will still be considered as heterogeneous.

Three projects were created with 8 plots less in the input field data of one of these stratum respectively. Table Figure 4.10 presents these three modified projects (2, 3 and 4 on the table) compared to the basic project (1).

	Project name			
	Basic project (1)	Alternative (2)	Alternative (3)	Alternative (4)
Estacion de tren	15	6	15	15
Rio Colorado	14	14	6	14
Puente Negro	15	15	15	6
Rio Turrialba	9	9	9	9

Table 4.10: Basic project and three modified projects for field data sensitivity analysis

Meteorological data sensitivity

To perform sensitivity analysis on meteorological data, same field inventory data is processed in different project by changing the weather station (linked with general weather data including precipitation and temperature data sets), as well as the location (linked with pollution data) when sensitivity on air pollution removal results is analysed. In fact, the location of the project only has an impact on the energy savings results, thus it will be modified in order to analyse sensitivity of meteorological data on air pollution removal with Turrialba urban forest simulation.

Anyhow, since the case study is located in a tropical region which has specific weather characteristics, it is always preferred to choose available weather stations in Costa Rica (Juan Santamaria, Tobias Bolanos or Limon). When creating a project, the weather station location as well as the year can be chosen. This way, two weather stations have been chosen for each analysis to be run with Turrialba inventory data and compared. Moreover, data availability for both chosen stations should be comparable: in Costa Rica all available stations have very low hourly data availability, thus stations with 6-hourly data is chosen for all of them. In order to facilitate the search for weather stations to compare, general information about local climate

should be known upstream: Juan Santamaria and Tobias Bolanos have similar climate features and Limon has about 3 to 4°C higher temperature level and is dryer. Besides, only temperature and precipitation data can be seen in the software, thus the selection has to be made on these two data sets.

For each sensitivity analysis, chosen weather stations and methods performed with the software R are listed below:

1. **Sensitivity analysis of precipitation data on avoided runoff:** search for two weather stations in Costa Rica with similar temperature profiles and levels but with significantly different precipitations levels and distribution. **Juan Santamaria 2017** and **Juan Santamaria 2018** have been selected. By choosing two times the same weather station location but different years, the probability is higher to have similar data for weather variables used in the software (temperature, wind-speed, etc). ΔAR (difference in avoided runoff) is plotted as a function of ΔP (difference in precipitation) and interpolated into a polynomial function (with a regression model using function “lm(”).
2. **Sensitivity analysis of temperature data on avoided runoff:** Search for two weather stations in Costa Rica with similar precipitation profile and quantity but with significantly different temperature profile and level. **Tobias Bolanos 2018** and **Limon 2017** have been selected (temperature averages are respectively of 26.24 and 21.73°C). The latter pair of weather station and year have similar precipitation amounts and similar number of big rain events, however they are not similarly distributed throughout the year. To overcome the uncertainty added to the analysis due to different precipitation distribution, the difference in avoided runoff obtained will be corrected with the polynomial function from above. Then, the obtained ΔAR should be corrected from the effect of the precipitation data difference and reflects temperature sensitivity (plotted as a function of ΔT).
3. **Sensitivity analysis of precipitation and temperature data on VOC emission results (Isoprene and Monoterpene):** similar weather station pairs are used for both precipitation and temperature sensitivity.
4. **Sensitivity analysis of precipitation data on air pollution removal results (dry deposition flux for CO , NO_2 , SO_2 , O_3 and $PM_{2.5}$):** Search for two weather stations in Costa Rica with same constraints on temperature and precipitation than steps 1 and with two added constraints. The fact that for a US location, no input air pollution data exists after year 2016 and that we want to have same air pollution input data in both projects since we do not know its sensitivity, thus same chosen year. **Tobias Bolanos 2014** and **Juan Santamaria 2014** have been selected. US location Winchester in Virginia has been chosen for air pollution data availability. The process of location choice is detailed below. For each pollutant flux X , the plot of ΔX as a function of ΔP is

obtained and approximated with the same method than above: the polynomial correction is then used in step 6.

5. **Sensitivity analysis of temperature data on air pollution removal results (dry deposition flux for CO , NO_2 , SO_2 , O_3 and $PM_{2.5}$):** with same constraints than step 2 combined with step 4, **Juan Santamaria 2015** and **Limon 2015** have been selected and location Winchester is used. However, both weather stations still have significant differences in precipitation data. Thus, similarly to step 2, for each pollutant flux X , the plot of ΔX (corrected from the effect of the precipitation data difference) as a function of ΔT is obtained. Then, it is approximated: the polynomial correction is again used in step 6.
6. **Sensitivity analysis of air pollution concentration data on air pollution removal results (dry deposition flux for CO , NO_2 , SO_2 , O_3 and $PM_{2.5}$):** again with location Winchester, two different years are chosen to get two different input air pollution concentration data sets. **Tobias Bolanos 2014** and **Tobias Bolanos 2015** have been selected. With the polynomial correction functions obtained steps 4 and 5, for each air pollutant flux X , ΔX is corrected from both effects of temperature and precipitation data difference. Then, ΔX is plotted as a function of ΔC with C air pollution concentration of respective air pollutant. This plot estimates air pollutant, the sensitivity of its concentration on its removal by trees. Figure 4.41 describes the present methodology.

Figure 4.41: Sensitivity analysis of air pollution concentration data on air pollution removal results: correction process of deviation in air pollution outputs from two different air pollution input data sets

Following paragraph tells on which assumptions location Winchester, Virginia has been encountered, but these are not considered as valid anymore. Since air pollution concentration levels do not matter for sensitivity analysis, any other US city could have been chosen.

Looking for a location in the US to perform sensitivity analysis on air pollution results basically started by searching for clues to estimate Turrialba city air pollution levels. Indeed, the aim was first to find a city reflecting the most Turrialba's air pollution concentration and thus local removal effects. However, data on local air pollution is scarce to non-existent. The closest air pollution data encountered throughout the research is from Cartago, the capital city of Cartago province where Turrialba is located. A paper published by the National University of Costa Rica [157] that performed the monitoring of the contaminant concentrations gives average annual concentrations of PM10 in the centre of Cartago from 2013 to 2015. However, PM10 emissions are poorly related to PM2.5 emissions sources even though they include them [158]. Hence, when comparing two cities air pollution levels, a similar level of PM10 emissions may not induce at all a similar level of PM2.5. Moreover, if it could be assumed that PM2.5 concentration reflects traffic in a city and subsequently levels for other pollutants, this assumption does not work for PM10.

Nonetheless, similarity of traffic between Turrialba and Cartago city centres has been assumed based on other observations: Turrialba is, such as Cartago, on the second main transportation road that leads from the capital city to the Caribbean coast, thus it is assumed that the majority of non-residents traffic through Cartago (transportation for commercial purposes) passes through Turrialba. Moreover, we assume (based on experience) that in the city centre, same concentration of resident traffic occurs in both. This way, we assume that both city centers have similar main road traffic, and comparable residents traffic contributions to PM10 emissions.

Cartago PM10 annual averages have then been compared with a table of Air Quality Statistics by US cities and counties in 2018 from US EPA [159]. This table also gives the number of inhabitants for each county or city. A city with similar PM10 levels and similar number of inhabitants has been chosen: Winchester, Virginia (it population in 2018 has been verified with another reference [160]). But those criteria are not enough and ozone levels as well as Air Pollution Index (AQI) on the US application AQI Air Visual [161] have been compared. Winchester and Turrialba are in the same range when looking at the NOAA Worldwide daily ozone map [121]. The AQI and PM2.5 in $\mu g/m^3$ can be seen daily and hourly over maximum one month on AQI Air Visual. For both stations, levels and frequency of higher levels, are similar. This way, Winchester is chosen to perform air pollution analysis.

5.2 Sensitivity analysis results

5.2.a Field data sensitivity

The chart on Figure 4.42 presents the variation in tree population percentage for the basic project compared to the three modified projects with varying field-data input. The percentage variation is presented per stratum except for “Rio Turrialba” since nothing has been changed on this stratum in none of the projects. In order to compare, the number of field-surveyed trees remaining for each project after plot removal drops the most in project 3 (11 trees less) and drops very little for projects 2 and 4 (2 trees). As a reminder, project 3 and 4 simulates

Figure 4.42: Percent tree population per stratum with varying field-data input

a change on heterogeneous stratum and project 2 on homogeneous stratum.

Chart Figure 4.43 presents tree population variation per specie.

First observation is that the number of trees only varies within the stratum that has been modified for each project. This allows to isolate the stratum we are interested in and look at results for both homogeneous and heterogeneous stratum modification.

Project 2 concerns homogeneous area and the result is a very low decrease in general population, which is expected since the number of trees in input data only decreased by 2 and as homogeneity implies proportionality.

Projects 3 and 4 concern heterogeneous area and the result in tree numbers is a significant increase for project 4 (2 input data trees less and 18 more trees estimated after project running) and a significant decrease for project 3 (11 input data trees less and 31 less trees estimated after project running). Since the number of trees reacts very differently for both projects 3 and 4, it can be concluded that a set of plots randomly defined with a 20% representation of the study area (which is the chosen representation percentage for Turrialba case study) is still a very uncertain zone if the area’s urban forest is spatially heterogeneous. In terms of species distribution, it can be seen on chart Figure 4.43 that projects 3 and 4 have different distributions. Thus, the same conclusion can be inferred for an area with an heterogeneous urban forest in terms of species.

In terms of canopy coverage, it does not vary for project 2 which is the expected result (17.1% tree coverage similar to the basic model) and project 3 has 17% tree coverage whereas project 4 has 17.8% which can be explained by the significant change in species distribution (seen chart

of population change per specie Figure 4.43).

Finally, the less homogeneous it is, the more sampling is needed to get accurate results.

Figure 4.43: Percent tree population per specie with varying field-data input

5.2.b Meteorological data sensitivity

Preliminary observation valid for all steps: the methodology could not properly be applied. Indeed, plotting the difference in output as a function of the difference in input only gave point clouds with no visible tendency and no correlation at all. Thus, it has been attempted to work with cumulated variables but this only makes sense for precipitation and avoided runoff variables. Indeed pollutant concentrations, pollutant deposition fluxes and temperature are physical quantities that cannot be cumulated. Finally, only Step 1 of the methodology is kept in the showed results and is complemented with qualitative observations after plotting of datasets.

On avoided runoff

Precipitation data sensitivity

First, cumulated precipitation for both compared datasets (Juan Santamaria 2017 and Juan Santamaria 2018) have been plotted as well as temperature throughout the year. Temperature averages are respectively of 22.75 and 22.76°C, thus similar. The similar distribution can be observed on Figure 4.44. For the precipitation, difference in quantities and distribution is clearly visible.

Figure 4.44: Temperature and cumulated precipitation over one year for both compared datasets Juan Santamaria 2017 and Juan Santamaria 2018

Sensitivity analysis of precipitation data on the avoided runoff has first been attempted with Step 1 of the methodology but with cumulated quantities of ΔP and ΔAR . Figure 4.45 gives the obtained plot with its polynomial regression line and coefficients. The summary of the regression gives the p-values for each polynomial coefficient. When they are lower than 0.05 it indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected, thus the regression can be considered. To reach the most precision possible, the highest polynomial degree that does not outfit the points, will be chosen. In this case, for regression to a 5th degree gives p-values that are higher than 5%, thus degree 4 is kept (function $-8.616e - 02 + 5.184e - 04 * x + 9.711e - 05 * x^2 - 8.172e - 07 * x^3 + 2.164e - 09 * x^4$). Then, confidence intervals are used to trace lower (2.5%) and upper (97.5%) confidence limits around the fitting regression line (black lines on the graph).

Figure 4.45: ΔAR as a function of ΔP (cumulated differences) and polynomial interpolation (trend line and coefficients)

The plot shows a trend but this could be misleading since it handles cumulated values. To understand better the physical phenomenon, for one data set, non-cumulated avoided runoff was plotted as a function of precipitation (for Juan Santamaria 2017 and then verified on Juan Santamaria 2018): a point cloud appears and no correlation is visible although a saturation of avoided runoff from around 1cm/hour precipitation is visible (see left graph on Figure 4.46).

Figure 4.46: Avoided runoff (cm/hour) of case study's urban forest as a function of precipitation (cm/hour) for weather station Juan Santamaria 2017

However, some phenomena can be observed: at hours corresponding to the end of precipitation events, no matter the precipitation intensity, avoided runoff tends to zero since all water drops from the leaves to the ground (storage in leaves is full). Thus, all hours with precipitation for which avoided runoff is close or equal to zero, correspond to hours at the end of rainfall events. In addition, hours can be observed with no precipitation but non-null avoided runoff: this could be due to the fact that in stage 3 of precipitation-interception model, there is still canopy dripping even though there is no more precipitation. This way, the model still calculates a runoff for the actual scenario but no runoff for the hypothetical scenario, which gives a non-null avoided runoff value although this water should not be considered as avoided runoff. However, since it concerns very small values, it will not make a significative difference in the annual avoided runoff result.

In order to find a correlation, all those points are excluded in the right graph Figure 4.46. This way, only the begin of rainy episodes are considered. Zooming on one rain episode, confirms the above assumption (graph Figure 4.47): avoided runoff decreases exponentially as a function of time for a constant rain. This shows the saturation effect that occurs from a certain volume of rain.

Figure 4.47: Avoided runoff (cm/hour) of case study's urban forest as a function of time (hours) for one precipitation event of weather station Juan Santamaria 2017

Thus the hourly avoided runoff does not only depend on the input amount of precipitation at time t but also on amount of precipitation at time $t-1$, i.e. on precipitation distribution. Finally, plotting ΔAR as a function of ΔP is misleading and cannot bring to any correlation applicable on other datasets. Hence, the effect of precipitation on avoided runoff cannot be removed on ΔAR for Limon 2017 and Tobias Bolanos 2018 and sensitivity of temperature on avoided runoff results cannot be observed. Qualitatively, in the model, temperature could only have an impact on evaporation rate (directly reflected by avoided runoff that corresponds to the evaporated water from trees above impervious cover) and could be assumed to be higher with higher temperature level, although this effect could be negligible.

Hydrology results obtained with user-submitted precipitation data (applicable to the case study)

By the end of the project, user-submitted data we received from the IMN (National Meteorological Institute) was integrated into the next software’s update. Thus, results could be obtained with accurate hourly precipitation data of Turrialba with a total annual precipitation of 2663.8 mm for 2018. However, this new simulation is then related to 2018 temperature data of Tobias Bolanos weather station. Tobias Bolanos is very close to Turrialba in terms of temperature levels (21.73°C 2018 average versus 22.5°C in Turrialba), thus we assume that temperature difference is negligible and will not add any effect on avoided runoff results. Figure below shows the avoided runoff per tree for each specie in the specific case of the Turrialba urban forest. Avoided runoff is proportional to leaf area since leaves are considered the only water interceptors by trees. By comparing this chart with the tree population chart Part 4. we see that species that have the highest leaf are/tree count ratio are ranked the highest in terms of avoided runoff per tree. Thus, *Erythrina*, *cojoba Arborea*, *Erythrina Poeppigiana* and *Magnifera Indica* reach the highest leaf areas in this urban forest and their corresponding water interception performance is the highest.

Figure 4.48: Aoided runoff of Turrialba case study per specie and per tree

Over year 2018, table 4.11 summarize all available annual results from *i-Tree Eco*. It can be observed that evaporation and water interception are equivalent due to the fact that all intercepted water is evaporated and not dripped of with this precipitation data set.

To get annual water volumes in $m^3/year$ for each elements related to vegetation covered areas (evaporation, transpiration, water intercepted, avoided runoff, potential evapotranspiration), hourly depth values (m) are multiplied by the area covered by vegetation, which is 17.1% of

Number of trees	Leaf area (ha)	Potential Evapotranspiration (m^3/yr)	Evaporation (m^3/yr)	Transpiration (m^3/yr)	Water Intercepted (m^3/yr)	Avoided Runoff (m^3/yr)
340	9.34	13835.55	5799.47	5516.29	5799.47	1243.16

Table 4.11: Summary annual hydrology results Turrialba case study with IMN user-submitted 2018 precipitation data and Tobias Bolanos weather station

the 12 hectares study area, thus 2.052 hectares and then summed annually. Annual avoided runoff result is way smaller than intercepted water result. This can be explained by the fact that only water intercepted by canopy above impervious ground will make a difference between both scenarios in the *i-Tree Eco* model. Almost all water intercepted by trees above impervious ground would be run off if there were no trees (hypothetical scenario) and little part of it evaporated. But water intercepted by trees above pervious cover will not make a difference in the runoff quantity since all water infiltrates and a very small part evaporates from ground in the no-trees scenario. Moreover, although 70% of the study area is impervious ground, most of the urban forest canopy is over pervious ground. Hence, this explains the very low avoided runoff value compared to the water intercepted.

The annual avoided runoff has then been related to the annual water runoff value of the hypothetical scenario without trees considered in the precipitation-interception model. Non available in the software, this data has been sent directly by the *i-Tree* team. Calculation Appendix F. gives the following result: avoided runoff due to trees represents 1.7% of the hypothetical scenario without trees. However, this hypothetical scenario does not use the actual pervious/impervious landcover estimated in the case study, but the US standards.

From the contextual analysis Part 1.2 , we have the average water runoff of Turrialba which is 1792mm/year. Knowing the avoided runoff value by trees in Turrialba year 2018 from *i-Tree Eco* (60.5 mm/year), the hypothetical scenario without trees could be estimated to have around $1792 + 60.5 = 1852.5mm/year$ runoff. This way, the avoided water runoff by the 12ha study area's urban forest would represent 3.26% of hypothetical scenario water runoff, which is higher and probably more realistic than with the calculation based on US standards.

On VOC emissions

Precipitation data sensitivity

In order to understand if there is a correlation between monoterpene or isoprene emissions and precipitation, emissions were plotted as a function of precipitation for one input dataset and then verified with the other dataset (Limon 2017 and Tobias Bolanos 2018).

Only point clouds are observed for both components as a function of precipitation. Hence, we conclude that there is no visible link between both physical quantities and that plotting $\Delta MONO$ or ΔISO (difference in monoterpene emissions between both years) as a function of ΔP would not give any result.

Temperature data sensitivity

However, as a function of temperature and for both datasets, a limiting curve can be seen for isoprene emission and a real correlation for monoterpene emissions.

Figure 4.49: Monoterpene and isoprene emissions as a function of temperature for year 2017 with Tobias Bolanos input datasets

This way, the (non-cumulated) differences of monoterpene and isoprene emissions can be plotted as a function of temperature difference between both input datasets. It increases linearly: the higher deviation in temperature is, the bigger the difference in monoterpene emissions will be. Obtained plot of $\Delta MONO$ Figure 4.50 can then be interpolated with polynomial regression. The resulting polynomial function is: $-0.036001 + 0.261527 * x$. On the second curve of ΔISO a line following the limit values for each ΔTPE can be plotted ($-12 + 2.8 * x$ as there is an offset on the y-axis).

Figure 4.50: Monoterpene and isoprene emission differences as a function of temperature difference between Limon 2017 and Tobias Bolanos 2018

VOC emission results applicable to the case study

With the user-submitted precipitation data and Tobias Bolanos 2018 weather station, which temperature level and profile is very close to Turrialba, monoterpene and isoprene variations due to temperature are negligible. This way, we can analyse the emission of volatile organic compounds per specie and per leaf area.

Figure 4.51: Monoterpene and isoprene emissions per specie and per unit leaf area (m^2) applicable to Turrialba case study

Those results are genus-specific and in Turrialba urban forest, species that stand out in terms of VOC emissions per leaf area are *Psidium guajava*, *Veitchia*, *Cocos nucifera*, *Psidium friedrichsthalianum* and *Roystonea regia*. However, highest emitters emit mainly isoprene and the monoprene emissions are much lower among all species except for specie *Magnifera indica* and *Persea americana* only emitting monoterpene.

On air pollution removal

In order to identify the significance of plotting ΔX (air pollutant deposition flux) as a function of ΔP or ΔTPE or ΔC (input air pollutant concentration), first X has been plot as a function of P, TPE and C for each air pollutant for year 2014 with Winchester location and Tobias Bolanos weather station. Figure 4.52 presents some of the outputs.

Figure 4.52: Plots of air pollutant deposition fluxes as a function of either temperature, precipitation or pollutant concentration

It is clear that deposition flux of air pollutants CO , NO_2 , SO_2 and O_3 is equal to zero when there is precipitation. Thus there is only deposition when there is no precipitation. It is also valid with $PM_{2.5}$ with the difference that there are negative values due to resuspension of particles in the atmosphere (see top left graph of Figure 4.52). With temperature (bottom left graph), for each pollutant but CO , a limiting line can be observed. All null points for pollutant flux correspond to hours where it rains thus no dry deposition occurs. Moreover, highest fluxes are from 25 to 28 degrees. It is probably linked to the fact that highest air pollution concentrations happen during the day since emission sources such as vehicle traffic are active at that time. In addition, with Costa Rican weather stations, temperatures are in this range during the day. It is important to remind that used air pollution input data is from Winchester (Virginia, US) whereas the weather station is in Costa Rica. Hence, there is no physical relation between air pollution concentrations and temperature in this simulation. Air pollution concentrations are linked with local climate in Winchester: it can be observed little differences in concentrations between winter and summer. In fact, there is in-leaf and out-of-leaf periods in Winchester which are taken into account in the calculations of air pollution deposition fluxes. It can especially be observed with CO flux since in the dry deposition model, its canopy resistance calculation is constant in each leaf season and doubles in out-of-leaf season (upper right graph with one curve corresponding to end of precipitation events ($y=0$ curve), one corresponding to out-of-leaf season (low values curve with near-null slope) and one corresponding to leaf-on season (curve

with highest slope)). However there is very few deciduous trees in Turrialba urban forest, thus it should not have a significant impact. But looking at the CO flux according to time over the year shows that there is indeed an out-of-leaf season considered that, no matter the tree species, sets the deposition values to almost zero (see graph of CO flux Appendix G.). With air pollutant concentrations, air pollutant deposition fluxes increase linearly, however a lot of noise is observable. A correlation can be observed if values close to the x-axis are discarded since they relate to precipitation events when no deposition occurs. Pollutant deposition fluxes were also plotted as a function of the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) hourly data set exported from *i-Tree Eco*. This data is used in stomatal resistance calculation but graphs did not show any correlation.

Then, between each weather station pair for each sensitivity analysis (temperature, precipitation or concentration), ΔX is plotted as a function of the input difference. However, it did not give any result: only point clouds. Maybe, removing all “noise” values such as all rain event hours and separating them between in-leaf and out-of-leaf season would show correlations.

Figure 4.53: Monthly PM2.5 and NO2 removal for two different weather stations with distinct precipitation profiles

Finally, qualitative observations result from this analysis and no quantitative conclusions can be applied to Turrialba case study without any local air pollution input data. Several are listed below:

- Since deposition flux is calculated by multiplying deposition velocity of each pollutant

by the leaf area index, deposition flux is directly proportional to leaf area of the urban forest, thus the bigger it is, the most pollutant removal occurs.

- Obviously there is no observable air pollutant flux saturation, but it would be interesting to see if there is an air pollutant removal saturation from trees. Indeed, it would be relevant to understand if the urban forest can still impact air pollution concentrations when the city is reaching peak concentrations, or if there is a maximum removal potential.
- The more precipitation events there is, the less deposition occurs. This is true for each pollutant but PM_{2.5} hourly deposition flux is not enough to quantify the level of PM_{2.5} removal because of the particle resuspension process. Thus, monthly removal summaries available in *i-Tree Eco* are relevant. Since precipitation events wash out particles from the leaves, it avoids resuspension in the atmosphere and increase the removal. This way, precipitation event frequency and intensity defines the efficiency of particle removal of an urban forest. It is clear on figure 4.53 where monthly results for Tobias Bolanos and Juan Santamaria 2014 are compared. In fact both weather stations have similar average temperatures and same air pollutant concentrations but frequency and intensity of rain events is higher in Juan Santamaria. The latter weather station systematically mostly has a greater removal. The second month, resuspension process can be observed coinciding with the dry period. In comparison, the NO₂ removal is also presented monthly and it is inverted: the removal is systematically greater for Tobias Bolanos where it rains less and less intensely. This is the case for CO, O₃ and SO₂ since deposition that is only happening during dry periods, exclusively determines the removal.

6. Complementary analysis on GIS-based softwares

6.1 Geographical visualisation

i-Tree Eco allows to get a Map-Active report of the individual results (for each georeferenced field-surveyed tree) by displaying points on an OpenStreet map. However, it is not possible to display values of chosen attribute simultaneously for all trees.

However, visualisation on GIS-based softwares such as *QGIS* or *ArcGIS* is relevant. Indeed, it is simple to export *i-Tree Eco* individual results with coordinates in CSV format which can be added as a “delimited text layer” in *QGIS* on top of a satellite image. Then, a label or histogram can be created with values of the attribute we want to display. Comparing both Figures 4.54 and 4.55 allows to identify individual services (level of air pollution removal for each pollutant, carbon sequestration, oxygen production, shading with canopy cover and leaf area) and individual disservices (VOC emissions (Isoprene and Monoterpene together)) of each tree measured on the field (identified by its specie type and its location). On Figure 4.55 histograms were automatically shifted up or down of their position indicator (red dot) according to the available space on the map. Therefore, not too many trees can be visualized simultaneously.

Figure 4.54: Mapping of individual tree species on satellite image

Figure 4.55: Mapping of individual tree attributes on satellite image

6.2 ArcGIS landcover classification method

With *ArcGIS* landcover classification analysis on satellite images of the case study area has been performed using following steps and tools:

1. Export of a satellite image of the case study area from *Google Earth* with highest quality available (4800x2833);
2. Georeferencing of the exported map of Turrialba on *ArcGIS*;
3. Addition of shapefile layer of the study area definition;
4. Addition of another layer and creation of at least 200 polygons of approximately 4 pixels representing all possible pixel combinations of tree canopy coverage on the satellite images (with study area delimitation) (see Figure 4.56);
5. On the table of attributes of the polygons layer, a value is assigned for all elements: number 1 is assigned for all polygons since we only want to investigate trees. However, to perform the classification analysis, the whole area needs to be classified and at least 2 classes need to be defined. This way, same is undertaken for “non-tree” class assigned to number 2 with polygons representing streets, buildings, bare soil and cement surfaces;
6. Use of function *Create Signature* to create a GSG format file of classes;
7. Use of tool *Maximum Likelihood Classification*: the classified raster appears on the map with a color code.
8. Use of function *Raster to Polygon* and *Calculate Geometry* to get area information of each class: it transforms raster layer in a shapefile with polygons according to each class color code (see Appendix H.).

Figure 4.56: Creation of 4 pixel polygons of tree canopy cover on satellite image, to perform raster classification with *ArcGIS*

This analysis has been performed on one satellite image focused on the 12 hectares study area and on another one focused on the whole city of Turrialba. Thus, the second satellite image has a lower resolution than the first one and this impacts the quality of the landcover classification method. Obtained raster images are presented Figure 4.57. The quality of the lower classification is clearly poorer, as more surface is classified as *Tree cover*.

Figure 4.57: Rasters of Turrialba case study area derived from *ArcGIS* landcover classification method: upper one based on a satellite image with higher resolution than the other one. Color code: Green represents *Tree cover* and Light green *Non-Tree cover*

Figure 4.58: Raster of whole Turrialba city derived from *ArcGIS* landcover classification method. Color code: Green represents *Tree cover* and Light green *Non-Tree cover*

However, applied to the area of whole Turrialba city, although the quality does not allow to get representative canopy cover distribution percentage, the classification method can be used for stratum definition and extrapolation of outputs. In fact, spatial distribution types of different areas can be identified (on the scale from homogeneous to heterogeneous) which will then enable to divide the study area in order to improve field-measurements strategy (see Part 4. Figure 4.36) and simulation. Furthermore, by bringing together an area that has been simulated on *i-Tree Eco* with another area showing similar spatial distribution, outputs and management decisions could be extrapolated to non-analysed areas.

Furthermore, a correction factor has been calculated considering the tree cover percentage for both resolutions of the classification method (see Table 4.12 below). This factor can be used to correct coverage obtained on bigger areas. This way, tree coverage obtained on whole Turrialba city, 50.1%, drops to 32.6% which should be closer to reality. In addition, the 20.25% tree coverage of the case study area obtained with the higher resolution satellite image allows to verify the consistency of the 17.1% tree coverage obtained with *i-Tree Eco* stratified statistical estimation and the inconsistency of the 13.8% tree coverage obtained without stratum consideration.

Satellite image quality	Class “Trees” (m ²)	Class “Non-Trees” (m ²)	Tree cover
Higher resolution	24165.63	95162.07	20.25%
Lower resolution	37198.34	82132.29	31.17%
Deviation	35%	Correction factor	65%

Table 4.12: Tree cover percentages derived from *ArcGIS* landcover classification method and correction factor

6.3 *i-Tree Canopy*

i-Tree Suite also proposes *i-Tree Canopy* which is a simple imagery based online tool [162]. On the area of study inputted in the tool with a shapefile, it allows to distribute randomly a desired number of points and to assign them to a class previously defined. Then, a landcover summary is outputted according to the defined classes. However, *ArcGIS* classification method is more accurate and far less time-consuming. Indeed, at least 1000 points are recommended with *i-Tree Canopy* to get a minimum accuracy.

Nevertheless, the tool also allows to perform a historical comparative analysis with Google Earth historical satellite images function. 1000 points on the satellite map are assigned to different classes (Tree cover, grass/shrub cover, bare soil, impervious road or impervious building) on *i-Tree canopy* tool. Then, all points assigned to their coordinates are exported in a KMZ file which is opened in Google Earth on a historical map (Turrialba, 2001). Each point is then compared with the current map and allocated to an other class if a difference in landcover is identified on the historical map (see the process on Figure 4.59).

Figure 4.59: Historical landcover analysis by comparing random *i-Tree Canopy* distributed points with Google Earth historical map

This way, it is interesting to observe the evolution of landcover from 2001 until now. The 1000 points for each year are displayed with a different color per class on a satellite map with *ArcGIS*. This way, it is easy to observe that in 20 years, although impervious surfaces increased, tree cover doubled. All shrub cover from 2001 became tree cover in 2020 and previous bare soil was mostly replaced by tree cover on the right side and mostly replaced by buildings on the left side.

Figure 4.60: Historical analysis of the study area in Turrialba with *i-Tree Canopy*, Google Earth and displayed on *ArcGIS*

Furthermore, this analysis could not be performed with *ArcGIS* classification method applied on the historical map, since the old imagery has a very poor quality that cannot be significantly analysed by a computer, only by the eyes.

Chapter 5: Discussion

1. *i-Tree Eco* tool assessment

i-Tree Eco describes a specific urban forest at its specific state at year of field-inventory. A common question asked is, “How does this city compare to other cities?” Although comparison among cities should be made with caution as there are many attributes of a city that affect urban forest structure and functions, Turrialba’s structural results allow to rank it among other cities in the US and Canada analyzed with *i-Tree Eco*. Looking closer at another city with similar forest structure attributes could permit to exchange experience and get inspired by successful actions that have been undertaken to improve the urban forest. In this respect, a knowledge community already exists in the US called ISA (International Society of Arboriculture) but it is very US oriented. A similar community among tropical cities could be very helpful to support urban forest planning decisions in these type of cities. Moreover, ISA mainly gathers arboricultural researchers and does not favour enough the dialogue with practitioners that needs to occur, so that, for instance, a shared database of recommended trees for different types of urban sites can be created [5].

Table appendix I. presents other cases treated with *i-Tree Eco*. Looking at these cases also allows to see which objectives are achievable such as the highest urban forest concentrations already achieved in other cities (e.g. 294.5 trees per hectare in Morgantown, WV). With 28.33 trees and 11.5 tons carbon stored per hectares, Turrialba is ranked at the bottom of the list (in-between Phoenix, AZ and Casper, WY in terms of number of trees and Oakville, ON and Chicago, IL in terms of carbon storage). However, in terms of carbon sequestration, it is situated in the upper middle with 0.77 tons per hectare per year such as in Syracuse, NY. This is due to the fact that plants grow faster in tropical climates, which gives an advantage to Turrialba. Nevertheless, those cities are much bigger with a higher density and it would be more relevant to compare Turrialba with cities of same scale and similar climate (at least cities with mainly evergreen species).

Although it is not yet adapted for Turrialba case study, if more tropical cities assess their urban forest, *i-Tree Eco* could become the support to create a knowledge and experience exchange platform among tropical cities.

On the technical aspect, the software presents a set of strengths and weaknesses identified through the case study and literature.

1.0.a Strengths

- Being management oriented and especially addressed to urban planners and municipalities, *i-Tree Eco* provides a list of urban forest management strategies to help improve air quality [163] (see Table 5.1 below).

Strategy	Result
Increase the number of healthy trees	Increase pollution removal
Sustain existing tree cover	Maintain pollution removal levels
Maximize use of low VOC-emitting trees	Reduces ozone and carbon monoxide formation
Sustain large, healthy trees	Large trees have greatest per-tree effects
Use long-lived trees	Reduce long-term pollutant emissions from planting and removal
Use low maintenance trees	Reduce pollutants emissions from maintenance activities
Reduce fossil fuel use in maintaining vegetation	Reduce pollutant emissions
Plant trees in energy conserving locations	Reduce pollutant emissions from power plants
Plant trees to shade parked cars	Reduce vehicular VOC emissions
Supply ample water to vegetation	Enhance pollution removal and temperature reduction
Plant trees in polluted or heavily populated areas	Maximizes tree air quality benefits
Avoid pollutant-sensitive species	Improve tree health
Utilize evergreen trees for particulate matter	Year-round removal of particles

Table 5.1: *i-Tree Eco* urban forest management strategies

This way, *i-Tree Eco* provides crucial elements to take into account in the decision making: both services and disservices need to be considered to ensure real benefits in terms of air quality improvement.

Another management oriented result derived from *i-Tree Eco* is the public/private status estimation of the urban forest. Indeed, it is relevant in order to observe whether actions should be undertaken by public or private actors and consequently adapt the planning focus. Similarly, results per stratum are relevant to communicate the discrepancies from one district to another and the need to reprioritize trees on the district level in the urban planning strategy.

- Some of the key variables to assess ecosystem functions are leaf area and leaf biomass. These attributes are estimated through equations using species type, crown measures and tree condition. Several methods can be used to estimate leaf area (e.g., light imaging devices) but in comparing various methods, the regression equations used in UFORE i.e. *i-Tree* model were among the best for leaf area estimation [164]. Moreover, in many cases, urban forest inventories are unsuitable to derive all required parameters creating the need of good default model parameterization, which is good enough in *i-Tree Eco* to estimate forest structure.

- Since i-Tree model provides good structural estimates, structural data can be monitored to assess urban forest change and help design long-term management plans. Moreover, *i-Tree Eco* forecast function is relevant to estimate urban forest population within different scenarios.
- As the model does not require specific technical data such as soil data for hydrology simulation, it allows to get access to hydrology results with scarce resources.
- *i-Tree Eco* dry deposition model results in relatively good estimates. Indeed, hourly pollution removal results are within the range of dry deposition velocities measured on the field [132].

1.0.b Weaknesses

Structural, biomass and biogenic emission model:

- Although carbon values produced by the model fall within the range of other forest carbon field studies [61], urban trees differ from forest tree growth and more specific tree growth modelling would improve carbon storage and sequestration estimates for urban trees. Although allometric equations have been adjusted for urban conditions, they may not accurately reflect urban wood quantity and density. Studies showed trees in the city center to be more responsive than those in urban boundaries [165, 166]. In this respect, modelling urban tree growth requires consideration of direct sensitivity to urban factors such as temperature and competition. Also, tree decay is not accounted for in the carbon estimates, which may lead to an overestimate of carbon storage [118].
Furthermore, there are currently limited biomass equations for palm trees or tropical trees in *i-Tree Eco*. Hence, the model needs to be updated with tropical tree biomass equations for more accurate estimates in tropical cities.
- Species characterization data is important as it defines basic parameters used for calculating all ecosystem services and disservices (e.g. leaf area, leaf biomass, allometric equations, BVOCs emission rates). When species information is not available, *i-Tree Eco* uses values that are defined by the genus, family, or tree type (evergreen/deciduous). This may be especially problematic if the model is applied to regions other than the US for which the parameters were designed. In addition, leaf area index calculation (one-sided leaf area per unit ground area) leaves significant uncertainty since it should be species-specific and not only sensible to genus family.

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- Limitations on calculation of VOC emissions from trees: Dunn-Johnston et al. (2016) [167] showed that, for subtropical species, a big difference exists between species-specific isoprene emission rates and those assumed in *i-Tree Eco* which are genus-specific. This assertion might also be valid for tropical trees. Additionally, the potential effects of increased air pollution or drought [168] (ozone and particulate matter formation), which might increase or decrease emissions, have been neglected.

Precipitation-interception model:

- Infiltration capacity is considered as infinite (water content is not tracked) whereas it is limited in reality and water dynamics according to soil types are not considered (only differentiation between pervious/impervious cover). Neither infiltration excess overland flow nor saturation overland flow are considered, whereas it is done in *i-Tree Hydro* (see Appendix K.). Without considering a maximum infiltration capacity, it is assumed that no water runoff comes from permeable cover. Thus, only tree canopy over impervious cover does contribute to avoid water runoff. In the end, *i-Tree Eco* model considers trees growing above pervious areas as useless in regards to hydrology.

This raises following question: “is it good enough to have an infinite infiltration rate in this model in respect to the precipitation data sets we have in the study case or is water runoff systematically underestimated?”

To verify this with Turrialba case study, the difference between hourly precipitation (local user-submitted precipitation from 2018) and hourly evaporation from leaves has been plotted. Obtained hourly values represent the amount of water per hour that would infiltrate on a pervious surface. Appendix J. presents the obtained graph combining data for both scenarios (hypothetical and actual): maximum amount reached is 60 mm/hr for one specifically strong rain event, 38 mm/hr for two other events but else amounts are lower than 25 mm/hr. Those amounts were compared with maximum and average infiltration capacities found in literature: according to Gregory et al. (2006) [169] and assuming that Turrialba was developed historically on pasture sites, the impact of urban development brings to a compacted soil with an average infiltration rate of 23 mm/hr which is a little lower than Turrialba average (30mm/hr) but in the same range. Knowing that Turrialba has silt and clayey silt soils, maximum infiltration capacities for “dry loam soils with little or no vegetation” (76.2 mm/hr) and for “moist loam soils with little or no vegetation” (25 mm/hr) given by Akan (1993) [170] could reflect soil type in Turrialba urban area. If we consider the lowest value of 25 mm/hr, and by discarding the three strong rain events, modelled infiltration quantities for Turrialba are acceptable. However, it is not reasonable for rain events overcoming 25 mm/hr. Furthermore, many parameters impact infiltration: precipitation, soil moisture, organic materials in soil (in particular vegetation roots reducing surface compaction and creating fissures) varying with depth, surface material (litter, crust, etc.), slopes (higher slope leads to lower infiltration). The

latter parameter implies very different non-linear results on infiltration according to slope gradient and to soil type: for clay loam, Ribolzi et al. (2011) [171] shows that permeability is greater for 75% slopes (21 mm/hr average infiltration rate) than for 30% slopes (6 mm/hr average infiltration rate) due to micro-relief. It also depends on the time: as the soil is unsaturated at the start of a rain event, infiltration rate is high but then slows down as the soil becomes more saturated. This way, if rainfall's rate is faster than infiltration rate, runoff will occur (called *saturation overland flow* in *i-Tree Hydro*). During a storm, infiltration capacity decreases rapidly and tends to a constant value after a couple of hours [172]. Since none of these parameters are taken into account in the model and since variability of infiltration rates is high depending on conditions, the uncertainty on infiltration is high. Over a certain amount of precipitation that reaches the limit of urban soil infiltration potential, the model cannot be trusted anymore.

- The model is not adapted to extreme events: during intense rain events, depression storage capacities should vary and store more water but they are constant in the model. Moreover, the model does not consider runoff water flows neither topography but solely runoff depth that is reset at the end of every precipitation event. This way, it does not reflect the accumulation and trapping phenomena happening when big rain events lead to floods. Moreover, if there was a resistance to infiltration in the model, during intense rainfalls, water could runoff as well from pervious ground and rain intercepted by trees over pervious ground could avoid this runoff. The current model underestimates avoided water runoff during extreme rain events and does not account for any difference of benefits of trees during peak events.
- One ecosystem service from trees that is not considered in the model is the uptake capacity by the roots and transpiration that reduces water in pervious soils where trees are planted, thus can increase infiltration capacity and avoided runoff. But soil moisture is not tracked and potential evapotranspiration which is calculated in the surface and upper air weather pre-processor is not used in any further calculation.
- To calculate water runoff volumes, actual pervious/impervious land cover that has been estimated from field data and statistically estimated over the whole area, is not used in the model. Instead, US average is used from Nowak et al. (2012) [173] (25.5% impervious and 74.5% pervious cover versus 64.8% impervious cover and 35.2% pervious cover found in Turrialba from the groundcover estimations). Those percentages are just used to get annual values and is inconsistent with the information whether one tree is above pervious or impervious ground (used to calculate hourly water runoff in depth) which is still derived from the local field data.

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- Avoided runoff results given in *i-Tree Eco* are relative to the total water runoff of the hypothetical area without trees. But the latter is not directly available in the programme's interface, thus this result can hardly be quantitatively interpreted.
 - The specific leaf water storage S_L used in the model should be species-specific, although it is constant in the model. To know how it impacts the accuracy of the model, a sensitivity analysis should be performed on this parameter by computing manually described equations and see how uncertainty propagates in the model.
 - Vegetation interception is underestimated since stem, branch and trunk interception is not taken into account. While in *i-Tree Hydro*, for deciduous trees, the LAI calculation is complexified by including a stem and trunk area index called Bark Area Index (BAI). It is considered that stem and trunk intercept precipitation even during leaf-off season, which improves the hydrologic model if deciduous trees are present in the case study. This way, BAI is used to represent average interception storage capacity of tree stem bark and is assumed constant for all seasons of one growing year (see *i-Tree Hydro* details Appendix K.)

Dry-deposition model:

- *i-Tree* dry-deposition model has a higher degree of detail (more detailed canopy modelling) than the precipitation-interception model and entails the only calculation considering soil: canopy resistance calculation. However, it still does not consider different soil types (soil resistance is attributed to a constant value changing according to growing season status).
- Soil water content is not considered to simulate the canopy stomatal resistance. This way, plants are assumed to transpire as if they were **always fully in water**. However, stomatal uptake could be influenced by drought stress, which *i-Tree Eco* model does not take into account, assuming sufficient water availability or irrigation for urban trees.
- Air pollution removal calculations are not species-specific but just depend on leaf area although each specie has a different leaf texture and roughness, thus a different performance on air pollution deposition. Barks and stems are not considered to also be deposition surfaces although this is relevant, especially for particles.
Moreover, deposition velocity of PM2.5 is calculated based on the average of values found in the literature for 17 different tree species. However, chosen species are very representative of an average forest in the US but not representative of a tropical forest.
For CO, deposition flux hourly graph over a year Appendix G. shows that even by modelling an urban forest composed of mostly evergreen trees such as Turrialba, all trees are considered to loose their leaves during out-of-leaf season (by assigning a very high canopy resistance to CO dry deposition velocity).

For NO_2 and SO_2 , it is also possible that pollution removal occurs through dissolving directly into the water on the plant surface [174]. Although it might have a minor impact compared to stomata influence on pollutant uptake, leaf-surface properties and the dependency on precipitation are underexplored in *i-Tree Eco*.

In addition, air turbulence within and around trees varying according to crown structure, urban infrastructure, weather conditions and tree position affects pollutant deposition (e.g. low turbulence may promote deposition and increase concentrations or O_3 formation) but local effects are not considered using *i-Tree Eco*.

1.0.c General outcome

The advantage of *i-Tree Eco* compared to other existing softwares modelling trees in urban environments is to give a general overview of (marketed) ecosystem services delivered by trees in cities as well as an important disservice which is VOC emissions. Indeed there are no software nowadays combining structural simulation as well as hydrology and air pollution removal. Although accuracy is lacking, this software's feature is very relevant as it raises awareness about the multiple tasks realised by trees and benefiting urban areas. Moreover, the software is good at monitoring composition and structure of a specific urban forest where statistics are needed for decision-making. In addition, *i-Tree* suite is publicly available, requires moderate resources and provides training and efficient communication with the technical team.

However, *i-Tree Eco* precipitation-interception model is a simplified version of *i-Tree Hydro* model (UFORE) (see *i-Tree Hydro* details Appendix K.): it does neither reflect soil transpiration through vegetation, nor tree stem and bark interception, nor soil resistances and water table depths limiting infiltration, nor land topography and directions of waterflows. Thus, this model relies on a lot of uncertainties which are all related to each other and propagate uncertainty. This way, it uses a simple water balance which is scientifically not reliable and systematically underestimates avoided runoff from a certain amount of precipitation. In that respect, the question “is the model good enough for the purpose?” should be raised before using *i-Tree Eco*. If the purpose is to give some framework to include tree ecosystem services (hydrology benefits among others) in a decision making process without hydrology experts, it may be enough. But if the purpose is to get accurate results of tree benefits on hydrology, it is not enough. Then using *i-Tree Hydro* is a better option, however it does not provide readily available avoided runoff results. Those can be calculated by manually creating a hypothetical scenario with same landcover but without tree coverage. Thereupon, *i-Tree Hydro* is also criticized as “too highly parameterized for management application or overly simplistic and lacking in physical management implications” [28] thus it may be amongst different needs but not really adapted for one specific purpose: this highlights the general challenge for software design to either adapt to one purpose and user or to be adaptable to several purposes and users.

Moreover, if the purpose is to show how trees can increase resilience of cities facing climate change, *i-Tree Eco* may not be enough. The software cannot measure benefits of trees under extreme events such as drought and rain peaks, whereas *i-Tree Hydro* is adapted to measure effects under peak rain discharges. Indeed, the latter can simulate storms by designing rain events. One interesting result was obtained with a project performed by UFORE team located in Maryland [28]: the lowest percentage of water interception by trees was obtained with highest intensity storm event simulation, showing that benefits of trees on hydrology are not significant during peak precipitation events and that storm management has to focus on other solutions than tree planting to increase urban resilience to storms.

Reciprocally, *i-Tree Eco* does not reflect the resilience of trees in the urban environment since their growth can be very different and more sensitive to many local parameters, than forest trees. While in *i-Tree Hydro*, there is ways to simulate this sensitivity by allowing to change parameters reflecting the conditions such as: potential evaporation rate for free water in tree canopies reflecting the change in meteorological conditions due to urban heat-island effects, climate change; or surface hydraulic conductivity representing the benefit tree growth has on reducing soil compaction (see *i-Tree Hydro* details Appendix K.).

For more informative purposes such as proving the need of trees within a city, an analysis on *i-Tree Hydro* could complement *i-Tree Eco*. Such, a particularly interesting output of *i-Tree Hydro* would be to show how increase of impervious cover in an urban area due to urbanisation increases the water runoff and how canopy cover can moderate this impact. This would support the assertion that urbanization should go along with city greening as a compensation. In addition, *i-Tree Hydro* outputs water quality results which are relevant to show how increased canopy and consequent decrease in water runoff decreases runoff pollutant loading and can help meeting clean water regulations.

Finally, *i-Tree Eco* together with *i-Tree Hydro* have one general limitation: it does not capture spatial heterogeneity of vegetation or built infrastructure and so limits our understanding of how variation in both landcover types influences the movement of materials, energy, organisms and water throughout a city. For this purpose, complementary analysis of the urban forest based on GIS is relevant: recommendations are given thereupon in next section.

2. Recommendations

2.1 *i-Tree* based recommendations

- While defining the study area that will be simulated in *i-Tree Eco*, it is crucial to decide on a *stratum data collection* method. Indeed, Figure 4.36 Part 5.2.a demonstrates the impact of this preliminary decision on the population results, then impacting the whole set of results. Thus it is recommendable to separate the study area in different districts that are either judged homogeneous or heterogeneous in terms spatial urban forest distribution and tree species. Then, a random plot definition should be performed separately in each sub-area with a different representation percentage according to the distribution type requiring more or less plots to optimize the balance of accuracy versus field resources. Indeed it is useless to measure too many plots on an homogeneous area that does not require as much as on heterogeneous areas for an acceptable accuracy. For an heterogeneous stratum up to 50% representation is recommended whereas a lower representation is acceptable for an homogeneous stratum.

Recommendations on how to use i-Tree Eco outside the US in location with scarce data availability:

- In *i-Tree Eco*, hydrology results are very sensitive to precipitation, whereas it cannot be concluded on their sensitivity to temperature. When local hourly precipitation data is available for user-submission in *i-Tree*, it can replace precipitation data of a geographically close weather station with similar temperature average and profile than the study area. This way, hydrology effects of the studied urban forest can be simulated with acceptable uncertainty related to meteorological data. However, imperfections in modelling considerations listed above add significant uncertainty.
- To estimate VOC emissions without adequate available weather station, a weather station with at least similar temperature average and distribution should be chosen. In fact no sensitivity to precipitation has been found but a great sensitivity to temperature.
- Without local air pollution concentrations, it is not possible to derive relevant results for air pollution removal over one year. However, if average air pollution data is available for the location and if it is possible to prove the similarity with a US city in terms of air pollution concentration (and same leaf season characteristics); if local precipitation data has been user-submitted in a weather station that has similar PAR (photosynthetically active radiation) levels, acceptable estimations of pollutant removal from local urban forest could be obtained.

2.2 Recommendations on valuation methods and decision-making

2.2.a Multi-criteria methods

Developing tree planting strategies in cities requires considering ecosystem services which are essential to human activities, too often taken for granted and neglected in economic development. Any sustainability-oriented decision must consider the direct and indirect role of ecosystem services. For this, the effects of greening decisions on ecosystem services must be evaluated according to several criteria.

These criteria must be evaluated to determine the best strategy and solutions depending on the ecosystem services that we want to value. In the city center, for example, regulation of heat islands can be a main objective of urban trees, whereas, in a large peri-urban park, biodiversity support may be the priority.

Different methods are relevant to accounting for the role of nature. They have been developed by ecologists such as *emergy*, *exergy* or *footprint analysis*, or by ecological economists for monetary valuation such as conventional life cycle assessment [54]. Each of them has its strengths and its weaknesses but none is really able to consider the full diversity of ecosystem services. Economic approaches make it possible to quantify the value of cultural services and indirect methods based on willingness-to-pay or willingness-to-accept are used to quantify the value of ecosystem services which are not in the market. But these methods are anthropocentric in nature, reflecting human preference. They are also subject to economic fluctuations (inflation, exchange rates, etc.) and not suitable for the evaluation of supporting services as soil formation, photosynthesis, primary production, nutrient and water cycling.

Thermodynamics approaches such as *emergy* and *eco-exergy* have been used to understand the behaviour of ecosystems. *Emergy* is the energy incorporated into a product or a service reduced to the energy supplied by the sun. It characterizes all products and services in solar energy equivalent. *Eco-exergy* is the available energy of an ecosystem (e.g. the chemical energy stored in organic matter), including the energy of the embodied information (e.g. genetic information). It is measured in kilojoules.

Emergy analysis quantifies the contributions from human resources and the work done by nature in dissipating pollution, while *exergy* is a way of quantifying resource depletion. However, these approaches are not appropriate to consider supporting and cultural services and they are affected by difficulties of collecting ecological data.

The *footprint analysis* represents the direct and indirect impact of human activities in terms of aggregate metrics such as ecological footprint, carbon footprint or water footprint. It calculates land and water area a population needs to produce resources and absorb the generated waste. It applies to multiple uses of land and biodiversity, but it does not cover cultural services (spiritual and recreational benefits) of eco-system services.

None of these methods allows to consider all the ecosystem services, which may provide misleading results and lead to unsatisfactory decisions. These approaches strive to aggregate the resources in terms of a single unit (e.g. monetary, kilojoules, CO₂, solar energy equivalent,

land area, etc.) which is not possible for representing all ecosystem services and lead to loss of information. In addition, the quantifications rely on information that is often uncertain and incomplete.

To facilitate the decision-making process, attention should be paid to methods able to combine quantitative and qualitative information represented in several units, and to deal with uncertainties. Such methods, inspired by “multi-attribute utility theory” (MAUT), have been tested in forest management (e.g. ELECTRE) [175].

The interest of multi-criteria methods is to consider a set of criteria of different nature (expressed in different units), without necessarily transforming them into economic criteria, or into a single function. It is not a question of seeking an optimum, but to find a compromise solution. In a first step, scenarios are constructed by the stakeholders, based on an information system and on models allowing to simulate the evolution of the characteristics of the forest. In a second step, the various objectives assigned to the forest area are assessed on the basis of the scenarios using a comprehensive set of criteria and indicators. A multi-criteria assessment can then be used to compare potential strategies and to make a choice taking into account the relative importance that the involved participants may attach to the different decision issues. Multicriteria analysis makes it possible to respect the nature of the evaluations expressed in different units.

To measure the criteria, context, actions and results indicators must be identified and possibly combined to represent the strengths and weaknesses of each potential scenario. These ones are classified according to the relative importance given to each criterion and a negotiation process can start to determine the best solution. This approach promotes communication between stakeholders and allows them to structure the decision-making process and to converge towards a consensus on the scenario to be adopted.

However, methods like *i-Tree Eco* aiming to quantify the urban forest structure and to monetarize some ecosystem services provided by trees, could be essentially used as constructive media to initiate the interest and engagement of the general public, planners, policy makers and managers in urban forest projects. Although they do not reflect realistically and holistically services provided by trees, they could represent an informative booster to invest in planning and in research on more trustable valuation methods of urban forests. In this way, urban greening can become a more readily appreciated strategy for improving environmental conditions in dense urban areas.

2.2.b Mapping methods

Because all current and future urban planning decisions are intrinsically spatial, it is very relevant to integrate mapping methods in decision-making processes.

Mapping of ecosystem services reveals the spatial relationships between urban landcover characteristics and their local efficiency [176]. If for example, local contributions of trees to local air quality is mapped thanks to a Geographical Information System (GIS) method, the rela-

tionship can be made with the other elements of the urban landscape, in order to understand if there are elements preventing full efficiency of air pollution removal (e.g. street architecture increasing heat-island effect, distance of trees from the pollution source). Overlaying this map with other maps showing spatial air temperature simulation, or city's traffic, would add even more information to understand interaction between all elements of the city, their impact on ecosystem services provided by trees and planning opportunities to improve them.

This type of decision support system avoids the challenging task of assigning monetary values to services. It is a place-based valuation of services in non-monetary terms to provide spatially-explicit guidance for future land use decisions [177].

In the case study of Turrialba with *i-Tree Eco*, it was seen that mapping of ecosystem services is only feasible for individual surveyed trees. A full urban forest mapping would only be possible if all urban trees are field-surveyed, which is not conceivable. Therefore, it would be relevant to investigate further in mapping local ecosystem services contributions by urban trees. Reed and Brown(2003) [178] already developed the idea of “values suitability analysis” incorporating mapped ecosystem data into traditional land suitability analysis.

The spatial analysis offered by *i-Tree Canopy* combined with *Google Earth* (see Part 6.3) permits comparison of urban forest cover over time to assess policy efficacy and inform adaptive management decision making for the future. Indeed, the areal extent and resolution of satellite and other aerial images are good enough for citywide and regional scale urban planning purposes.

Moreover, the “landcover classification” method (see Part 6.2) offered by *ArcGIS* can be used to get the spatial distribution and percent coverage of urban canopy. With the highest quality satellite images exported from *Google Earth* (4800x2833), the most accurate output raster image will be obtained on small areas. It is possible to perform the analysis on wider areas to get the bigger picture of the canopy cover distribution. However, a lot of accuracy is lost in the output raster image. Nevertheless, with a reasonable satellite image quality (recommendation 20 hectares maximum), classification raster images can permit to visualize the urban canopy cover network compared to the non-canopy surface where other classes can be analyzed such as “buildings” and “roads”. Moreover, by running landcover classification analysis on several images with exact same resolution, it would be possible to get the analysis on a wider area by assembling raster images together.

Thanks to this method, areas with different types of canopy cover distribution (according to tree cover percentage and to spatial distribution i.e. heterogeneity and homogeneity) can be identified. This could support the *i-Tree Eco* “stratum” identification that goes along with the study area definition (see Part 5.2.a). Then, analysed areas with *i-Tree Eco* can be brought together with similar areas identified by means of landcover classification method. Such, results can be extrapolated to other areas and extend the study area. This extrapolation method would help limiting the field-survey work, that is time and costs invested in the field inventory. In addition, remote sensing can also be used to get information on the spatial distribution of different types of vegetation patches and their canopy coverage and condition [5], what is more with increased accuracy but increased costs.

2.3 Recommendations on urban forest composition decision-making and on planting

2.3.a Species choice

While deciding on urban forest design strategies, species composition must be considered. Research forester Zipperer [179] reckons that with the aim of maintaining or enhancing ecosystem services through influencing urban ecosystem structure and altering urban ecosystem processes, a landscape planner must consider how to link ecosystem management to **single-tree management**. To this purpose, he designed this decision-making scheme Figure 5.1 that comes from the *Theory of vegetation dynamics* ([180]). He modified it for application of ecosystem management in urban landscapes by incorporating elements of the urban ecosystem used in the management-decision process.

Figure 5.1: Criteria for urban forest design to include in decision-making processes [5]

Adequate specie is chosen considering: the criteria listed under “environmental”, “autoecology” and “interactions” and according to the priority criteria chosen by the decision-makers (e.g. if they want to prioritize one specific ecosystem service); the growing site availability (if an adequate plot to grow the specie is available, since planting site affect tree growth rate [181] and health); specie’s availability (practically be able to provision easily chosen tree species through nursery if they are exotic or through natural dispersal for native species).

However, under the pane “autoecology” mentioning how the tree can sustain itself, should also appear criteria reflecting the tree’s resistance to stressors and adaptability to future changing conditions: its climate resilience potential. Moreover, tree resilience should then be a systematic priority in the species decision-making process. This way chosen species should both be “mitigators” of local threatening urban conditions and “adaptors” to local stressors and to the occurrence of extreme conditions.

In this respect, tree selection is an important decision point to smoothly transition to a more stable and resilient urban forest structure and reduce vulnerability leading to catastrophic loss of tree canopy in the future. Besides, a more resilient urban forest is likely to produce more ecosystem services compared to a less resilient forest. One of the most important urban forest climate adaptation strategy is planting and maintenance of tree species well-suited to both present and future site growing conditions, namely “climate-ready trees” [182]. Identifying and testing the resilience of tree species in a specific study area that are not locally grown (non-native species), is the research topic of McPherson et al. (2018) [182] aiming to provide field-based information on the “climatic” performance of tree species. For example, tree species *Eucalypts parramattensis* from the study of Drake et al. [183] was remarkably capable of tolerating an extreme heatwave via “sustained transpirational cooling and increased leaf thermal tolerance”. Another still ongoing research track is based on the mechanisms of the physiological adaptability of trees: the development of genetically modified vegetation to function under much higher ambient temperatures seems to be a promising perspective according to Santamouris et al. (2018), convinced that further research on vegetation adaptation will be intensified in the future [71].

Inspired from above elements, Figures 5.2 and 5.3 suggest sets of criteria (non-exhaustive) for decision-making on tree species, according to desired functions to be delivered by trees or according to the resistance and adaptability to different stressor types differing among tree species. This way, it is easier to select priority criteria according to priority functions and stressors. Moreover, Figure 5.3 includes climate stressors, thus includes criteria for choosing “climate-ready” trees. Resistance to most of these stressors is measured experimentally relatively to other tree species. For example paper [182] presents a ranking method of a set of trees in terms of adaptability and resistance to climate change. Potential adaptation processes by trees mentioned Figure 5.3 are not tested, but only the health of trees experimentally exposed to stressors. This way, most resistant and adaptable trees will be identified among a set of trees.

Additionally, tree tolerance to air pollution stressor (increase in N, S deposition, acidification) is intimately related to its air pollution removal function.

Figure 5.2 is inspired by a presentation from Fernando Bulnes S. [184]. Figure 5.3 is partly based on root ecology research, since roots are playing an important role in the functioning of forest ecosystems and in the response to urban stressors. Soil alkalinity and soil contamination response processes come from the study carried out by Day et al. (2010) [38] and responses of roots to drought was found in Brunner et al. (2015) [46].

Figure 5.2: Criteria for decision-making on tree-species according to prioritized tree function

Figure 5.3: Criteria for decision-making on tree-species according to stressors trees must adapt and resist to

In addition, to take more efficient decisions on tree species, relevant indicators can be created, representing the absolute performance of a tree specie on a specific ecosystem service, by considering related positive and negative processes or traits, as well as their tolerance to related stressors that can potentially inhibit benefits.

For example, Sicard et al. (2018) [185] has developed a relevant indicator to reflect ozone removal potential of species: the Species-specific Air Quality Index S-AQI from “recommended” (> 8) to “not recommended” (< 4). While taking into account all processes that can favour new ozone production or inhibit ozone removal capacity, this indicator also reflects tolerance of trees to changing conditions (increase of ozone concentration, droughts, pest outbreaks and diseases). To get the final score, the following categories are scored between 1 and 3 (1 low, 2 medium and 3 high) and summed up: O_3 removal capacity, NO_2 removal capacity, PM10 removal capacity, O_3 formation potential, and “pollen allergenicity, O_3 sensitivity and tolerance to drought, pest and diseases” averaged into one score. The study presenting this indicator provides a graph presenting S-AQI of certain European tree species. The recommended value to select species according to this index is $S-AQI > 8$ i.e. with good O_3 removal capacity, O_3 -tolerant, resistant to pests and diseases, tolerant to drought and non-allergenic.

However, decision-making on air pollution mitigation with trees should go along with reduction of motorized vehicles through the city, especially during heat waves. Such, VOC emissions from trees will not reach peak concentrations [82] that are not taken into account in this indicator and would considerably degrade ozone removal function of trees basically chosen to ensure it. To follow-up on this example, similar indicators could be created for other prioritized ecosystem services such as water retention, biodiversity habitat, cooling effect with as *positive processes*, respectively, leaf area index, crown size, potential evapotranspiration and as *inhibition stressors* respectively storm event, pest outbreaks, drought.

2.3.b Planting recommendations

Different urban native afforestation methods exist through either natural colonization (from seed bank and dispersal) or the planting of juvenile trees. In any case, diversity needs to be ensured. Indeed, devastating pest outbreaks in some cases presented in Carreiro et al. (2008) [5] showed potential hazards of low diversity tree population and their negative impact on urban forest management. Tree species diversity also goes along with fauna diversity since habitats are diversified within the city. Richards (1993) [186] suggests that “no species should represent more than 15% of the total tree population of a city and even better that no genus should account for more than 10% of the total tree population”.

Current research revealing patterns for the initial years of planting (1–5) [187] shows that where nearby tree seed sources exist, vegetation colonization is possible without intervention but that management by mowing of invasives boosts species diversity. However, they demonstrate the difficulty of achieving diversity if planted natives do not contribute to recruitment and if local seed source diversity is low. The first reason can occur frequently since native species are

often not suitable to local urban conditions, although they are from the local region. Indeed, urban local conditions can vary a lot and are different from the natural conditions of the same region. For example, many urban soils have alkaline soils due to concrete chemistry, but many native species grow in acidic soils [187]. Moreover, planting juvenile trees has the advantage to bypass the high-mortality seedling recruitment stage but the drawback to bypass earlier stages of succession in order to achieve desired species composition [188]. With all these observations, Sullivan et al. (2009) recommends “removing invasive seed sources within 100 meters” of afforestation sites and ensuring the abundance of nearby desired seed sources through creation of buffer areas surrounding them.

Moreover, landscape ecologists increasingly recognize that exotic-native mixed urban forests are not necessarily a threat to native tree types persistence [189] and that they can provide ecosystem services by coexisting [190]. This supports the strategy of looking for “climate-ready” species mentioned above but also to keep native species for supporting native biodiversity. Exotic species integration is a new strategy since forest managers have always been choosing native trees for urban afforestation [191, 192, 193].

However, in order to conclude on competition of different species over time and on the best species mix, it is necessary to perform longer terms (10 to 25 years) experiments to understand vegetation dynamics. For example, there may be initial dominance by an invasive specie compensated on the long-term by canopy closure covering up shade-intolerant invasives [194, 195]. What is more, the relative position of trees on the site should be taken into account (distance between them and distance to buildings) and experimented over time in relation to canopy competition as a limiting factor.

Moreover, as a first step, planting sites can be improved by human intervention in order to increase tree growth rate and life expectancy of urban trees. Indeed, providing good growing sites and conditions combined with a selection of resilient species will keep them robust. This will permit them to reach their biological maturity in terms of size and physiology and consequently to enhance their functions performance, thus to increase benefits on urban ecosystems. Landscape architects have developed several planting recommendations based on the idea that “larger, higher quality soil volumes for rooting enhances survival and growth” [36]. Indeed, the study has shown that increasing soil volume allows to recover transplanting shock more rapidly, which is a very critical process in relation to trees survival and growth rate. Moreover, standard pavement tree pits are usually not large enough to sustain street tree health over time ($1.4m^3$)[196]. Although the study only reflects short-term responses and that long-term responses could most likely show the limitation of trees growth rate by urban conditions, planting site improvement is already a great upgrade in the early stage. Furthermore, the study suggest to ensure maintenance of the planting site (ensure proper irrigation and drainage) at least during first 15 years following installation of trees in order to overcome urban environment limitations to tree growth.

2.4 Case study related recommendations

These recommendations derive from Turrialba case study and can be generalized to other urban forest case studies.

Decision-making on planting site availability:

- The highest planting potential of cities will be identified, if it is equally investigated on public and on private planting opportunities. Thus by knowing the current distribution between public and private trees derived from *i-Tree Eco*, we can identify where the investigation of planting opportunities should be focused. In Turrialba, stratum “Puente Negro”, “Rio Colorado” and “Estacion de tren” should look more into private planting possibilities, thus develop campaigns reaching private public to sensitize citizen. In addition, ensuring an equal distribution of street trees and non-street trees (parks or small green spaces such as forest remnants) can ensure that each neighbourhood has at least a number of streets with tree borders as well as green patches.

Decision-making on species composition:

- To decide on the species to prioritize in the species mix, following **functions** should be prioritized (see Part 2.3): *wildlife habitat and biodiversity conservation, hydrology effects* and *air pollution removal*. In fact, Turrialba is a tropical city where water flows can be very intense during storm events and lead to flood and erosion which is an important concern. Although flood risk in the city of Turrialba is quite low, it may increase with climate disruption. What is more, water quality is ranked as “poor” in Turrialba which adds to the priority of tree benefits set on hydrology. Concerning air pollution, human health related to air quality is an important issue in the region and the city centre of Turrialba is very exposed to vehicle exhaust air pollution. Furthermore, prioritising biodiversity conservation is relevant since Turrialba city is part of a biological corridor linking different protected areas and it should reduce its fragmentation impact on wildlife. Moreover, Turrialba is part of the region with the greatest richness of birds and mammals, where the government invests in biodiversity conservation. A “green corridors” project to reconnect wildlife patches surrounding the city could be part of this investment. Besides, a large variety of edible fruit trees can easily grow in the region and attract bird species and insects.

The other non-prioritized ecosystem services provided by trees are still convincing and should be used in tree planting project campaigns. Planted in the city, they could also bring benefits to the population such as bringing a sense of ownership and of caring for nature.

- To decide on the species composition of the urban forest, a priority should be put on the following **stressors** to be tolerant to (see Part 2.3): soil compaction (with only 27% of plantable soil according to *i-Tree Eco* most of the ground surface is hosting concrete or asphalt infrastructures bringing to soil compaction), heat wave (the city might be subject to elevated temperatures due to climate change) and storm (trees on the river banks should be very resistive to strong flows and overflow). This way, the priority is set on “climate-ready” trees to transition smoothly to a more resilient city.

Other planning recommendations:

- Trees provide benefits on soil structure and increase soil stability via mechanical reinforcement (see Part 2.). Moreover, Turrialba watershed suffers from erosion on the river banks, rendering these areas more vulnerable and bringing alluvial deposits in the river flow that can obstruct artificial concrete channels such as the one constructed to let Rio Colorado flow under the city. Therefore, it is important to reinforce the urban forest on the river banks, such as on risk zones drawn Figure 4.10 and along Turrialba river part that is within the city. However, since it has been experienced to see trunks obstructing the channel, it is recommended to regularly maintain the trees around it so that tree material does not fall into it.
- More trees should be grown near air pollution sources. Especially at all intersections of “Avenida 2” with other streets since it is a high-traffic axis. Indeed, near to their sources, particulate interception by trees would be considerably higher [5].
- Using the image outputted from ArcGIS landcover classification method (Part 6.2), green corridors and patches can be identified and an improved green network could be proposed.

2.5 Other recommendations

2.5.a Bureaucratic aspect

Political identification of urban forests is crucial since of all constraints, inertia is the most limiting: main obstacles are administrative and political related to policies [197]. The transition to sustainable cities is costly because of the dual task of repairing past ills as a “transgenerational debt” and of increasing future benefits. Indeed, in many compact cities, the “inaction of previous generations has left a heritage of greenery deficit” [5]. Therefore, a city’s urban forest should be considered as “vital urban infrastructure” deserving as much scientifically informed decision-making and long-term planning as built infrastructure.

2.5.b Participatory processes

“It takes more than an understanding of trees to sustain a successful urban forest” states Nerys Jones [5]. Indeed, in an anthropogenic ecosystem such as cities, ensuring sufficient ecosystem services levels per capita demands human effort integration in planning processes. Furthermore, participation of people in greening projects can build a sense of ownership that helps prevent non-respect of urban nature, increases general knowledge, reconnects people with nature, therefore improving the intangible benefits they receive from trees, and empowering them.

In addition, achieving the social goal of equal allocation of ecosystem services from urban trees goes through improving public-private partnership. “Reforestation can be viewed as analogous to dramas: vegetation ecologists write play scenarios, government and private companies work as producers and directors, and citizens, including school children, play the part of leading characters on the stage. Everyone has the opportunity to play a role in reforesting their region” expresses Akira Miyawaki [5].

Another relatively new research field tackles the integration of spatial information in participatory planning processes [198] called “PPGIS”. Cox et al. (2014) [199] states that “PPGIS offers a practical toolset for efficiently capturing and analyzing stakeholder management preferences, allowing managers to make informed decisions and understand trade-offs”. Through surveying, intangible tree-based ecosystem services can also be highlighted.

Furthermore, the example of Porto Alegre (Brazil) where a system of integrated environmental management was successfully adopted, is inspiring [73]. The system is based on four interrelated components presented Figure 5.4.

All components are inter-related: programmes and activities implemented within each component should also consider principles of the other components in order to be more effective and to benefit from integration in the global system.

In order to involve different actors, the need was identified for a largely accessible knowledge and information system of the urban and surroundings natural environment. Fundamental changes followed-up for example teaching methods placed greater emphasis on the students own environmental context. This way, citizens participate in environmental policy-making and participatory budgeting through municipal councils or assemblies. They also participate in multi-stakeholder programmes providing ownership of their local environment: for example the City Square Councils Programme,

Figure 5.4: Integrated environmental management system applied in Porto Alegre [73]

which brings together citizens, civil society organizations and businesses to organize gardening and maintenance of a city square and define rules for its use.

This innovative system in Porto Alegre is based on the principle that, in order to meaningfully participate in urban environmental management, citizens need adequate information and knowledge about the natural and built environments to be able to make informed decisions. This was achieved mainly through the *Environmental Atlas of Porto Alegre*, produced between 1994 and 1998 by about 200 school and university actors. It is organized into three sections: the “Natural Environment” (city’s geology, geomorphology, hydrology, soils, flora, fauna, climate and conservation units), the “Built Environment” (evolution of the city, urban spatial model, development of green areas, tree planting along public roadways, urban climate, environmental impacts and urban sanitation) and “Environmental Management” (key concepts and problems of environmental management in an increasingly urbanized context, public environmental management and environmental data from Porto Alegre itself). Moreover, the language used makes it accessible and easy to read with lots of visuals, for technophiles and non-technophiles and makes information readily available for decision-making involving planners, politicians, institutions and citizens.

2.5.c Urban greening design

A design that fulfils the purpose of *landscape connectivity* mentioned Part 2 would include “large green areas connected with wide and long linear corridors that offer greater exchange and contact for people and organisms with the surrounding of the city and that are situated next to artificial linear features (such as roads, coastlines or streams), to serve as environmental buffers facilitating movement of organisms among remnant habitat patches.” Indeed, studies showed that width is the feature of green corridors that is most significant for their functional fulfillment [200]. This green network design (also called “dynamic patch mosaic system” [5]) allows interpenetration of grey and green areas thanks to longer interfaces and to more efficient biochemical processes on the green areas (due to a sufficient surface) thus benefiting better grey areas. Moreover, “small remnant nature islands embedded in compact developed areas, should be kept in wild state” [201]. Although these pockets of nature randomly distributed in the city have mostly been eradicated through urbanization, they can still serve as a linkage between the city and its boundaries through diverse wildlife attraction. Besides, a distinction has to be made between *structural connectivity* representing spatial connection and *functional connectivity* representing ecological processes pathways such as dispersal and nutrient dynamics. Indeed, *functional connectivity* can radically deviate the spatial green network [5].

Furthermore, urban forest planning and design should not stop at urban limits. The *hierarchy theory of landscapes*, adds to the *connectivity principle* and suggests that an understanding of hierarchical relationships on multiple scales (single trees, urban forests, corridors, remnant patches, urban boundaries, regional context) and on multiple disciplines is required to ensure urban planning success.

For example, Table 5.2 lists functions of elements of urban green spaces gradually according to scale, each element fulfilling special functions.

Setting or context	Park type	Park function
Urban parks	Urban “pocket” parks Urban nature parks/urban forests Urban cultural-landscape park	Neighbourhood use Urban recreation/leisure
Urban to suburban	Green corridors, greenways, trails	Linking urban parks for people, fauna, and flora Linking city center and outskirts for people, fauna, and flora
Country parks, regional parks	Suburban parks and green zone territories/suburban forests Linkage of open spaces	Recreation for town inhabitants Sources of natural resources (water, air, etc.) for the city Protection of open space and landscape Linking suburban forests and suburban parks Instrument for landscape structuring

Table 5.2: Gradual elements of urban green space and examples of their functions [202]

The *connectivity principle* can be applied by mapping existing green areas in the city according to their type (patch, corridor, wild forest remnant, managed area) and visualize their positioning towards the morphology of the city (e.g. buildings, main roads) and of the surroundings (identify the connections to sub-urban green areas). Also, the available sites for planting should be mapped (including private sites based on citizen participation to identify planting plots in their own properties). After identifying new connections and new green patches that can potentially be created, suggestions can be emitted to rectify the shape of existing green patches and corridors (wider, longer corridors, extension of green patches). Moreover, streets with very low planting site availability can still be considered in the planning as street-tree lines, since they can be used as secondary ecological connection axis and can socially benefit the area. Besides, distributing forest canopy cover in ways that are socially equitable is also an important aspect that can be dealt with through GIS mapping, trying to equally provide each neighbourhood of a city and especially identified unprivileged zones with trees and green areas. As such, opportunities for providing both greater ecological and social connectivity can be identified.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

Throughout this study, the impact of urbanization on natural ecosystem processes and the existence of a new “urban ecosystem” has been identified. In an era of simultaneous urban compaction and climate change, threats of urbanization on human health and on nature are enhanced. The need to compensate anthropogenic disturbances, to mitigate climate change effects and to adapt to mutating urban and natural ecosystem dynamics, is vital. These necessities call for urban resiliency solutions to achieve “system metastability” (or “nonequilibrium resilience”) defined by the urban system’s internal diversity, flexibility, and adaptability in response to unpredictable environmental changes. According to the “landscape self-organizing complexity” principle [5], this state is spontaneously achievable by complex systems where numerous elements are interacting nonlinearly such as cities, but how (ecologically and socio-economically) and when it will happen is unpredictable. However, to preserve human health and well-being, this evolution needs to be controlled, to ensure smooth transition in the timescales dictated by climate change processes (before entering a deadlock), and influenced by human effort focusing on urban internal resources.

Although previous generations left a legacy of greenery deficit in cities, trees have been used in cities for purposes changing over time and have always responded and adapted to their changing environment, in quick unpredictable ways. As a remarkable tool, the potential of the urban forest to increase city’s resilience, in addition to other city greening solutions, has been identified in this study. The relevance of trees is determined by the multiple range of ecosystem services they can provide together with their ability to adapt biochemical processes so as to resist rough biotic and abiotic changes. Consequently, trees can indirectly influence their environment’s dynamics and turn other components of the urban landscape into key actors of resiliency. In this respect, human-beings as “urban species” have the duty to be the first link of the change chain.

In order to influence urban planning stakeholders to integrate urban forests into their decision-making processes, the need for tools to understand an urban forest’s structure, function and value has been proved. Scientific papers about tree benefits are not lacking but methodologies to use those results are. Numerous methods have currently been developed to assess ecosystem services and most of them are designed to be readily available through monetarizing. *i-Tree Eco* is one of them and focuses on ecosystem services provided by trees. The software has been tested on a case study in Turrialba, Costa Rica, which is a tropical region. With such a study area location where data availability is low, the software revealed a lot of uncertainty sources. Although the need to improve input data to perform a relevant quantitative analysis is real, the output results are also questionable. Indeed, the model behind the software showed to entail many simplifications rendering hydrology results unreliable and leaving uncertainty

in air pollution removal and biogenic emission results. However, strengths of the software lie first in its stratified statistical model to monitor structural composition of the urban forest, with the prerequisite of partitioning the study area to get more accurate results and optimize the field inventory resources. Then, it lies in the informative aspect through raising awareness about the multiple benefits of trees as well as about their disservices. Being widely accessible thanks to its public and user-friendly interface, it can act as a connecting platform creating community-based knowledge and experience. Besides, the readily available results it provides can initiate and give some framework to the integration of urban forestry in multi-stakeholder urban planning decisions.

Consequently, it is crucial to define the purpose of the study before using *i-Tree Eco* which can be sufficient for purposes implying qualitative urban forest functions description. To quantitatively assess city trees on the hydrology functions, *i-Tree* proposes a more reliable process-based model, *i-Tree Hydro*, also suitable for analysis under extreme rain event conditions. This tool is not suitable to assess the effect and resistance of trees under extreme conditions. Thereupon, decisions-making on tree-species is particularly relevant based on existing tree-knowledge and identification of “climate-ready” trees. Although the suggested multi-criteria framework is adapted for the practical planning phase of an urban greening project, it can also be powerful at the decisions-making stage to highlight the availability of specific trees proved to be performant and resistant.

To actually integrate ecosystem services provided by urban trees in planning decision-making, there is a need to shift from optimisation methods focused on one criterion to multi-variable approaches seeking a compromise between several scenarios such as the “multi-attribute utility theory”. Those methods can deal with both quantitative and qualitative information, thus also capturing intangible ecosystem services.

Additionally, spatial heterogeneity of the urban forest within its urban environment, which is not captured in *i-Tree* tools, is particularly relevant in both decision-making and urban forest design processes. While GIS softwares offer tools based on satellite image analysis which can identify canopy cover distribution and ensure the design of socio-ecological green networks, mapping local effects of trees can help understanding the relationships between urban landscape characteristics and their local efficiency to contribute to human well-being. Maps are meaningful supports for decision-making speaking to everyone and able to highlight essential connections.

Finally, qualifying tree-based ecosystem services also goes through participatory processes valuing intangible benefits of trees on human well-being and simultaneously improving them by reconnecting urban dwellers with their own local nature as well as promoting inclusive urban planning decisions.

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Appendix :

A. Local tree species information of i-Tree database

The following table lists the information used in the i-Tree model by inputting each local tree type in the inventory data. The percent leaf type informs on leaf density. Cells are let empty when the data was not found in the i-Tree database online platform.

APPENDIX

Genus name	Species name	Family	Order	Class	Common name	Growth form	Percent leaf type	Leaf type	Growth rate	Longevity	Height at maturity (m)
Acnistus	arborescens	Solanaceae	Solanales	Asteridae	Hollowheart	Shrub or small tree	Hardwood	Evergreen	Fast	Short	6
Jacaranda	mimosifolia	Bignoniaceae	Scrophulariales	Asteridae	Blue jacaranda	Tree	Hardwood	Deciduous	Fast	Short	13
Cecropia	palmata	Cecropiaceae	Urticales	Hamamelidae	Cecropia	Tree	Hardwood	Evergreen			
Chrysophyllum	cainito	Sapotaceae	Ebenales	Dilleniidae	Star apple	Tree	Hardwood	Deciduous	Slow		12
Cocos	nucifera	Arecaceae	Arecales	Arecidae	Coconut palm	Palm	Palm	Evergreen	Moderate	Moderate	18
Cojoba	arborea	Fabaceae	Fabales	Rosidae	Cojoba	Tree	Hardwood	Evergreen	Slow		17
Erythrina	edulis	Fabaceae	Fabales	Rosidae	Sacha poroto	Tree	Hardwood	Deciduous	Fast	Moderate	8
Erythrina	poeppigiana	Fabaceae	Fabales	Rosidae	Mountain immortelle	Tree	Hardwood	Deciduous	Fast		17
Psidium	friedrichsthalianum				Guayaba coronilla						
Mangifera	indica	Anacardiaceae	Sapindales	Rosidae	Mango	Tree	Hardwood	Evergreen	Moderate	Long	20
Morinda	citrifolia	Rubiaceae	Rubiales	Asteridae	Indian mulberry	Shrub or small tree	Hardwood	Evergreen	Moderate	Long	6
Persea	americana	Lauraceae	Laurales	Magnoliidae	Avocado	Tree	Hardwood	Evergreen	Moderate	Moderate	12
Persea	urbaniana	Lauraceae	Laurales	Magnoliidae	Aguacatillo	Shrub or small tree	Hardwood	Evergreen	Moderate		17
Psidium	gua.java	Myrtaceae	Myrtales	Rosidae	Common guava	Shrub or small tree	Hardwood	Evergreen	Moderate	Long	6
Roystonea	regia	Arecaceae	Arecales	Arecidae	Florida royal palm	Palm	Palm	Evergreen	Fast	Long	25
Syzygium	malaccense	Myrtaceae	Myrtales	Rosidae	Malaysian apple	Tree	Hardwood	Evergreen	Moderate		12
Terminalia	muellerii	Combretaceae	Myrtales	Rosidae	Terminalia muellerii	Tree	Hardwood	Deciduous	Moderate	Moderate	
Veitchia	merrillii	Arecaceae	Arecales	Arecidae	Christmas palm	Palm	Palm	Evergreen	Moderate		8
Zygia	longifolia	Fabaceae	Fabales	Rosidae	Buscilla	Tree	Hardwood	Evergreen	Moderate	Long	15
Zygia spp											

B. Local tree species identification guide

Common name	Casquil	Common name	Guaba caite
Scientific name	<i>Cupania cinerea</i>	Scientific name	<i>Inga spectabilis</i>
Leaf and trunk			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference:	https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php	Reference:	https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php

Common name	Guachipelin	Common name	Cachá
Scientific name	<i>Diphysa americana</i>	Scientific name	<i>Chloroleucon eurycyclum</i>
Leaf and trunk			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference:	http://unibio.unam.mx/irekani/handle/123456789/57115?proyecto=Irekani	Reference:	https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php

Common name	Lorito	Common name	Hule
Scientific name	<i>Cojoba arborea</i>	Scientific name	<i>Castilla elastica</i>
Leaf and tree shape			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php		Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php	

Common name	Poró (can be found inside houses)	Common name	Guarumbo
Scientific name	<i>Erythrina costaricensis</i>	Scientific name	<i>Cecropia obtusifolia</i>
Leaf			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference: http://herbario.up.ac.pa/Herbario/herb/vasculares/view/species/2150		Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php https://twitter.com/hillron/status/615181595612327936?lang=es	

Common name	Uruga	Common name	Balsa
Scientific name	<i>Trichilia havanensis</i>	Scientific name	<i>Ochroma pyramidale</i>
Leaf			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference: http://unibio.unam.mx/irekani/handle/123456789/54904?proyecto=Irekani		Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php	

Common name	Ficus	Common name	Guaba chilillo
Scientific name	<i>Ficus benjamina</i>	Scientific name	<i>Inga densiflora</i>
Leaf			
Flower		Flower	
Fruit		Fruit	
Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php		Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php	

Common name	Jacaranda	Common name	Leucaena
Scientific name	<i>Jacaranda mimosifolia</i>	Scientific name	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>
Leaf			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference: http://www.elmundoforestal.com/album/index11.html#jacaranda		Reference: http://www.elmundoforestal.com/album/index12.html	

Common name	Poró (Big tres that are found in river areas)	Common name	Mamón chino
Scientific name	<i>Erythrina poeppigiana</i>	Scientific name	<i>Nephelium lappaceum</i>
Leaf			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php		Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/find_sp2.php?customer=Mam%F3n&busca=Buscar#	

Common name	Aguacatillo	Common name	Aguacate
Scientific name	<i>Persea caerulea</i>	Scientific name	<i>Persea americana</i>
Leaf			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference: http://www.elmundoforestal.com/album/index1.html#aguacatillo		Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php	

Common name	Cas	Common name	Llama del bosque
Scientific name	<i>Psidium friedrichsthalianum</i>	Scientific name	<i>Spathodea campanulata</i>
Leaf			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php		Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/index.php	

Common name	Candelillo	Common name	Capulín
Scientific name	<i>Tecoma stans</i>	Scientific name	<i>Trema micrantha</i>
Leaf			
Flower			
Fruit			
Reference: http://www.crbio.cr:8080/neoportal-web/species/Tecoma%20stans		Reference: https://sura.ots.ac.cr/local/florula4/find_sp2.php?customer=Trema+micrantha&busca=Buscar	

C. Field work information sheets

These sheets were realised in Spanish and partly translated in English to integrate in this report. It is based on following references: FAO, 2009; *i-Tree Eco V6.0 Field Manual* in Spanish (2017) and Pérez Bravo et al., *Variables dasométricas relacionadas con la productividad de Acacia mangium Willd*, Centro Agrícola (2017).

To measure crown height with the hypsometer, the user has to stay at a 15 meters distance from the tree (or 20 meters distance if the tree is very high, in this case the other side of the graduations on the hypsometer should be used). 2 people should measure it with 90 ° difference.

TRUNK CHARACTERISTICS - Diameter at breast height 1.37 m (4.5 ft)

TRUNK CHARACTERISTICS – Measure DBH with irregularities

CROWN CONDITION – Total height, crown height, height of lowest branch, crown width (N-S and W-E)

CROWN CONDITION – How to measure crown height

Methodology to follow in case of significant different values for crown height measurements:

- 1) if the difference is around 10%, values are averaged;
- 2) if the difference is of 15% or more, change measurement positions and try to tend to a 10% difference;
- 3) for trees which anyways give a high difference of values between both measurement positions, values are averaged.

CROWN CONDITION – % Regressive dead

State	Description
Healthy	Crown transparency is less than 50% and there is no crown dieback on top part
Decaying sanitary state	Crown transparency is approximately 50% and crown dieback on top part is evident
Sick	Crown transparency is more than 50% and important crown dieback on top part
Dying	Crown transparency is more than 75% and crown dieback is increasing
Dead	Tree apparently dead or already in vegetative period

CROWN CONDITION – % Missing crown

D. i-Tree surface and upper weather pre-processor: Potential Evaporation and Evapotranspiration calculation methods [95]

Potential evaporation, E [$m.hr^{-1}$] is calculated by the modified Penman-Monteith equation (Shuttleworth 1992):

$$E = \frac{1}{\lambda \rho_w} \left[\frac{\Delta R_n + \frac{\rho_a c_p D}{r_a}}{\Delta + \gamma} \right] \times 10^{-3}$$

λ [$MJ.kg^{-1}$] is the latent heat of vaporization:

$$\lambda = 2.501 - 0.002361T$$

ρ_w [$kg.m^{-3}$] is the density of water:

$$\rho_w = -0.0051T^2 + 0.018T + 999.88$$

δ [$kPa^\circ C^{-1}$] is the slope of vapor pressure temperature curve:

$$\Delta = \frac{4398e_s}{(237.3+T)^2}$$

ρ_a [$kg.m^{-3}$] is the density of air:

$$\rho_a = 3.486 \frac{P}{275+T}$$

c_p is the specific heat of moist air ($=1.013 kJ.kg^{-1}^\circ C^{-1}$) D [kPa] is the vapor pressure deficit:

$$D = e_s - e$$

e_s [kPa] is the saturated vapor pressure:

$$e_s = 0.6108 \exp\left(\frac{17.27T}{237.3+T}\right)$$

e [kPa] is vapor pressure:

$$e = 0.6108 \exp\left(\frac{17.27DT}{237.3+DT}\right)$$

DT is the dew point temperature [$^\circ C$], γ [$kPa^\circ C^{-1}$] is the psychrometric constant:

$$\gamma = \frac{c_p P}{\lambda}$$

P [mb] is the measured surface pressure.

r_a [$s.m^{-1}$] is the aerodynamic resistance. To estimate the potential evaporation from trees, r_a shown below is used above in the first expression of E .

$$r_a = \frac{4.72 \left(\ln \frac{Z_t}{Z_{ov} d_t} \right)^2}{1 + 0.536 U_t}$$

Z_t is the wind estimate height for trees (=7m), Z_{ov} [m] is the mass transfer coefficient (=0.0123m), d_t [m] is the roughness height for tree (=0.95m). U_t [$m.s^{-1}$] is the wind speed at the tree top:

$$U_t = U \frac{\ln \left(\frac{Z_t}{d_w} \right)}{\ln \left(\frac{Z_u}{d_w} \right)}$$

U is the measured wind speed, d_w is the roughness height for water (=0.00137m), Z_u is the wind measurement height (=2m).

To estimate the potential evaporation from the ground, r_a shown below is used in in the first expression of E .

$$r_a = \frac{4.72 \left(\ln \frac{Z_u}{Z_{ov} d_w} \right)^2}{1 + 0.536 U_g}$$

U_g [$m.s^{-1}$] is the wind on the ground

$$U_g = U \frac{\ln \left(\frac{Z_g}{d_w} \right)}{\ln \left(\frac{Z_u}{d_w} \right)}$$

Z_g is the wind estimate height for the ground (= 0.1 + d_w). The potential evaporation from snow on tree canopy [$m.h^{-1}$] is calculated as (Fassnacht 2004):

$$E = \frac{0.1}{P} \left\{ \frac{U_t}{\left[\ln \left(\frac{Z_t}{d_w} \right) \right]^2} (611.2 - e) \right\} \times 10^{-3}$$

The potential evaporation from snow on the ground [$m.h^{-1}$] is calculated as (Fassnacht 2004):

$$E = \frac{0.1}{P} \left\{ \frac{U_g}{\left[\ln \left(\frac{Z_u}{d_w} \right) \right]^2} (611.2 - e) \right\} \times 10^{-3}$$

Potential evapotranspiration from trees, ET [$m.h^{-1}$] is calculated by the modified Penman-Monteith equation (Shuttleworth 1992):

$$ET = \frac{1}{\lambda \rho_w} \left[\frac{\Delta R_n + \frac{\rho_a c_p D}{r_a}}{\Delta + \gamma \left(1 + \frac{r_s}{r_a} \right)} \right] \times 10^{-3}$$

The aerodynamic resistance, r_a [$s.m^{-1}$] shown below is used in previous equation.

$$r_a = \frac{208}{u_t}$$

r_s [$s.m^{-1}$] is the stomatal resistance:

$$r_s = \frac{200}{L}$$

L is the leaf area index.

References

Fassnacht, S.R., 2004. *Estimating alter-shielded gauge snowfall undercatch, snowpack sublimation, and blowing snow transport at six sites in the coterminous United States*. Hydrological Processes, 18: 3481-3492.

Shuttleworth, W.J., 1992. *Evaporation*, in: Maidment, D.R., (Ed.), Handbook of Hydrology, McGraw-Hill, Inc., New York, pp. 4.1 –4.53.

E. Friction velocity calculation according to atmosphere stability state [94]

E.1 Neutral atmosphere ($L = 0$)

For the neutral atmosphere, u_* is calculated as:

$$u_* = \frac{k \cdot u(z-d)}{\ln\left(\frac{z-d}{z_o}\right)}$$

where k is the von Karman constant ($=0.41$), $u(z)$ [$m \cdot s^{-1}$] the mean wind speed at height z , z [m] height of the weather station, d [m] displacement height, z_o [m] roughness length.

E.2 Unstable atmosphere ($L < 0$)

When the atmosphere is unstable such as during daytime when the air convection occurs, u_* is calculated as ([133]):

$$u_* = \frac{k \cdot u(z-d)}{\ln\left(\frac{z-d}{z_o}\right) - \psi_M\left(\frac{z-d}{L}\right) + \psi_M\left(\frac{z_o}{L}\right)}$$

where Ψ_M is the stability function for momentum and L the Monin-Obuhkov stability length. Stability function for momentum (Ψ_M) is calculated as (van Ulden and Holtslag 1985):

$$\psi_M = 2 \ln\left(\frac{1+x}{2}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{1+x^2}{2}\right) - 2 \tan^{-1}(x) + \frac{\pi}{2}$$

where x is calculated as (Dyer and Bradley 1982):

$$x = \frac{1}{\left(1 - 28 \frac{z}{L}\right)^{0.25}}$$

E.3 Stable atmosphere ($L > 0$)

When the atmosphere is stable u_* is calculated as (Venkatram 1980):

$$u_* = C_{DN} \cdot u(z) \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{2u_o}{\sqrt{C_{DN}} \cdot u(z)}\right)^2} \right]$$

where C_{DN} neutral drag coefficient (dimensionless), calculated as (US EPA 1995):

$$C_{DN} = \frac{k}{\ln\left(\frac{z}{z_o}\right)}$$

and u_o is calculated as (US EPA 1995):

$$u_o = \sqrt{\frac{\beta_m z g \theta_*}{T}}$$

where β_m dimensionless constant (=4.7), g acceleration due to gravity (=9.81 $m.s^{-2}$), T air temperature in K. θ_* is calculated as (US EPA 1995):

$$\theta_* = 0.09(1 - 0.5N^2)$$

where N fraction of opaque cloud cover.

To obtain real valued solutions for u_* , the following condition must hold:

$$\frac{2u_o}{\sqrt{C_{DN} \cdot u(z)}} \leq 1$$

Otherwise, the friction velocity u_* is calculated as (US EPA 1995):

$$u_* = u_{*cr} \frac{u(z)}{u_{cr}}$$

where u_{cr} and u_{*cr} are calculated as (US EPA 1995):

$$u_{cr} = \sqrt{\frac{4}{C_{DN}}} u_o$$

$$u_{*cr} = \frac{C_{DN} u_{cr}}{2}$$

References

Dyer, A. J. and C. F. Bradley. 1982. *An alternative analysis of flux gradient relationships*. Boundary-Layer Meteorology 22: 3-19.

United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA). 1995. *PCRAMMET user's guide*. Research Triangle Park, NC: United States Environmental Protection Agency.

van Ulden, A. P. and A. A. M. Holtslag. 1985. *Estimation of atmospheric boundary layer parameters for diffusion application*. Journal of Climatology and Applied Meteorology 24: 1196-1207.

Venkatram, A. 1980. *Estimating the Monin-Obukhov length in the stable boundary layer for dispersion calculations*. Boundary-Layer Meteorology 19: 481-485.

F. Avoided Runoff Calculation from the i-Tree technical team

This data comes from the i-Tree simulation of Turrialba with the 2019 field data, the user-submitted precipitation data for 2018 and the weather station Tobias Bolanos. To calculate cubic meter values of annual water quantities, it is not the estimated pervious and impervious land cover from the study area that is used but the US average from Nowak et al. (2012) [173]. The 1.7% value is the avoided runoff percentage of the No Tree Cover Runoff which is the runoff of the hypothetical no-tree scenario. Scenario 1 corresponds to the real scenario and scenario 2 to the hypothetical scenario where same ground land cover would be without trees.

Area Information			
Scenario	Considered Area	Calculation details	m2
1 & 2	Study area		120000
1	Tree Cover Percent		17.12121
1 & 2	Pervious Cover Percent		74.5
1 & 2	Impervious Cover Percent		25.5
1	Canopy Area	$\text{Area} * \text{TreeCoverPct} / 100$	20545
1	No Canopy Area	$\text{Area} * (100 - \text{TreeCoverPct}) / 100$	99455
1	Under Canopy Pervious Area	$\text{canArea} * \text{PERVIOUS_PCT} / 100$	15306
1	Under Canopy Impervious Area	$\text{canArea} * \text{IMPERVIOUS_PCT} / 100$	5239
1	No Canopy Pervious Area	$\text{noCanArea} * \text{PERVIOUS_PCT} / 100$	74094
1	No Canopy Impervious Area	$\text{noCanArea} * \text{IMPERVIOUS_PCT} / 100$	25361
2	No Tree Cover Pervious Area	$\text{Area} * \text{PERVIOUS_PCT} / 100$	89400
2	No Tree Cover Impervious Area	$\text{Area} * \text{IMPERVIOUS_PCT} / 100$	30600
Annual Calculations			
Scenario	Considered variable	m/yr	m3/yr
1 & 2	Rain	2.6638	319656
1	Under Canopy Thrufall	2.381524882	48929.51
1	Under Canopy Infiltration	2.194631581	33591.83
1	Under Canopy Runoff	2.157847165	11305.16
1	No Canopy Infiltration	2.431432517	180153.7
1	No Canopy Runoff	2.395132791	60742.74
2	No Tree Cover Infiltration	2.431432517	217370.1
2	No Tree Cover Runoff	2.395132791	73291.06
2-1	Avoided Runoff due to Trees		1243.161
	Percentage avoided Runoff due to Trees		1.7%

G. CO dry deposition flux calculated over a year with *i-Tree Eco*

The CO dry deposition flux graph derives from *i-Tree Eco* projects with Turrialba urban forest, Winchester location and air pollution data and weather stations respectively “Juan Santamaria 2014” and “Tobias Bolanos 2014” in Costa Rica. CO deposition flux still shows the effect of in-leaf and out-of-leaf season on its calculation whereas there are almost no deciduous trees in Turrialba and no radical change in CO concentrations can be observed (graph above). It shows that tree species are not considered in pollutant removal calculations.

H. ArcGIS *Raster to Polygon* function applied on study area raster classification

I. List of cities analysed with *i-Tree Eco* and ranked according to structural results per hectare

City	Number of Trees/ha	Carbon Storage (metric tons/ha)	Carbon Sequestration (metric tons/ha/yr)
Morgantown, WV	294.5	37.7	1.17
Atlanta, GA	275.8	35.7	1.23
Oakville, ON , Canada	192.9	13.4	0.61
London, ON, Canada	185.5	15.3	0.53
Syracuse, NY	167.4	23.1	0.77
Woodbridge, NJ	164.4	24.2	0.84
Toronto, ON, Canada	160.4	17.4	0.73
Moorestown, NJ	153.4	27.9	0.9
Hartford, CT	124.6	28.5	0.86
Washington, DC	121.1	29.8	0.92
Baltimore, MD	118.5	25	0.8
Freehold, NJ	94.6	35.9	0.98
Boston, MA	82.9	20.3	0.67
New York, NY	65.2	15.3	0.48
Minneapolis, MN	64.8	15	0.53
Philadelphia, PA	61.9	14.1	0.43
Chicago, IL	59.9	10.9	0.38
San Francisco, CA	55.7	14.7	0.39
Albuquerque, NM	53.9	8.8	0.28
Los Angeles, CA	48.4	9.4	0.36
Jersey City, NJ	35.5	5	0.21
Phoenix, AZ	31.8	2.9	0.3
Casper, WY	22.5	6.2	0.2

J. Hourly infiltration for Turrialba *i-Tree Eco* model

The model used is with Turrialba field data, IMN user-submitted precipitation data from 2018 and Tobias Bolanos weather station. Infiltration is obtained by subtracting hourly evaporation data to hourly precipitation data and is calculated for both scenarios (hypothetical and actual).

K. *i-Tree Hydro* model details based on Wang et al. [28] and compared to *i-Tree Eco*

The research of UFORE-Hydro is based on creation of a relatively simple, process-based, forest management and research model that would explicitly represent the effects of vegetation and soils on the urban hydrological cycle. This first-order estimate of the water balance allows to compare two or more land use management options, such as the base case and other scenarios for urban tree and vegetation cover. Calibration of the model water balance is only available for watershed simulations of the base case. The topographical-based Urban Forest Effects Hydrological mode combines a set of interception, storage, infiltration, evaporation, and runoff algorithms and is designed for municipal land cover managers and researchers, with algorithms selected, modified, or developed for minimal data input requirements such that most urban areas would be able to readily apply the model.

Model inputs are land cover data, elevation data, meteorological data, and nine soil and runoff parameter values (initial average water table depths and soil moistures, and soil physical parameters, such as hydraulic conductivity), many satisfied using optional default values or

constrained-calibration values.

Meteorological data for the model are precipitation, potential evaporation, and potential evapotranspiration (computed using the modified Penman-Monteith equation like in the *i-Tree Eco* weather pre-processor). These data can be entered at any regular timestep, but increments of 1 h or finer are recommended.

National elevation data to derive a topographic index (TI) is enhanced National Land Cover Data (NLCD) providing subgrid heterogeneity estimates of impervious cover, and tree canopy (extracted from NLCD data using the method of Yang et al. (2003)). Each watershed pixel has a TI value, and these are grouped into blocks of hydrologically representative Units. For each TI block, the watershed distribution of impervious cover and tree canopy are represented.

Outputs at each timestep include canopy interception, impervious depression storage, infiltration, evapotranspiration, surface (pervious and impervious) and subsurface runoff, channel discharge, water quality mean concentration (with algorithms simulating runoff-pollutant loading relationships).

Similarities to the *i-Tree Eco* precipitation interception model : precipitation is distributed on the surface of the watershed according to through canopy precipitation, in-canopy precipitation (and shrub canopy intercepted precipitation if considered); same three phases from the start of a rain event are considered; fraction of watershed surface without vegetation cover and fraction of watershed surface with vegetation cover are considered. The vegetation storage capacity of the forest canopy is linearly related to LAI and expressed as a multiplication of S_L and LAI, where S_L is the specific leaf storage (maximum depth of water retained by leaves of a particular species per unit leaf area). Literature described laboratory methods for experimentally deriving a value of S_L , however, for model simplification and based on reported averages (Dickinson, 1984), UFORE-Hydro sets a default value to 0.0002 m, same simplification is used in *i-Tree Eco*. However this value can be modified in i-Tree Hydro. Similarly, impervious depression storage maximum capacity is defaultly set as 1.5mm but user can input field-derived value.

Added complexity compared to *i-Tree Eco* precipitation interception model:

- Vegetation interception is simulated using a modified Rutter algorithm to incorporate sparse vegetation and seasonal adjustments to leaf area. For deciduous trees, LAI experiences leaf-on, growth, and leaf-off processes within a year, and is set to include a stem area index that intercepts precipitation even during leaf-off. LAI is a minimum in winter (full leaf-off), dominated by stem area, and reaches its maximum with full grown leaf area in summer (full leaf-on). There are transition days between full leaf-off and leaf-on. For simplicity in UFORE-Hydro, we assume equation for vegetation storage ($S = S_L * LAI$) still applies with a combined effect of LAI and stem bark, denoted as bark area index (BAI), represented as total tree area index (TAI). BAI is used to represent average interception storage capacity of tree stem bark (branch and trunk) and is assumed constant for all seasons for one growing year; it is based on canopy area and is updated with tree

growth. The following formula is used to describe the variations of average daily TAI in the catchment: $TAI = LAI * F_{leaf} + BAI$ where F_{leaf} is the fraction of tree canopy in-leaf (i.e., not counting bare trees) in the catchment. This value is a maximum of 100% after full leaf-on in summer, and is a minimum after deciduous leaf drop, representing only the percent of evergreen canopy. The maximum TAI, TAI_{max}, is in summer and minimum TAI, TAI_{min}, is in winter, adjusted based on F_{leaf} decreasing in winter. For daily TAI values in spring and autumnal transition days, when leaf cover is changing, a modified sigmoid function is used.

- Water balance in Hydro-model considers more loss terms than only the evaporation from free water in the tree canopy and from depression storage, like in the *i-Tree Eco* precipitation interception model: also considers evaporation from the free water in the short crop (grass or shrub) canopy and the evapotranspiration of soil water volumes through direct evaporation and vegetation transpiration. An energy balance is maintained to ensure total available energy is reduced by the energy used to evaporate intercepted water from the canopy and leaves a smaller total available energy for soil and transpiration. Evapotranspiration of soil water through the vegetation is also based on Penman-Monteith formulations, where potential values are modified downward based on soil and leaf canopy moisture resistances. Evapotranspiration is calculated similarly than for evaporation calculations in *i-Tree Eco* by multiplying potential evapotranspiration (higher when there is more trees) by S_r/S_{max} where S_r is root zone storage deficit (m), S_{max} is maximum allowable storage deficit (m). Direct evaporation from soil surfaces is based on the same soil moisture resistances (not on fictive pervious depression storage such as in *i-Tree Eco*).
- Infiltration UFORE-Hydro in the pervious area watershed fraction takes precipitation not allocated to interception and partitions it between ponding, infiltration, or runoff. In considering this partition, UFORE-Hydro uses the modified Green-Ampt infiltration theory together with TOPMODEL concepts of infiltration and saturation excess processes (Beven et al., 1995). In this formulation of the infiltration routine, the infiltration rate, i , is given as:

$$i = \frac{dI}{dt} = \frac{\Delta\psi + Z}{\int_{z=0}^{z=Z} \frac{dz}{K_z}}$$

in which I is the cumulative infiltration, K_z is the hydraulic conductivity (m/s) at soil depth Z (m), $\Delta\psi$ is effective wetting front suction (m). In the numerical solution to this equation, hydraulic conductivity was set to decay exponentially with soil depth (Beven, 1984), and model output provides instantaneous and cumulative infiltration at any time. UFORE-Hydro also provides an infiltration formulation where hydraulic conductivity decays as a power function with soil depth fz (Wang et al., 2006): $K_z = K_O(1 - fz)^n$. Two power function options are linear where $n = 1$, and parabolic where $n = 2$, to match infiltration rates and processes observed in the field. The user selects the fraction of

the pervious watershed controlled by infiltration excess runoff and the remaining fraction using a direct incorporation of precipitation into soils until the water table reaches the surface. In all cases of infiltration, the model accounts for water table depth, and rain falling directly on saturated soils will be converted to surface runoff known as *saturation excess overland flow*. In urban areas, hydraulic conductivity values may be set to represent the impedance of compacted soils (Hamilton and Waddington, 1999; Pitt et al., 2003), and the case of precipitation rates exceeding infiltration will result in ponding and possible runoff known as *infiltration excess overland flow*. The model can dynamically move between these scenarios across time and across the topographic index (TI) distribution in space. Based on standard TOPMODEL theory, the water table rise will be allocated across all TI distributions. To capture tree effects on infiltration, the user might increase surface hydraulic conductivity values to represent the benefit tree growth has on reducing soil compaction. According to the soil compaction assessment of the study area, one part of the pervious area is set to generate infiltration excess overland flow and the rest is simulated to generate saturation excess overland flow (related to water table). In addition, slope information in each TI seem not to be used in the infiltration calculations.

- Water runoff is calculated based on standard urban runoff models such as SWMM (Storm Water Management Model), per unit watershed area. UFORE-Hydro uses TOPMODEL-based runoff routines, where streamflow (q_{total}) per unit watershed area (m/s) is the sum of unit area subsurface flow ($q_{subsurface}$), overland flow ($q_{overland}$) and impervious area runoff ($q_{impervious}$): $q_{total} = q_{subsurface} + q_{overland} + q_{impervious}$. The total overland flow ($q_{overland}$) is the sum of the saturation excess and infiltration excess overland flow from pervious areas. It is calculated based on TOPMODEL theory using:

$q_{overland} = (A_{sat}/A) * P_w$ where A_{sat}/A is the quotient of saturated to total hillslope area, and P_w is spatially weighted open-sky and below-canopy precipitation (m/s) for the appropriate watershed area. Impervious surfaces have no infiltration capacity and no water table exposure; hence, overland flow follows the TOPUrban application of Valeo and Moin (2000) when surface storages are maximized. The model estimates total impervious runoff to the channel based on the effective or connected impervious area, and assumes runoff from disconnected impervious area will run-on to pervious areas and infiltrate (default value of 65% of impervious areas being connected to a water transportation network in US urban areas is used in the software). Subsurface flow in UFORE-Hydro is water reaching the stream channel from the saturated subsurface zone. Subsurface flow is simulated in UFORE-Hydro using TOPMODEL concepts (Beven et al., 1995).

- The TI is used to map hydrologically similar areas, and soil depth-transmissivity relationships are simulated either as exponential or generalized power function (Ambroise et al., 1996). UFOREHydro assigns each form of the soil depth-transmissivity relationship a unique form of the TI and a unique form of the subsurface and overland flow equations. The hydrograph time series discharge, (q_{total}), at the watershed outlet is either generated

as a step-function or an optional channel routing function. Channel routing is modeled using a time-area convolution technique, where further upstream sections of the watershed are assigned longer flow routing times. Contrarily to *i-Tree Eco*, i-Tree Hydro allows to display total runoff outputs but also impervious and pervious runoff outputs which is very interesting to analyse the impact of increased impervious area.

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L. “The Value of Nature in Urban Life” Poster from INTERACT-Bio [8]

The Value of Nature in Urban Life poster was produced as a part of the INTERACT-Bio project. INTERACT-Bio is implemented by ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability and supported by the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU) through the International Climate Initiative (IKI).

THE VALUE OF NATURE IN URBAN LIFE

Nature provides diverse life-supporting and life-enhancing contributions to people in cities and towns. These gifts from nature make human life both possible and worth living. All cities critically depend on healthy interconnected ecosystems within and around them, so it is essential that nature is fully integrated into urban planning and development. There is a growing urgency for collective and large-scale action to protect the biodiversity in and around cities to prevent irreversible loss and damage to the natural systems we depend on.

- TANGIBLE THINGS FROM NATURE THAT MEET HUMAN NEEDS
- BENEFITS OBTAINED FROM THE PROCESSES THAT REGULATE THE NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- NATURE'S GIFTS THAT ENRICH OUR LIVES
- SUPPORTING THE LONG-TERM HEALTH OF THE PLANET

